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ON THE WELL-POSEDNESS OF DISCRETE VARIATIONAL PROBLEMS WITH EDGE-AWARE REGULARIZATION

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Abstract. *Edge-aware regularization is a cornerstone of variational methods in image processing and computer vision, typically implemented by weighting discrete gradients with functions dependent on local intensity differences. This paper investigates the phenomenon of scale inconsistency in standard weighting schemes of the form $w \propto \exp(-\beta|\Delta I|^2)$. We demonstrate that under grid refinement ($h \rightarrow 0$), such weights degenerate to a constant at a rate of $0(h^2)$, effectively reducing the regularizer to an isotropic Laplacian and nullifying the edge-preserving properties in the continuum limit. To address this, we propose a scale-consistent formulation utilizing discrete directional derivatives, $(I_{i+e_k} - I_i)/h$, within the weight argument. We provide a rigorous analysis proving the $-$ consistency of the modified discrete functional with a weighted anisotropic Dirichlet energy and establish $0(h)$ -convergence of the associated variational problems. Numerical validation on synthetic data and cardiac MRI segmentation (ACDC dataset) confirms that the proposed method ensures hyperparameter stability across varying physical resolutions, eliminating the need for resolution-dependent tuning.*

Keywords: *weighted Dirichlet energy; edge-aware regularization; scale consistency; discrete-to-continuum limit; inverse problems; $-$ convergence.*

1. Introduction

Variational methods and regularization techniques remain fundamental to applied mathematics, particularly in solving ill-posed inverse problems [1, 2, 3] and in image reconstruction [4, 5, 6]. The classical approach involves recovering an unknown field from noisy observations by minimizing an energy functional:

$$J(u) = \mathcal{D}(u, f) + \lambda \mathcal{R}(u), \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{D} is a data fidelity term and \mathcal{R} is a regularizer enforcing prior knowledge, such as smoothness.

While the standard Dirichlet energy $\int |\nabla u|^2 dx$ promotes global smoothness, it invariably blurs structural boundaries. To mitigate this, edge-aware regularization techniques were developed, suppressing smoothing across high-gradient regions. The seminal work on anisotropic diffusion by Perona and Malik [7] introduced diffusivity coefficients dependent on the image gradient magnitude. These concepts evolved into weighted Dirichlet energies and Total Variation (TV) methods [8, 9], which are now ubiquitous in both classical solvers and modern deep learning architectures [10, 11].

Despite their widespread adoption, the discretization of these functionals on grids with varying spatial resolution (pixel/voxel size) poses a subtle but critical challenge. In many implementations, the grid step h is implicitly treated as unity. Consequently, regularization weights are computed based on raw intensity differences between adjacent pixels. As we show in this work, this practice leads to scale inconsistency: models tuned on data with one physical resolution fail to generalize to data with a different resolution, a scenario common in multi-center medical imaging studies [12].

2. Scientific Problem

The central issue addressed in this study is the mathematical degeneracy of standard discrete edge-aware weights under grid refinement.

Consider a domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ discretized by a uniform grid Ω_h with mesh size h . Let I be a fixed continuous image (or guidance signal). In standard discrete implementations [13, 14, 15], the weight $w_{i,k}$ assigned to the edge between nodes i and $i+e_k$ is typically defined as a function of the absolute intensity difference:

$$w_{i,k}^{\text{std}} = g\left(|I_{i+e_k} - I_i|^2\right), \quad (2)$$

where $g(\cdot)$ is a decaying function, often the Gaussian kernel $g(s) = \exp(-\beta s)$. The intuition is that large differences imply an edge, reducing the weight and thus the smoothing.

However, from the perspective of numerical analysis, this formulation is ill-posed with respect to the limit $h \rightarrow 0$. For a differentiable function, the finite difference scales as $\mathcal{O}(h)$. Specifically, via Taylor expansion:

$$|I(x + he_k) - I(x)| \approx h|\partial_k I(x)|. \quad (3)$$

As $h \rightarrow 0$, the argument of the weight function tends to zero regardless of the local gradient magnitude, causing the weight $w_{i,k}^{\text{std}}$ to converge to its maximum value $g(0)$. This implies that the ‘‘edge-awareness’’ of the regularizer is an artifact

of the discretization step size rather than an intrinsic property of the image content. This scale dependence necessitates the recalibration of the sensitivity parameter β whenever the physical resolution changes, complicating model deployment and reproducibility.

3. Contributions

This paper provides a rigorous mathematical treatment of scale inconsistency and proposes a geometrically correct remedy. Our main contributions are:

Negative Result: We formally prove that standard edge-aware weights degenerate to a constant with an asymptotic error rate of $O(h^2)$ as $h \rightarrow 0$, transforming the anisotropic regularizer into an isotropic one in the continuum limit.

Proposed Remedy: We introduce a scale-consistent weight formulation based on discrete directional derivatives (normalized differences). This modification restores the correct continuum behavior.

Theoretical Analysis: We establish the consistency of the proposed discrete functional with the continuous weighted Dirichlet energy ($O(h)$ accuracy) and assert the Γ -convergence of the respective variational problems, ensuring convergence of minimizers.

Asymptotic Characterization: We analyze the joint limits of the grid step h and the sensitivity parameter σ , classifying the regimes of isotropic, anisotropic, and TV-like behavior.

Numerical Validation: The theoretical findings are corroborated by synthetic resolution-sweep tests and a real-world cardiac MRI segmentation experiment, demonstrating superior robustness to resolution changes compared to the baseline.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1. Preliminaries and Notation

Let $\Omega \subset R^d$ ($d = 2, 3$) be a bounded Lipschitz domain. We introduce a sequence of uniform grids Ω_h with spacing $h > 0$. Grid nodes are denoted by $x_i = ih$, $i \in Z^d$.

For a grid function $u: \Omega_h \rightarrow R$, the forward difference operator in the direction of the basis vector e_k is defined as:

$$D_k^+ u_i = \frac{u_{i+e_k} - u_i}{h}. \quad (4)$$

The discrete L^2 -norm is defined as $|u|_{2,h}^2 = h^d \sum_i |u_i|^2$.

We consider the discrete weighted Dirichlet energy:

$$E_h[u] = h^d \sum_i \sum_{k=1}^d w_{i,k} |D_k^+ u_i|^2, \quad (5)$$

where $w_{i,k}$ are non-negative weights derived from a guidance image.

4.2. Analysis of Standard Weight Degeneration

The standard weight formulation is given by:

$$w_{i,k}^{\text{std}} = \exp\left(-\beta|I_{i+e_k} - I_i|^2\right) + w_{\min}, \quad w_{\min} > 0. \quad (6)$$

Proposition 1 (Asymptotic Degeneration). Assume $I \in C^3(\overline{\Omega})$. Then, for any edge $(i, i+e_k)$, the following expansion holds as $h \rightarrow 0$:

$$w_{i,k}^{\text{std}} = (1 + w_{\min}) - \beta h^2 |\partial_k I(\bar{x})|^2 + O(h^4), \quad (7)$$

where \bar{x} is the midpoint of the edge. Consequently, $w_{i,k}^{\text{std}} \rightarrow 1 + w_{\min}$ uniformly.

Proof.

We expand I around $\overline{x_{l,k}} = x_i + \frac{h}{2} e_k$:

$$I_{i+e_k} - I_i = h \partial_k I(\overline{x_{l,k}}) + \frac{h^3}{24} \partial_k^3 I(\xi). \quad (8)$$

Squaring this expression yields:

$$|I_{i+e_k} - I_i|^2 = h^2 |\partial_k I(\overline{x_{l,k}})|^2 + O(h^4). \quad (9)$$

Let $t = \beta |I_{i+e_k} - I_i|^2$. Since $t = O(h^2)$, we use the expansion $e^{-t} = 1 - t + O(t^2)$:

$$w_{i,k}^{\text{std}} = (1 - \beta h^2 |\partial_k I|^2 + O(h^4)) + w_{\min}. \quad (10)$$

This completes the proof.

This result implies that the contrast of the weights — the difference between weights at edges and in flat regions — vanishes quadratically: $\Delta W \sim O(h^2)$.

4.3. The Proposed Remedy: Scale-Consistent Weights

To ensure a non-trivial continuum limit, the argument of the weight function must approximate the gradient magnitude $|\nabla I|^2$, not the difference $|\Delta I|^2$. Furthermore, to handle noise and discontinuities rigorously in the continuum limit, we adopt the standard practice of using a mollified guidance image $I_\rho = G_\rho * I$, where G_ρ is a Gaussian kernel with fixed width $\rho > 0$.

We define the **scale-consistent weights** as:

$$w_{i,k}^* = \exp\left(-\beta |D_k^+ I_{\rho,i}|^2\right) + w_{\min} = \exp\left(-\beta \left| \frac{I_{\rho,i+e_k} - I_{\rho,i}}{h} \right|^2\right) + w_{\min}. \quad (11)$$

Theorem 2 (Consistency). Let $I_\rho \in C^2(\overline{\Omega})$. The discrete functional $E_h^*[u]$ with weights $w_{i,k}^*$ is consistent with the continuous anisotropic energy

$$E[u] = \int_{\Omega} \sum_{k=1}^d w_k^*(x) |\partial_k u(x)|^2 dx, \quad \text{with } w_k^*(x) = \exp\left(-\beta |\partial_k I_\rho(x)|^2\right) + w_{min}, \quad (12)$$

satisfying $|E_h^*[u_h] - E[u]| = O(h)$ for any $u \in C^2(\overline{\Omega})$, where is the grid restriction of u .

Proof Sketch.

Since is smooth, the discrete derivative $D_k^+ I_{\rho,i} = \partial_k I_\rho(\bar{x}) + O(h)$ converges to the continuous derivative. Since the exponential function is Lipschitz continuous on bounded intervals, $|w_{i,k}^* - w_k^*(\bar{x})| = O(h)$. The convergence of the Riemann sum to the integral introduces another $O(h)$ error, resulting in a total error of $O(h)$.

Γ -Convergence.

Beyond pointwise consistency, variational correctness requires Γ -convergence [16, 17, 18, 19]. Under coercivity assumptions (e.g., Dirichlet boundary conditions) [20], it can be shown that the sequence of functionals E_h^* Γ -converges to E in the $L^2(\Omega)$ topology. This ensures that minimizers u^* of the discrete problems u_h^* converge to the minimizer of the continuous problem.

4.4. Two-Parameter Asymptotic Analysis

In practice, the sensitivity parameter is often denoted as σ , where $\beta = 1/\sigma^2$. We analyze the joint behavior of h and σ .

Regime 1: Fixed Sensitivity ($\sigma = \text{const}$ independent of h). This corresponds to the correct anisotropic limit derived in Theorem 2. Regime 2: Vanishing Sensitivity ($\sigma \rightarrow 0$). As $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, the weights approximate a characteristic function indicating edges. This approaches a Total Variation-like regime but may introduce numerical stiffness. Regime 3: Standard Scaling ($\sigma \propto 1$). If one uses standard weights without normalization, effectively $\beta_{\text{eff}} \propto h^2$, which corresponds to $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$. In this regime, weights converge to unity, and the model becomes isotropic. Recommendation: The parameter must have physical units (e.g., intensity/length) and be fixed independently of the grid step h .

5. Numerical Experiments

5.1. Synthetic “Resolution Sweep” Test

Setup:

We generated a 1D synthetic edge profile $I(x) = \tanh(x/\delta)$ with width $\delta = 0.1$ on domain $[-1, 1]$.

We generated grids with spacings $h \in \{2^{-4}, 2^{-5}, \dots, 2^{-9}\}$.

We computed the weight contrast $\Delta W = \frac{W_{\text{flat}}}{W_{\text{edge}}}$, where $\overline{W_{\text{edge}}}$ and $\overline{W_{\text{flat}}}$ are average weights in the flat and transition regions, respectively.

5.2. Cardiac MRI Segmentation (Physical Scale Transfer)

Dataset:

We utilized the ACDC (Automated Cardiac Diagnosis Challenge) dataset [21, 22], comprising 100 patient MRI scans. A key feature of this dataset is the heterogeneity in physical resolution: pixel spacing varies from 1.37 mm to 1.68 mm.

Methodology:

A U-Net architecture [23] was trained to segment the left ventricle. The loss function included a regularization term on the softmax probability maps. We compared two strategies:

Baseline + StdWeight: Standard weights based on raw differences, fixed across all images.

Baseline + ScaleCons: Proposed scale-consistent weights (normalized by pixel size from metadata), fixed in physical units (mm^2).

Training used the Adam optimizer [24] with fixed hyperparameters. Evaluation metrics included the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Expected Calibration Error (ECE) [25].

6. Results

6.1. Synthetic Test Results

Table 1 illustrates the dependence of weight contrast on grid resolution.

The standard weights exhibit a rapid collapse in contrast (approximately factor of 4 per halving of h , consistent with $O(h^2)$). At fine resolutions, the standard regularizer fails to distinguish edges from flat regions. In contrast, the proposed method maintains a stable contrast ≈ 0.416 , demonstrating scale invariance.

6.2. MRI Segmentation Results

Performance on the ACDC test set (5-fold cross-validation):

Baseline (No Reg): Dice = 0.864 ± 0.011 .

+ StdWeight: Dice = 0.869 ± 0.012 . The improvement is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.09$) due to inconsistent regularization strength across patients with different resolutions.

+ ScaleCons: Dice = 0.886 ± 0.008 . The proposed method yields a statistically significant improvement ($p < 0.001$) and reduces the Expected Calibration Error from 0.047 to 0.038.

7. Discussion

The results highlights a fundamental flaw in naive discretizations of variational models: the conflation of discretization parameters (grid step) with model parameters (edge sensitivity).

Interpretation of Degeneration:

The quadratic decay $\Delta w \sim O(h^2)$ explains a common practical frustration: hyperparameters tuned on low-resolution prototype data often perform poorly on

high-resolution production data, leading to “oversmoothing.” The model effectively degenerates into isotropic diffusion as resolution increases.

The Role of Mollification:

While our theoretical analysis assumes $I_\rho \in C^2$, this is not merely a technical convenience. In applied settings, computing gradients on raw noisy data is unstable. Pre-smoothing (guidance) is standard in edge-preserving filters (e.g., Guided Filter [13]). Our analysis shows that this step is also necessary for the existence of a well-defined continuum limit.

8. Conclusion

This work presented a comprehensive analysis of scale inconsistency in discrete edge-aware regularization.

We proved that standard weights based on raw intensity differences degenerate as $O(h^2)$ under grid refinement.

We proposed a theoretically sound remedy using discrete directional derivatives, ensuring $O(h)$ -consistency with the anisotropic continuum model.

Experimental validation confirmed that the proposed scale-consistent weights provide superior robustness and accuracy in multi-resolution medical imaging tasks.

We recommend that all implementations of weighted Dirichlet energies or similar variational regularizers explicitly normalize intensity differences by the grid step to ensure mathematical well-posedness and practical robustness.

References

1. Engl HW, Hanke M, Neubauer A. *Regularization of Inverse Problems*. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers; 1996. doi: 10.1007/978-94-009-1740-8
2. Vogel CR. *Computational Methods for Inverse Problems*. Philadelphia: SIAM; 2002. doi: 10.1137/1.9780898717570
3. Tikhonov AN, Arsenin VY. *Solutions of Ill-Posed Problems*. Washington: Winston; 1977.
4. Chambolle A. An algorithm for total variation minimization and applications. *J Math Imaging Vis*. 2004;20(1-2):89-97. doi: 10.1023/B:JMIV.0000011325.36760.1e
5. Natterer F, Wübbeling F. *Mathematical Methods in Image Reconstruction*. Philadelphia: SIAM; 2001. doi: 10.1137/1.9780898718324
6. Scherzer O, Grasmair M, Grossauer H, Haltmeier M, Lenzen F. *Variational Methods in Imaging*. New York: Springer; 2009. doi: 10.1007/978-0-387-69277-7
7. Perona P, Malik J. Scale-space and edge detection using anisotropic diffusion. *IEEE Trans Pattern Anal Mach Intell*. 1990;12(7):629-39. doi: 10.1109/34.56205

8. Rudin LI, Osher S, Fatemi E. Nonlinear total variation based noise removal algorithms. *Physica D*. 1992;60(1-4):259-268. doi: 10.1016/0167-2789(92)90242-F
9. Ambrosio L, Fusco N, Pallara D. *Functions of Bounded Variation and Free Discontinuity Problems*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2000.
10. Litjens G, et al. A survey on deep learning in medical image analysis. *Med Image Anal*. 2017;42:60-88. doi: 10.1016/j.media.2017.07.005
11. He K, Zhang X, Ren S, Sun J. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. Las Vegas; 2016. p. 770-8. doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2016.90
12. Modersitzki J. *Numerical Methods for Image Registration*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2004.
13. He K, Sun J, Tang X. Guided image filtering. *IEEE Trans Pattern Anal Mach Intell*. 2013;35(6):1397-409. doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2012.213
14. Kornprobst P, Deriche R, Aubert G. Image Sequence Analysis via Partial Differential Equations. *Journal of Mathematical Imaging and Vision*. 1999;11:5-26. DOI: 10.1023/A:1008318126505
15. Singer A, Wu HT. Spectral convergence of the connection Laplacian from random samples. *Inf Inference*. 2017;6(1):58-123. doi: 10.1093/imaiai/iaw016
16. Braides A. *-Convergence for Beginners*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2002.
17. Dal Maso G. *An Introduction to -Convergence*. Boston: Birkhäuser; 1993. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4612-0327-8
18. Bauschke HH, Combettes PL. *Convex Analysis and Monotone Operator Theory in Hilbert Spaces*. Cham: Springer; 2017. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-48311-5
19. Braides A, Defranceschi A. *Homogenization of Multiple Integrals*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 1998.
20. Evans LC. *Partial Differential Equations*. Providence: American Mathematical Society; 2010.
21. Bernard O, et al. Deep learning techniques for automatic MRI cardiac segmentation. *IEEE Trans Med Imaging*. 2018;37(11):2319-31. doi: 10.1109/TMI.2018.2837502
22. ACDC Challenge. *Automated Cardiac Diagnosis Challenge [Internet]*. [cited 2026 Feb 14]. Available from: <https://www.creatis.insa-lyon.fr/Challenge/acdc/>.

23. Ronneberger O, Fischer P, Brox T. U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. In: *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention — MICCAI 2015*. Cham: Springer; 2015. p. 234-41. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-24574-4_28

24. Kingma DP, Ba J. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*; 2015 May 7-9; San Diego, CA. 2015.

25. Guo C, Pleiss G, Sun Y, Weinberger KQ. On calibration of modern neural networks. In: *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*. PMLR; 2017. p. 1321-30.

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ACHIEVEMENTS AND GOALS OF MATHEMATICS IN UNDERSTANDING THE WORLD OF ECOLOGY

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Keywords: *mathematical models of ecology and ways to improve them.*

1 Justification of the choice of the topic and the purpose of the study

Mathematics, the most powerful tool created by humans, allows us to study the specific and diverse phenomena of the natural world. This article presents the history of the application of mathematics in ecology. In these sections, the author will share the following theoretical ideas: about the achievements and goals of mathematics in understanding the world of ecology; about the ecology of the external world; about the ecology of the internal and external world of humans; about the ecology of the soul and the spiritual world of living beings; and about the ecology caused by natural, random, and human factors. The ecology of these sections is a relevant issue in the 21st century. The purpose of this research is to express our opinion on unresolved problems, the “ecology of the soul,” and ways to improve existing mathematical models in ecology. The greatest teacher of mankind is nature. We learn from nature and get what we need to live. For example, the rotation of a round log and Euclid’s geometry led to the invention of wheels. The invention of the wheel contributed to the development of mechanical engineering. The movement of logs down a river and Archimedes’ law, as well as human intelligence, led to the invention of boats and ships, which are essential for our lives. The study of the dragonfly’s takeoff and landing led to the invention of helicopters. The takeoff and landing of an airplane are modeled after the eagle. The movement of a tracked tractor is an example of the movement of a millipede. A submarine is an example of a dolphin. No matter how advanced modern technology is, it is an example of nature. Life is about discovering the mysteries of nature, learning to extract from it and give to it. Recognizing the processes that occur in nature is the path of modeling. This path has its roots in the minds of great thinkers and scientists such as Aristotle, Al-Farabi, Al-Khwarizmi, Newton, Leibniz, Euler, and many others. In the 17th century, Blaise Pascal expressed his frustration with human helplessness.

In 1900, David Hilbert, a participant in the Second International Congress of Mathematicians, stated: “Mathematics is the foundation of all exact natural sciences.” In his *Critique of Pure Reason* (1781), Immanuel Kant reached a more comforting conclusion by recognizing all the axioms and theorems of mathematics as true. Kant stated, “The study of nature will only contain science in its proper sense to the extent that mathematics can be applied to it.” The paths taken by these thinkers and luminaries in science have led us to mathematical modeling. A mathematical model is a set of results of creative work and logical mathematical thinking based on numerous experiments, fundamental laws of nature, and the intuition of the human mind in the study of processes occurring in nature, living organisms, physics, chemistry, continuous media, deformable solids, geology, the Earth’s core, outer space, ecology, and economics. The accuracy of this model is a testament to the numerous experiments and the intuition and logical mathematical thinking of the human mind in the study of natural processes. Process models can be divided into three main types: transport models based on physical and chemical principles; population balance models based on population size; and empirical models used to fit experimental data. Mathematical models can be linear, quasi-linear, or nonlinear, depending on the complexity of the natural process being studied. Analytical and numerical methods are available for studying these models. The scope of these methods is determined by the physical, mechanical, physical-chemical, biophysical, biochemical, and ecological properties and parameters of the process being studied. Today, mathematical modeling is well-developed in all fields of science and serves humanity, but the goal that mathematics sets for itself is limitless. There are still many unsolved problems in mathematical modeling.

2 Definition of the research object

The term “ecology” was first coined by the German biologist Ernst Haeckel in 1866 in his book “*General Morphology of Organisms*.” In biology, ecology refers to the study of the relationships between organisms and their interactions with their environment. Ecology consists of five sections: ecology of the external world (outer space, Earth’s atmosphere, caused by earthquakes, lightning, tsunamis, biological and nuclear testing, Earth, air, river, lake, sea, and ocean waters, plants, oil and gas extraction sectors, ore mining and sorting sectors, coal mining sectors, copper, iron, cast iron, silver, and gold smelting factories, industrial sectors for the production of light, heavy, and agricultural machinery of all kinds, electric power sectors of all kinds, construction sectors of all kinds, manufacturing and agricultural sectors, and technological sectors); ecology of the inner world of man, mind, reason, consciousness, foresight, humility, feelings, memory, faith, honor, soul, spirits, nervous system, psychology, human qualities); ecology of the internal and external organs of man; ecology of the inner world of all other

living beings; ecology of the internal and external organs of all other living beings. Ecology can be divided into three main sections. Ecology caused by natural factors (solar space hurricanes, wind, drought, volcanic eruptions, rock erosion, dust storms, wind-borne sea salt particles in the air, drying of water droplets in the air, decomposition of dead organisms, bacteria that cause various diseases, fungal spores, pollen from certain plants, cosmic dust from the remains of meteorites that burned in the atmosphere, asteroid collisions with Earth, magnetic storms, global warming, and erosion of the western bank of a river due to the Coriolis force). Ecology caused by random factors (the city of Spitak that disappeared from the face of the earth, the restored city of Tashkent, earthquakes in Turkey and Syria, destruction of civilian buildings and industrial facilities caused by earthquakes and tsunamis, as well as lightning, forest fires caused by lightning strikes, solar fires caused by concave mirrors, destruction of roads due to soil degradation, and environmental degradation caused by a very strong hurricane that carried away a lake, including the fish that were swimming in the lake). Anthropogenic ecology (all types of ecology caused by a person's inability to receive from nature and give it back, i.e., all types of artificial sources of environmental pollution). The most dangerous of these ecological systems is the human-made ecology. The most dangerous of these ecological systems is the human-made ecology. I will provide examples to support my opinion. From August 29, 1949, to 1989, 468 nuclear tests were conducted at the Semipalatinsk Test Site, of which 116 were open-air tests conducted on land and in the air. The total yield of the nuclear weapons tested in the air and on the ground at the Semipalatinsk Test Site was 2,500 times greater than the yield of the atomic bomb dropped on Hiroshima in 1945. Three hundred square kilometers of land will continue to pose a danger to all living things for a long time to come. The consequences are still not fully understood. The environmental problems of the Caspian and Aral Seas, as well as Lake Balkhash, have not been resolved. Today, as a result of the nuclear missile war, industrial, civilian, and other energy facilities are being destroyed and turned into ruins. People who have been deprived of housing, light, water, and heat, as well as food. Children, who have lost their parents forever, and parents who have lost their children forever. The ecology of the inner world of children and parents has been destroyed by this war. The ecology of these sections is a pressing issue of our time. Environmentalists are raising a large-scale problem ("The Global Environmental Problem"), which could be a barrier to this undesirable problem. Today, there are numerous environmental journals and articles, textbooks, books, and monographs. Ecology, as a part of biology, has been included in the curricula of technical universities. The community hopes that future engineers will be able to solve problems in all areas of life in the country and the global community. The methods of solving these problems are the current issues of the 21st century.

3 Critical analysis of existing works

Apparently, the 21st century will be the century of ecology. The future development of humanity will be closely related to the development of this particular science, which studies the mechanisms of ecosystem pollution. An analysis of existing works has shown that the influence of human, random, and natural factors, as well as the influence of the inner world of humans and ecosystems, has not been sufficiently studied. The ecology of the inner world of humans and the ecology of their internal and external organs have not been studied. The dynamic impact on the process of ecosystem variability has not been sufficiently studied. The ecology of the inner world and the ecology of the internal and external organs of all other living beings have not yet been studied. Aspects of spiritual education were not taken into account in the mathematical modeling. Although everyone knows that spiritual education is a field of science that encompasses religion and spirituality, nature conservation, scientific communities, and environmental sustainability. At the core of this science is the spiritual wealth of every nation. The goal of the scientific community is to provide spiritual education for individuals. Today, human madness poses the greatest threat to ecosystems. "The world is infinite, but human madness is boundless," said Albert Einstein. Life is a struggle. There is a ruthless struggle for life. The methods of struggle are limitless. There are information, psychological, metrological, economic, biological, sabotage, armed, and nuclear wars. There is no type to stop at the decision of the UN judges. We are at the beginning of a century in which the scales of God and the scales of the inner world of man, which are necessary for all the most complex phenomena of the world and which maintain the balance of creation, have become unbalanced. Oh, man! The maintenance of balance in the universe lies in our inner world and in our responsibility to nature and to each other. The value of our ancestors' academic school, which we have inherited, is in crisis today. As for the ecological purity of the provider of our bodies, I cannot say that it is absolutely pure. In order to maintain our bodies, the soul is also in a state of ecological stress. In our "Report" book, the good and bad deeds of the soul are recorded. After the death of the body, the accumulated rewards and sins of the soul are weighed on the scales of God. The weight reading is an indicator of the "Ecology of the Soul." As for the ecological purity of the provider of our bodies, I cannot say that it is absolutely pure. In order to maintain our bodies, the soul is also in a state of ecological stress. In our "Report" book, the good and bad deeds of the soul are recorded. After the death of the body, the accumulated rewards and sins of the soul are weighed on the scales of God. The weight reading is an indicator of the "Ecology of the Soul." As for faith, there is no place for it in this treacherous world. The ecology of the human inner world is not clean. If we talk about the ecology of the human body's internal and external organs, I wouldn't say it's transparent. The reasons include unhealthy lifestyles,

environmental pollution, food contamination, improper medical treatment, and drug addiction. I wouldn't be wrong if I said that seventy out of a hundred people suffer from chronic diseases. Half of these seventy people suffer from at least two chronic diseases, such as high blood pressure, diabetes, bile duct, kidneys, liver, heart, lungs, and stomach. It would be desirable to have a mathematical model for disease prediction and treatment that can predict the aforementioned pain and provide effective treatments, taking into account all human factors.

4 Mathematical problems of the ecosystem

The future of human development is inextricably linked to the development of environmental science, which explores the mechanisms of world pollution. In the 21st century, the global ecosystem problem has shifted from the "soil-groundwater- body of water" system to the "human inner world-human internal and external organs-human inner world of all other living beings-human internal and external organs of all other living beings-human-random-natural factors" system. The future of human development is inextricably linked to the development of environmental science, which studies the mechanisms of world pollution. The global problem of the ecosystem in the 21st century is the transition from the soil-groundwater-water body system to the ecology of the inner world and the ecology of the internal and external organs of humans, the ecology of the inner world and the ecology of the internal and external organs of living beings, the ecology that is affected by human, random, and natural factors. The world's number one pressing issue in the 21st century is the "Global Economic Problem." This problem encompasses the availability of water and land resources necessary for the survival of humanity and other living beings, as well as the vitality of all fields of science, clean technology, engineering, transportation, energy, construction, and the natural resources of the Earth's interior. If this issue remains unresolved, it is futile to discuss the aforementioned environmental concerns. The global problem of the ecosystem can only be solved by combining the following sciences: mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology, medicine, new technology, artificial intelligence, and improving existing mathematical models of ecology; supercomputer modeling; the global problem of economics and models of spiritual education. When I was thinking about the problem, I came up with the fundamental work "The Mathematical Theory of the Struggle for Existence" by the outstanding mathematician V. Volterra [1] and the general dynamic behavior of the Lotka-Volterra economic system [2]. The question arose as to how I could use these works. My question was answered by the voice of my inner world. According to the "voice of my inner world", the structural model of the "global ecosystem problem" consists of: a reference information model of the "predator", which includes radiation exposure, ionizing radiation, nuclear radiation, military conflicts, human madness, immorality, arrogance, irresponsibility, lust,

jealousy, illiteracy, ignorance, inability to foresee early and random events, natural disasters, climate change, and environmental factors; reference information model “victim”, which includes the ecosystem of the external world and the internal world of all living beings and their internal and external organs; reference information mathematical model of the “treatment fund” including environmentalists and their work, the ShakeAlert system in the United States, smart sensors for predicting fires in Ecuador, IoT sensors for preventing pollution of the city’s water supply in China, artificial intelligence for predicting forest fires, and the inner and spiritual world of humans. The mathematical language of these models is systems of differential and integro-differential equations of all kinds (ordinary, stochastic, and partial differential equations), given in specific initial and boundary conditions. The combination of these three models represents a hypercomputer model of a global ecosystem problem. If we conduct research in this area, we will be able to create a hypercomputer model of the global ecosystem problem.

5 Conclusions

If we delve into the global ecosystem problem, the ecosystem problem not only serves as an arena for the application of mathematical methods, but it also becomes an increasingly significant source of new mathematical challenges and a source of development for all fields of science. I wish you all the best of luck in your search for a solution to the global ecosystem problem.

References

1. *Volterra V.: Mathematical Theory of the Struggle for Existence, UFN, 1928, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 13-34.*
2. *Kamimura A., Burani G. F. and Franca H. M., The Economic System Seen As A Living System: A Lotka-Volterra Framework//E: CO Vol. 13 № 3 2011 pp. 80-93.*

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RED-LISTED PLANTS OF BADHYZ: BIOLOGY, ECOLOGY, CONSERVATION ISSUES

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Abstract. *The article contains scientific essays on 14 species of protected medicinal plants of Badhyza included in the Red Book of Turkmenistan, indicating the status and category, the significance of the taxon in preserving the gene pool, in the field of application (folk and scientific medicine), distribution, habitats, population size and trends, biological and ecological characteristics, limiting factors, data on introduction and cultivation, and protective measures that have been taken and are needed. The biodiversity of the medicinal flora of Badhyz currently comprises 644 plant species.*

Keywords: *natural reserves, Badhyz, biological characteristics, Turkmen folk medicine.*

Today, the biodiversity of the medicinal flora of Badhyz is represented by 644 plant species. Of these, 14 plants are listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan [4]. During expeditions organised in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve and adjacent territories in 2020-2025, the bioecological features of protected medicinal plants were studied and their natural reserves were determined using a generally accepted methodology [5]. Below is information about the Red Book plants of Badhyz, studied by the authors based on their own observations.

Research results.

Badhyz curly dock (*Atraphaxis badhyzi* Kult.) is a shrub of the buckwheat family (*Polygonaceae* Juss.) with a height of 30-80 cm. It is a xerophyte. It reproduces by seeds. Its germination rate is low. It blooms and bears fruit in April–May. It grows at an altitude of 200-400 m above sea level, on red sandstone outcrops, loamy and sandy loam, often gravelly serozems [3; 6].

In terms of status, it belongs to category III vulnerable species. The population occupies the northern border of the range. The taxon is important for the preservation of the gene pool as a medicinal and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badhyz: Menlikhan, Hojagar, Yeroylanduz, Kagyzlysuyji, Serhetabat, Galaymor. It is endemic to Turkmenistan [2-4; 6].

Badhyz curly hair is one of the rare woody plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. Part of the area is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4].

It occurs at a density of 5-12 specimens per km² or in sparse groups. In 2025, 56 specimens were recorded in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve on an area of 2000 m².

The main limiting factors are poor seed renewal and grazing. Necessary conservation measures: compliance with the protection regime in the species' habitats.

Bryonia monoica Aitch. et Hemsl. is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Cucurbitaceae Juss. family with a vine length of 2-4 m. The plant has a thickened root and climbing stems. It is a mesophyte. It blooms in May and bears fruit in June. It reproduces by seeds and vegetatively (tuberous roots). It grows at an altitude of 400-800 m above sea level, on fixed sands, among shrubs and between the ruins of an ancient fortress [3; 6].

According to its status, it belongs to category III vulnerable species. The taxon's significance in preserving the gene pool: Badhyz-South Karakum species. Used in folk medicine.

The plant is found in Badhyz: Yarlyankala Fortress, Nardivanly, Damdam. In April 2025, we found and recorded new habitats of the species in the Nardivanli and Damdam gorges for the first time. Forty-five specimens were recorded in a population covering 0.5 hectares [1].

Monotropa uniflora is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. It is protected in the Badhyz State Reserve. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4].

The main limiting factors are the cutting of shrubs, grazing and the collection of roots for medicinal purposes. Necessary protection measures: in areas of distribution, prohibit the cutting of shrubs and the digging up of roots.

Afghan fig (*Ficus afghanistanica* Warb.) is a bushy tree or multi-stemmed branched shrub 2-5 m tall belonging to the mulberry family (*Moraceae* Link). It is a mesophyte. It flowers in April–May and bears fruit in August–September. The species is drought- and heat-resistant and undemanding in terms of soil. It propagates by cuttings, root suckers and shoots. It grows at an altitude of 600-1200 m above sea level, on dry rocky, shallow soil and gravelly slopes and in gorges.

It belongs to category IV, rare species. The taxon's importance in preserving the gene pool: one of two species of fig in the flora of Turkmenistan, found in a very limited area. The Badhyz and East Kopetdag populations are unique to Central Asia.

The plant is found in Badhyz: the Gezgyadik Range, the Inzirli Gorge, Turan-gali [3; 4; 6].

Afghan fig is one of the rare woody plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are limited. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. According to estimates for 2024-2025, 325 bushes were recorded in Badhyz. Part of the population is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are the destruction of natural habitats and the death of young shoots and bushes in extremely cold winters. Necessary protection measures: strict compliance with the reserve regime.

Astragalus vassilzenkoi Berdyev is a perennial herbaceous plant of the *Fabaceae* Lindl. family with a well-developed tall (90-130 cm) straight stem, branched from the middle and covered with simple white hairs. Ephemeroïd. Xerophyte. Propagates by seeds. Blooms in June-August. Grows at an altitude of 500-700 m above sea level, on grassy sandy slopes of hills with fescue-sedge-large-grass formation [6].

According to its status, it belongs to category III vulnerable species. The taxon's significance in preserving the gene pool: representative of a polytypic genus, with a distinct position within it. Medicinal and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badhyz: Pynhancheshme, Kepele. Endemic to Badhyz and Karabilya [2; 4; 6].

Astragalus vasilchenkoi is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. Populations are small. Individual specimens are found. In 2025, 27 specimens were recorded in the Kepele tract on an area of 2,000 m², and 23 specimens were recorded in the Pynhancheshme tract on the same area. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. Part of the range is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are intensive grazing and haymaking. Necessary protection measures: strict compliance with the protection regime. Restriction of grazing and haymaking.

Astragalus kuschkensis Boriss. is a perennial stemless plant 20-25 cm tall of the *Fabaceae* Lindl. family. It has a powerful root. It is ephemeroïd and xerophytic. It reproduces by seeds. It flowers and bears fruit in April-June [6]. It grows at an altitude of 400-600 m above sea level, on shallow, gravelly slopes, in pistachio groves or among couch grass and mixed grass vegetation.

According to its status, it belongs to category III vulnerable species. The taxon's significance in preserving the gene pool: Endemic to Turkmenistan with a narrow disjunctive range [2; 4]. Medicinal and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badkhyz: Gezgyadik, Mount Dynya, Yarylankala [3; 4].

Astragalus kushkinskyi is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. In 2025, isolated specimens were found in the Gezgyadik Gorge (no more than 27 specimens/km²). It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. Part of the range is protected in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are drought and livestock grazing. Necessary conservation measures: strict compliance with the protection regime in places of growth. Restriction of grazing.

Malacocarpus crithmifolius (Retz.) C. A. Mey. is a shrub of the *Peganaceae* family (Tiegh.) with a height of 80-120 cm. The lower part of the trunk is woody, covered with whitish bark on younger branches and brownish-grey bark on older branches. Annual shoots are bare, thin, twisted, and spreading. The fruit is berry-like, brownish-red, and rounded. It grows at an altitude of 800-1200 m above sea level, in rock crevices, dwarf pine forests, near springs, on clayey and sandy soils, among shrubs. It flowers from May to September and bears fruit from June to October [4; 6].

It is classified as a vulnerable species (category III). The taxon's importance in preserving the gene pool: a relict, sharply isolated representative of the Irano-Turanian genus. Medicinal and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badkhyz: Serhetabat, Nardivanly, Gezgyadik [4; 6].

The soft-fruited critmolist is one of the rare plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. In 2025, 11 specimens were recorded in the Serhetabada tract. Five specimens of the plant were recorded in the Nardivanly Gorge. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. Part of the range is protected in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are drought, water erosion, grazing, and shrub cutting. Necessary protection measures: strict observance of the reserve regime. Prohibition of shrub cutting.

Badkhyz pistachio (*Pistacia badkhyzi* K. P. Popov) is a deciduous tree 4-6 m tall belonging to the *Anacardiaceae* family. It is a dioecious, wind-pollinated plant. It is xerophytic. It flowers in March–April and bears fruit in July–September [6]. It reproduces by seeds. It grows at an altitude of 400-600 m above sea level, on forest slopes, on dense sandy soil among pistachio trees.

It belongs to category IV of rare species. The taxon's importance in preserving the gene pool: one of two species of the genus *Pistacia* L. It has important scientific and practical significance. Medicinal and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badkhyz: the Shorsafid ridge, east of the village of Serkhetchi. The only known location [4; 6].

The Badkhyz pistachio is one of the rare plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. It is rare, with a total of no more than 50 specimens. The population

is declining. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. It is protected in the Serhetabad section of the Mary Forestry.

The main limiting factors are natural factors (drought, poor pollination, etc.). Necessary protection measures: strict compliance with the protection regime.

Smyrniun cordifolium Boiss. is a perennial herbaceous plant of the *Apiaceae* Lindl. family, 30-50 cm tall. It blooms in April and bears fruit in May. It reproduces by seeds. It grows at an altitude of 400-800 m above sea level, in river valleys and on shallow slopes [4; 6].

According to its status, it belongs to category V of insufficiently studied species. The taxon's significance in preserving the gene pool: the species occupies the northern border of its range. Medicinal and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badkhyz: in the vicinity of the village of Serkhetchi and the valley of the Kushka River. This is the only known location of this species in Central Asia [4].

Smirnia cordifolia is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. In 2025, seven specimens were recorded in the Kushka River valley. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. The species is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4].

The main limiting factors are drought and intensive grazing. Necessary conservation measures: restriction of grazing, planting in areas of occurrence.

Ferula foetida (Bunge) Regel is a perennial herbaceous plant of the celery family, 100-120 cm tall. Monocarpic. Ephemeroïd. Xerophyte. It blooms in March–May and bears fruit in May–June. It grows at an altitude of 150-300 m above sea level in forest, clayey-gravelly, and sandy deserts [4; 6].

According to its status, it belongs to Category III vulnerable species. The taxon's importance in preserving the gene pool: Irano-South Turanian species. Medicinal, fodder and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badkhyz: Yeroylanduze [3].

Ferula stinking is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. In 2025, 127 specimens were recorded in the Eryulanduze tract on an area of 2,000 m². In 2025, seven specimens were recorded in the Kushka River valley. The species is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. Part of the range is protected in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are the collection of plants for medicinal purposes. Necessary protection measures: prohibit uncontrolled collection of the plant.

Phagnalon androssovii B. Fedtsch. is a semi-shrub or perennial herbaceous plant of the *Asteraceae* family up to 40 cm tall. Seed reproduction is weak. Mesophyte. It blooms in April-May and bears fruit in May-June. It grows at an altitude of 600-800 m above sea level, on gravelly slopes [4; 6].

It is classified as a category II endangered species. The taxon's significance in preserving the gene pool: a relict of Mediterranean subtropical flora. Medicinal and fodder plant.

The plant is found in Badhyz: Inzirlicheshme [3; 4].

Androsov's faganlon is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. In 2025, 25 specimens were recorded in the Inzirlicheshme gorge. The species is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. Part of the range is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are slope erosion and grazing. Necessary protection measures: strict compliance with the protection regime.

Siebera nana (DC.) Bornm. is an annual herbaceous plant of the *Asteraceae* family, 3-10 cm tall. It reproduces by seeds. It blooms and bears fruit in April–May. It does not grow in dry years. Xerophyte. Grows at an altitude of 400-600 m above sea level, on dry, shallow, gravelly slopes [6].

According to its status, it belongs to category IV rare species. Significance of the taxon in preserving the gene pool: Eastern Mediterranean species. Representative of a monotypic genus. Medicinal plant.

The plant is found in Badhyz: Pulhatyn [3; 4].

Zibera dwarf is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. In 2025, 37 specimens were recorded in the Pulhatyn tract. The species is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. Part of the range is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are livestock grazing. Necessary protection measures: monitoring the status of natural populations.

Cousinia badhyzi Kult. is a semi-shrub of the *Asteraceae* family, 40-50 cm tall. The stem is thick, short, and twisted. It grows at an altitude of 400-800 m above sea level, on shallow, gravelly mountain slopes and red sandstone outcrops. It flowers and fruits in May–July. It reproduces by seeds. Germination is low. Xerophyte [4; 6].

According to its status, it belongs to category III vulnerable species. The taxon's significance in preserving the gene pool: a narrow-local relict endemic of Badhyz [4]. Eastern Mediterranean species. Representative of a monotypic genus. Medicinal plant.

The plant is found in Badhyz: slopes of the Eroyulanduz depression and the Kyzyljar ravine [3; 4].

Badhyz kuzinia is one of the rare semi-woody plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. The population is extremely small. In 2025, 312 specimens were recorded in Eroyulanduz on an area of 2000 m². It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. It is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are climatic conditions and poor seed renewal. Necessary conservation measures: monitoring of natural populations. Development of cultivation and propagation methods.

Kushki's tulip (*Tulipa kuschkensis* B. Fedtsch.) is a perennial bulbous herbaceous plant of the lily family (*Liliaceae* Juss.) 15–40 cm tall. It grows at an altitude of 400–800 m above sea level, on loess, often limestone-gravelly, heavily sandy slopes of gorges, hills and valleys. It blooms in March–April, and the seeds ripen at the end of May [6]. It reproduces by seeds and occasionally vegetatively. Xerophyte. Ephemeroïd. It blooms en masse only in years favourable for its development.

According to its status, it belongs to category III vulnerable species. The taxon's significance in preserving the gene pool: subendemic to Badhyz and Karabyl [4]. Medicinal and ornamental plant.

The plant is found in Badhyz: Serhetabat, Serhetchi, Galaymor, Chemenabat, Kyzyljar, Yeroylanduz, Kepele, Akarcheshme, Pynkhancheshme, Gezgyadik [3; 4].

The Kushki's tulip is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. The population is declining, despite its abundance at different times of the year. In 2025, 6 to 22 specimens were found in the Kepele and Akarcheshme tracts on an area of 100 m². It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. Part of the range is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are the consumption of bulbs by porcupines and wild boars. Grazing, mass picking of flowers and sometimes bulbs. Necessary protection measures: ban on picking flowers and bulbs. Wide publicity of protection among the population.

Lehmann's tulip (*Tulipa lehmanniana* Merckl.) is a perennial bulbous herbaceous plant of the lily family, 10–25 cm tall. It has a single yellow flower. It blooms in its 7th–8th year in March–April, and the fruits ripen in May [4; 5]. Xerophyte. Ephemeroïd. Abundant flowering is observed only in years favourable for growth. It reproduces mainly by seeds and weakly vegetatively. Grows on foothill plains, at an altitude of 400–800 m above sea level, on shallow, gravelly and sandy forest slopes, outcrops of variegated mountain rocks.

It is classified as a vulnerable species (category III). The taxon is important for the preservation of the gene pool as a medicinal and ornamental plant. It is also important for breeding.

The plant is found in Badhyz: Kyzyljar, Yeroylanduz, Kepele, Akarcheshme, Pynkhancheshme, Gezgyadik, the low foothills between the Murghab and Kushka rivers [3; 4]

Leman's tulip is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyz. Natural reserves are insufficient. Its population is low and fluctuates from year to year depending on meteorological conditions. In 2025, 4–12 specimens per 100 m² were counted

in the Kepele tract. In 2025, 13 specimens were recorded in Akarcheshme on an area of 1 m². From 2023 to 2025, in Badhyz, between the Murghab and Kushka rivers, the population ranged from 9 to 102 specimens per hectare. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [4]. It is cultivated on an experimental plot of the Badhyz State Nature Reserve. It is protected on the territory of the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

The main limiting factors are unregulated grazing and mass collection of flowers and bulbs. Necessary conservation measures: prohibition of collecting flowers and bulbs. Extensive educational work among the population on the conservation of the species.

References

1. *Study of the bioecological and systematic characteristics of protected species in Badhyz, search for new locations. Clarification of numbers.*
2. *Monitoring of population status throughout the range. Study of vegetative reproduction.*
3. *Development of measures for cultivation and reproduction. Study of biology and ecology in natural and cultivated conditions. Sowing in the reserve territories.*
4. *Strict observance of the protection regime in the species' habitats, control of natural populations, restriction of grazing and haymaking, and prohibition of uncontrolled harvesting of the plant.*

Bibliography

1. *Akmuradov, A., Perdaeva, A. M. Ecological and biological characteristics and component composition of medicinal plants of Eroyulanduz // Higher Education: Scientific Research. Materials of the Interuniversity International Congress. Volume 2. — Moscow: Infinity Publishing House, 2025. — pp. 115-122.*
2. *Akmuradov A., Rakhmanov O. Kh., Shayimov B. K. Summary of endemic flora of Turkmenistan: results of work in 2007-2017. — Kazan: Buk, 2018. — 142 p.*
3. *Bochanets V. P., Kamelin R. V., Gorelova T. G. Vascular plants of the Batkhizsky Reserve (operational and informational material). — Moscow, 1990. — 56 pp.*
4. *Red Book of Turkmenistan. Vol. 1: Plants. 4th edition, revised and expanded. — Ashgabat: Turkmen State Publishing Service, 2024. — 296 p.*
5. *Maslyakov V. Yu., Khanumidi E. I., Sorokopudova O. A. et al. Assessment of medicinal plant reserves: experience and research approaches. — Moscow: FBGSNU VILAR, 2024. — 126 p.*
6. *Nikitin V. V., Geldikhanov A. M. Identification guide to the plants of Turkmenistan. — Leningrad: Nauka, 1988. — 680 p.*

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TRANSFORMATION OF THE POULTRY INTESTINAL MICROBIOTA UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF STEAM TREATMENT OF FEED

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Abstract. *The effect of the process of heat treatment (steam treatment) of compound feeds for poultry and the introduction of additional compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D₃, E) into the diet in order to correct their thermally induced losses on changes in the dynamics of the quantitative composition of the intestinal microbiota of experimental poultry was studied. The study subjects were Super Nick laying hens. The experiments revealed significant changes in the quantitative composition of the duodenal resident microflora in laying hens.*

Key words: *fat-soluble vitamins, steam treatment, heat treatment of compound feeds, egg production, microbiota of the gastrointestinal tract of poultry, laying hens.*

Introduction

In the context of intensive poultry farming, it is important to find methods that allow for the full realization of the genetic potential of poultry without compromising their health and product quality. The improvement of diets is of particular importance, as they are not only a source of nutrients but also an effective mechanism for regulating physiological conditions and immunity [1, 2]. It is important to note the transformation of feeding approaches. Previously, productivity was the primary focus, but now the emphasis has shifted towards nutritional immunology and maintaining intestinal homeostasis [3, 4]. The key link in maintaining the homeostasis of poultry is the gastrointestinal microbiota, a complex ecosystem that determines the efficiency of digestion, the biosynthesis of vitamins, and the barrier function of the intestine. As the primary link in the interaction with feed components, the resident flora provides colonization resistance and modulation of the immune response. The protective potential of the microbiota is realized

through direct competition for nutrients, the synthesis of bacteriocins and organic acids, and indirectly through the activation of adaptive immunity. In this regard, alimentary disorders or hypovitaminosis, destabilizing the microbial landscape, inevitably lead to the suppression of natural resistance and an increase in the susceptibility of the livestock to infectious agents [5, 6].

The modern methodology for organizing vitamin nutrition in industrial poultry farming should be based on a comprehensive analysis of all stages of the feed life cycle. It is not enough for specialists to rely only on theoretical calculations of the vitamin balance in the diet; predictive analysis of secondary nutrient losses caused by the technological cycles of feed production becomes critically important. The leading destructive factor in this chain is hydrothermal processing (such as expansion, conditioning, or pelleting), which is a necessary condition for improving nutrients digestibility and ensuring strict infection safety in production. On the other hand, high temperatures and humidity can cause partial or even critical inactivation of thermolabile vitamins in feed formulations. However, using average table values to assess the degradation of biologically active substances is often ineffective. The actual level of vitamin preservation is a variable that is influenced by the complex synergy of the specific feed formulation (ingredient composition) and individual equipment parameters (pressure, exposure, and temperature), requiring personalized monitoring at each facility [7, 8].

The high relevance of this study based on the pressing industrial need to develop precision methods for monitoring and quantifying thermally induced degradation of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D₃, and E). During hydrothermal processing (steam treatment), feed matrix components are exposed to aggressive attack, leading to a significant reduction in the biological value of the diet. The experiment examined in detail the hypothesis that nutritional deficiency of key vitamins resulting from steam treatment initiates a cascade of changes in the poultry body. Particular attention was paid to analyzing the microbiological profile of laying hens' gastrointestinal tract. The study established a direct correlation between the decreased concentration of vitamins A, D₃, and E in thermally processed mash feed and changes in the composition of the resident microbiota, confirming the role of vitamin availability as a fundamental factor in maintaining the stability of the intestinal microbiome.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in the experimental poultry house of the Bashkir State Agricultural University, Ufa, Republic of Bashkortostan. The study involved laying hens of the Super Nick cross. Three groups of 21 birds each were randomly assigned to the experiment at 35 weeks of age, with a 38-week study period. The experimental birds were fed four diets:

- Control group — basic feed without heat treatment;

- Treatment 1 — feed subjected to heat treatment;
- Treatment 2 — feed subjected to heat treatment with the addition of additional levels of vitamins A, D₃, and E to compensate for their losses.

The experimental poultry were housed in standard windowless poultry houses. The technological parameters of breeding, housing conditions, microclimate parameters, lighting regime, cage density, feeder space, and housing complied with generally accepted industry standards.

During the preparatory phase of the experiment (the first 7 days), all birds were fed a basal diet. Upon transition to the recording period, the control group remained on the same diet, while the experimental groups were switched to feed that had undergone heat treatment according to the experimental modifications.

The duodenal microbiota study of laying hens was conducted at the L. K. Ernst Federal Research Center for Animal Husbandry (Podolsk, Moscow Region). Duodenal samples from the control and experimental groups were collected at slaughter and necropsy on the final day of the experiment. Euthanasia was performed by cervical dislocation. To preserve tissue integrity, laparotomy and evisceration of the abdominal organs were immediately performed. The duodenum was identified topographically by the loop surrounding the pancreas.

Statistical data processing was performed using Microsoft Excel.

Figure 1. Extraction of a duodenal fragment from laying hens for microbiota analysis

Results and discussion

The microbiota of the small intestine of poultry is a dynamic system sensitive to changes in diet and living conditions. Since this region is where active interaction between chyme and resident microflora begins, monitoring its composition

is crucial for preventing dysbiosis and the development of pathogenic flora [5]. Figures 2-5 show the dynamics of changes in the quantitative ratios of the main microorganisms' groups that make up the duodenal microbiota of laying hens in the control and experimental groups.

Figure 2. Content of lactobacilli in the resident microbiota of the laying hens' duodenum

Figure 3. Content of enterococci in the resident microbiota of the laying hens' duodenum

Figure 4. Content of lactose-negative *E. coli* in the resident microbiota of the laying hens' duodenum

Figure 5. Content of lactose-positive *E. coli* in the resident microbiota of the laying hens' duodenum

Analysis of the intestinal microbiome of experimental poultry revealed the main functional groups of microorganisms: lactobacilli (gen. *Lactobacillus*), enterococci (gen. *Enterococcus*), lactose-positive and lactose-negative *Escherichia*

coli (gen. lac+, lac-). As can be seen from the data presented in the figures, lactobacilli are the dominant genus in both the control and experimental groups, confirming their key role in the normal gastrointestinal flora of poultry. The intergroup dynamics showed an exponential increase in the number of normal microflora representatives in the experimental groups compared to the control: lactobacilli (from $1.5 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g in the control to $13 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g in the Treatment 2), enterococci (from $1 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g in the control to $2.5 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g in the Treatment 2), lactose-positive E. coli (from $0.1 \cdot 10^2$ CFU/g in the control to $3.5 \cdot 10^2$ CFU/g in the Treatment 2). At the same time, a negative intergroup dynamics was recorded in terms of the quantitative ratio of lactose-negative E. coli: its number decreased from $5.0 \cdot 10^2$ CFU/g in the control to $0.5 \cdot 10^2$ CFU/g in the Treatment 2.

Thus, the results of the study confirm the significant effectiveness of heat treatment of compound feed in combination with adjustments to the levels of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D₃, E) in terms of the composition and quantitative parameters of the duodenal microbiota of laying hens, which may indirectly indicate a pronounced prebiotic effect of the experimental factors. Moreover, the feeding strategy implemented in this experiment led to a significant increase in the numbers of dominant and associated beneficial bacteria (lactobacilli, enterococci, lactose-positive E. coli) and a significant suppression of opportunistic lactose-negative E. coli. This may be due to the fact that heat treatment of feed increases the availability of certain substrates for lactobacilli, and fat-soluble vitamins, with their immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties, likely contribute to the formation of a more favorable intestinal mucosal environment for symbiotic microflora. Moreover, the observed increase in the populations of enterococci and lactose-positive E. coli, which are also part of the normal microflora, indicates a complex positive shift in the microbial community towards enhanced symbiotic functions, which can contribute to more efficient digestion, competitive exclusion of pathogens and vitamin synthesis. Consequently, it can be concluded that heat treatment of feed is the primary factor improving the availability of nutrients and the sanitary quality of feed. The additional introduction of fat-soluble vitamins A, D₃, and E enhances this effect, which may be associated with their role in maintaining the integrity of the epithelial barrier, regulating the immune response of the mucous membranes (vitamins A, D₃), and protecting cells from oxidative stress (vitamin E), which creates an optimal physicochemical and immune environment for the development of beneficial microflora [8, 9].

Conclusions

The proposed feeding strategy, combining heat treatment (steam treatment) of feed with the addition of compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D₃, E), has a pronounced prebiotic effect leading to an improvement in the duodenal microbiota of laying hens. The combined use of heat treatment of feed and dietary

optimization through the addition of compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins substantiates an effective concept for maintaining vitamin balance in modern feed production, allowing for the optimization of the intestinal microbiome.

References

1. Podobed L. I. *Guide to mineral nutrition of agricultural poultry [Text]* / L. I. Podobed, A. N. Stepanenko, E. A. Kapitonova. — Odessa: Aquatoria, 2016. — 360 p.: ill.
2. Fisinin V. I. *Feeding farm poultry [Text]* / V. I. Fisinin, I. A. Egorov, I. F. Draganov. — M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2011. — 344 p.
3. Chen L. *Effects of dietary lysozyme supplementation on growth performance, intestinal morphology, immune function, antioxidant capacity, and gut microbiota in broilers [Text]* / L. Chen, W. Peng, T. Wang, S. Ma, X. Wang, B. Dai, R. Zhang, C. Yang, Y. Wu // *Poultry Science*. — 2025. — № 104 (11). — 16 p. — <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2025.105741>.
4. Naeem M. *Probiotics in Poultry: Unlocking Productivity Through Microbiome Modulation and Gut Health [Text]* / M. Naeem, D. Bourassa // *Microorganisms*. — 2025. — № 13. — 21 p. — <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms13020257>.
5. Skvortsova L. N. *Functions of the microflora of the gastrointestinal tract of poultry [Text]* / L. N. Skvortsova // *Scientific journal of KubSAU*. — 2020. — No. 161 (07). — 8 p. m. — DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21515/1990-4665-161-005>.
6. Rychlik I. *Composition and Function of Chicken Gut Microbiota [Text]* / I. Rychlik // *Animals*. — 2020. — № 10. — 20 p. — <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10010103>.
7. Yang P. *Evaluation of Extrusion Temperatures, pelleting parameters, and vitamin forms on vitamin stability in feed [Text]* / P. Yang, H. Wang, M. Zhu, Y. Ma. *Animals*. — 2020. — 10, 894. — 19 p. — <https://doi:10.3390/ani10050894>.
8. Borojoni F. G. *The Effects of Hydrothermal Processing on Feed Hygiene, Nutrient Availability, Intestinal Microbiota and Morphology in Poultry — A Review [Text]* / F. G. Borojoni, B. Svihus, H. G. von Reichenbach, J. Zentek // *Animal Feed Science and Technology*. — 2016. — 220. — P. 187-215. — <https://doi:10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2016.07.010>.
9. Cox N. A. *Effect of the Steam Conditioning and Pelleting Process on the Microbiology and Quality of Commercial-Type Poultry Feeds [Text]* / N. A. Cox, D. Burdick, J. S. Bailey, J. E. Thomson // *Poultry Science*. — 1986. — № 65. — P. 704-709. — <https://doi:10.3382/ps.0650704>.

**PHYTONEERING OF PEONIES FROM THE COLLECTION
OF THE SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL CENTER
OF LOMONOSOV MOSCOW STATE UNIVERSITY¹**

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Abstract. *Currently, every second medicinal drug is derived from natural sources. However, the mechanisms underlying the therapeutic efficacy of certain plants remain not fully understood. Medicinal plants acquire their specific properties through adaptation to environmental conditions, continuously developing new defense mechanisms that may also prove beneficial to humans. Such plants serve as raw materials for the production of herbal medicinal products with optimally balanced formulations. While chemical pharmaceuticals typically contain one to three active ingredients, phytopharmaceuticals are multicomponent mixtures comprising hundreds of pharmacologically active and inactive substances. Therefore, the search for suitable medicinal plants and the elucidation of their therapeutic properties is a complex task. Finding the necessary medicinal compound for treating a particular disease is only half the battle. It is essential to identify the active substances, determine the appropriate method of extraction, produce medicinal formulations, and subsequently conduct scientific studies to demonstrate their clinical efficacy in humans. Natural compounds are full of surprises. To date, more than 100,000 plant*

¹ The study was carried out in connection with the assignment of the Lomonosov Moscow State University.

species remain entirely unstudied. Discovering and learning to utilize the hidden therapeutic potential of plants for the benefit of all constitutes one of humanity's foremost objectives. The revelation of the medicinal potential of plants (phyto) by means of modern technologies and cutting-edge scientific methods (engineering) constitutes a relatively novel branch of interdisciplinary research — phytoengineering. In this publication, using the species *Paeonia lutea* as an example, we present selected results from investigations of heparin-like compounds.

Keywords: extracts from peony roots, anticoagulant activity, heparinoid, antithrombotics.

In Chinese medicine, the biological activity of dried, scalded, and purified peony roots is well known; these have long been used in folk medicine to treat diseases of the central nervous system, post-hemorrhagic anemia, retinal hemorrhage, infectious hepatitis, cancer, diabetes, nephritis, hypertension, loss of appetite, spastic colitis, gastralgia, and lactation delay. In Tibetan medicine, peony roots are used in the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis, bronchitis, pneumonia, common colds, and many other ailments. The chemical composition analysis of the roots [10] revealed the presence of monoterpenoids (paeoniflorin, paeoniflorigenin, albiflorin, oxypaeoniflorin, 6'-O-benzoylpaeoniflorin), benzoic acid, steroid (β -sitosterol), tannins (penta-O-galloyl- β -D-glucose), carbohydrates and related compounds (starch, pectin, etc.), triterpenoids, quinones, essential oils, traces of coumarins and alkaloids, and flavonoids (paeonidin, paeonin, paeonoside, astragaline). Pyrethrin is present in the petals, while the leaves contain the flavonoid kaempferol. According to the requirements of the Pharmacopoeia of the PRC, the content of paeoniflorin ($C_{23}H_{28}O_{11}$) in the roots of the milk-flowered peony must be no less than 0.8% [9].

We were interested in the published data on extracts from peony roots containing anticoagulants of heparin nature, demonstrating sufficient activity in the bloodstream [7; 13; 12], capable of preventing fibrin formation with its subsequent conversion into a thrombus. It can be inferred from this that peonies may have applications as active pharmaceutical ingredients in the development of medicinal products for the treatment of thrombosis or in the design of functional preventive agents for cardiovascular diseases.

It is known that the normal function of the hemostatic system relies on the regulatory interactions between the coagulation and anticoagulation systems of the blood, which constitute the overall hemostatic system in mammals. Disruptions in the functioning of this system lead to various diseases, including life-threatening conditions such as thrombosis or uncontrolled hemorrhages [8]. Blood coagulation is an essential biochemical process directed towards the formation and subsequent lysis of fibrin clots [2].

To date, various medicinal agents have been developed that either prevent thrombus formation or facilitate their dissolution. These include thrombolytic (fibrinolytic) agents (alteplase, tenecteplase, urokinase, and others) and various anticoagulants (glycosaminoglycans, flavonoids, and their analogues). However, the application of high-molecular-weight heparins derived from the mucosa of the pig intestine or the lungs of cattle is associated with several adverse side effects, including the development of immunogenicity and systemic fibrinolysis [11].

Therefore, unlocking the therapeutic potential of plants through modern technologies and scientific methods—phytoengineering—remains a topical issue. The objective of this study is to determine the anticoagulant and antithrombotic activity *in vitro* of aqueous extracts from the roots of the yellow peony *Paeonia lutea* Delav. ex Franch.

The yellow peony and Delavay's peony were discovered by the French Catholic missionary Abbé Pierre Jean-Marie Delavay (Père Jean-Marie Delavay) in Yunnan Province, China, during 1883-1884. They were described by the French botanist Adrien René Franchet (Adrien René Franchet) in 1886. Both species occur in the forest and subalpine zones within shrub thickets at elevations of 2400-3400 m above sea level. Many researchers consider them to be the same species. Some botanists regard the yellow peony as a variety of *Paeonia delavayi*, while others support the view of two distinct species.

In the central regions of the Non-Black Earth zone of Russia, the stems of these plants, which are straight, unbranched, or sparsely branched, can reach a height of 2 m. The leaves are twice trifoliate, 55 cm long, with petioles measuring 20 cm. Typically, 3-4 flowers form on each shoot with a diameter ranging from 4 to 9 cm with bright yellow petal coloration. It blooms two weeks later than the tree peony, allowing for an extended flowering period of peonies in the garden.

Results of the study on the anticoagulant properties of KPZh preparations under *in vitro* and *in vivo* conditions.

In vitro

It was established that the 2% alcoholic extract from the bark of the root of yellow peony (KPZh) exhibited a non-enzymatic (fibrin depolymerization) fibrinolytic effect under *in vitro* conditions. It dissolved unstabilized fibrin both in the absence and presence of the enzymatic fibrinolysis blocker—a 0.2% solution of soybean trypsin inhibitor. The lysis zones ranged from 20 to 49 mm². In the presence of blood plasma, the preparation from KPZh bark exhibited tissue plasminogen activator activity (lysis zones averaged 28 mm²), while control solutions showed no lysis zones.

The investigation of the anticoagulant properties of the KPZh preparation demonstrated their presence in APTT and TV tests compared to the Control (Table 1).

Table 1.
Anticoagulant activity of the KPZh preparation under in vitro conditions (M±m)

Hemostasis parameters	Control (0.85% NaCl)	Experience (5% preparation from the bark of roots <i>P. lutea</i>)
Prothrombin time (PV), s	32.6 ± 1.1	65.4 ± 0.9**
Activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT), s	34.5 ± 1.3	60.4 ± 1.6**
Thrombin time (TV), s	23.5 ± 1.5	36.4 ± 1.6**

Note. Statistical parameters were calculated relative to the corresponding control samples. Designations: ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

As shown in Table 1, the KPZh preparation increases PV nearly 2-fold, APTT by 1.7-fold, and TV by 1.5-fold. These results indicate that KPZh participates in the inhibition of both the intrinsic and extrinsic coagulation pathways.

Therefore, KPZh preparations exhibit an anticoagulant-fibrinolytic effect under *in vitro* conditions.

In vivo

Twenty-four hours after five consecutive daily oral administrations of the KPZh preparation, a significant increase in SFA by 1.3 times, t-PA activity by 1.6 times, and anticoagulant activity according to the APTT test by 1.5 times was observed in rat plasma compared to control values (Controls 1 and 2). Non-enzymatic fibrinolysis of plasma increased by 1.26 times compared to controls (Table 2).

Table 2.

Total (SFA) and non-enzymatic (NE) fibrinolytic activity, tissue plasminogen activator (t-PA) activity, platelet aggregation (PA), and anticoagulant activity (according to the APTT test) in rat blood plasma 24 hours after five- and tenfold oral administrations of heparinoid from KPZh bark at a dose of 0.1 mg/kg (M±m).

Administered drugs	APTT, s	AT, %	SFA, mm ²	NF, mm ²	t-PA, mm ²
Experience 1 — KPZh bark preparation (5-fold)	45.5±1.0**	102.0±4.9	45.5±1.3**	31.5±0.7**	20.0±1.4**
Experience 2 — KPZh bark preparation (10-fold)	46.2±1.5**	101.5±1.7	36.6±1.4*	32.5±0.8**	16.25±1.1*
Control 1-0.85% NaCl (5-fold)	30.5±1.2	101.3±2.4	31.0±0.7	25.0±0.9	12.5±1.0
Control 2-0.85% NaCl (10-fold)	33.0±1.0	100.4±1.9	36.2±0.7**	10.8±0.5*	13.5±1.5

Note. Significance of differences calculated relative to corresponding control samples. ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

As shown in Table 2, 24 h after 10-fold administration of the KPZh bark preparation, plasma SFA in the experimental group still exceeded control levels, but to a significantly lesser extent (by 1.18 times), non-enzymatic fibrinolysis and tissue plasminogen activator activity by 1.3 times, and anticoagulant activity according to the APTT test by 1.4 times. At the same time, the platelet aggregation index in the experiment was practically indistinguishable from that of the controls.

The results indicate that even a five-fold administration of an alcoholic peony preparation is sufficient to induce an anticoagulant effect in the bloodstream.

2. Hypoglycemic properties of the KPZh preparation under in vivo conditions.

In an animal model of alloxan-induced diabetes, intravenous administration of alloxan 24 hours after the completion of chronic (10-day) oral administration of KPZh bark preparation to the experimental group of rats resulted in a significant increase in blood glucose levels by nearly fourfold on the second day following alloxan administration. During this period, hyperglycemia was more pronounced in the Control group of animals (blood sugar level increased by 6.2 times). By the 7th day after alloxan administration, the blood glucose level normalized in the experimental group of rats. At the same time, hyperglycemia persisted in the Control group of rats, with their glucose levels exceeding those of the experimental group by 1.6 times (Table 3).

The experiment also demonstrated that the heparinoid preparation from KPZh bark protected the animals from the toxic effects of alloxan, as evidenced by 100% survival in the experimental rats compared to 66% survival in the Control animals by the end of the experiment [4].

Thus, based on the results of the conducted experiment under *in vivo* conditions, it can be concluded that the heparinoid preparation from KPZh bark, upon chronic oral administration, exerted both a protective anticoagulant effect in the bloodstream and an antidiabetic effect, normalizing the blood glucose level. After only five applications of the peony extract, all types of fibrinolytic (total, non-enzymatic, enzymatic) and anticoagulant activities significantly increased. The increase in anticoagulant activity induced by the heparinoid from KPZh bark is attributable to the presence of polysaccharides of a heparin-like nature. The enhancement of enzymatic fibrinolysis in blood plasma is due to the fact that, on one hand, the peony-derived preparation itself exhibits tissue plasminogen activator properties, and on the other hand, it induces an endothelium-dependent reaction leading to the release of natural tissue plasminogen activator from the vascular wall of rats into the bloodstream.

Table 3.

Blood glucose concentration in rats 24 hours after tenfold oral administration of the heparinoid from KPZh bark at a dose of 0.1 mg/kg (Experience) or 0.85 % NaCl (Control) (M±m)

Experimental conditions	Glucose concentration (%)		
	Before the experience	After alloxan administration	
		On the 2nd day	On the 7th day
Experience — KPZh bark	100 ± 4,5	385 ± 8,4**	111 ± 7,5
Control — (0.85 % NaCl)	100 ± 5,9	620 ± 9,1**	160 ± 6.0**
Norm	100 ± 3,9	100 ± 4,9	100 ± 4,6

Note. Significance of differences calculated relative to the corresponding Norm samples, accepted as 100%: ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

With prolonged (10-fold) administration of the peony preparation, the fibrinolytic activity of the animals' blood plasma remained above the control level. Under these conditions, the peony preparation protected the organism from the toxic diabetogenic effects of alloxan: by the 7th day after alloxan administration, the blood glucose levels in most experimental animals returned to normal values, with a 100% survival rate observed among the rats. Therefore, an important conclusion can be made about the favorable effect of the preparation derived from KPZh in reducing the risk of occurrence and progression of both pre-thrombotic and thrombotic conditions, as well as hyperglycemic states, in the pathogenesis of which increased functional activity of the hemostasis system plays a leading role [1].

Subsequently, a comparison of the anticoagulant properties of heparinoids from the bark and the pith of *Paeonia lutea* roots was conducted [3].

It was established that *Paeonia lutea* contains an anticoagulant component in the extract from whole roots. No data have been found in the literature regarding which part of the roots (primary cortex or central stele) of this peony exhibits the highest activity. It is known that the primary cortex (hereinafter the "cortex") consists of fundamental tissue cells and contains a considerable amount of intercellular substance; this part of the root conducts water and dissolved mineral substances from the root hairs to the center of the root. The central stele (hereinafter the "pith") carries out the transport of substances.

Protein-purified anticoagulant preparations were obtained from different parts of the roots (bark or pith) of the ecologically clean yellow peony (*P. lutea*); their nature was established, and their anticoagulant (anticoagulant, fibrinolytic, and antithrombotic) effects were investigated using coagulological methods. Anticoagulants from the bark and pith of KPZh were utilized in this study. Experiments were conducted under *in vitro* and *in vivo* conditions. To investigate

the effects of various parts of the roots on the inhibition of blood coagulation processes under *in vitro* conditions, 2% aqueous extracts were prepared, from which anticoagulant fractions were subsequently isolated. For this purpose, the active compound was purified from proteins by biochemical methods through their precipitation from the extract using 5% ethyl alcohol, followed by centrifugation at 3000 g for 30 minutes; thereafter, the supernatant containing anticoagulants was dried at 37 °C.

Subsequently, the anticoagulant activity of each preparation was determined depending on the concentrations used. For this purpose, solutions of the preparation dissolved in physiological saline from KPZh (RGP 1) and from the core of KPZh (RGP 2) were prepared at concentrations ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-1} mg/ml. The preparations were incubated with normal rat plasma for 15 min at 37 °C. Control samples consisted of normal rat plasma to which physiological saline was added instead of the preparations.

In *in vivo* experiments, rats maintained on a standard laboratory diet were used. Under *in vivo* conditions, a non-invasive intranasal method was employed to administer drugs to the animals, whereby the drugs do not come into contact with the acidic environment of the stomach and can directly enter the bloodstream.

The animals were divided into three groups — two experimental groups, each receiving one of the two studied heparinoids — RGP 1 and RGP 2 — intranasally five times at a dose of 500 µg/kg body weight in a volume of 0.15 ml, and one Control group, which at the same times and in a similar manner received 0.85% NaCl solution (physiological saline) instead of heparinoids. Twenty hours after the last (fifth) administration of GP 1, GP 2, or physiological saline, blood samples were collected from fasted animals for analysis.

In dried anticoagulants, the amidolytic method revealed the presence of heparins in the bark (RGP 1) and the core (RGP 2), at levels of 2.3 mg% and 2.05 mg%, respectively, as well as low-molecular-weight components in the form of salts, amines, and amides (according to electrophoretic analysis results). Thus, the heparinoid nature of the anticoagulants in the RGP 1 and RGP 2 preparations has been established.

As shown in Table 4, under *in vitro* conditions, the experimental samples of RGP 1 exhibited high anticoagulant activity in the APTT test at all investigated concentrations (from 10^{-6} to 10^{-1} mg/ml).

This activity was maximally increased by 1.3 times at a heparinoid concentration of 10^{-2} mg/ml and subsequently decreased, beginning at an RGP 1 concentration of 10^{-5} mg/ml, showing an increase of only 1.16 times. According to the TV test, the addition of RGP 1 to normal rat plasma also significantly increased the anticoagulant properties of the plasma. Thus, at RGP 1 concentrations ranging from 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} mg/mL, a significant increase in anticoagulant activity of nearly 1.7 times was observed, which then decreased at RGP 1 concentrations from 10^{-4} to 10^{-6} mg/mL.

Table 4.

Concentration-dependent anticoagulant activity (according to APTT — activated partial thromboplastin time, TV — thrombin time, PV — prothrombin time tests) and fibrin depolymerization activity (FDPA) of plasma from healthy rats after addition of heparinoid from the bark (RGP 1) and core (RGP 2) of roots *P. lutea* ($M \pm m$)

Concentrations (mg/ml)	GP 1	GP 2	Control
	APTT, s		
10^{-6}	42.0 ± 2.5	41.0 ± 0.8	40.8 ± 2.9
10^{-5}	$47.0 \pm 1.6^*$	41.3 ± 1.4	
10^{-4}	$51.8 \pm 2.0^{**}$	43.0 ± 1.9	
10^{-3}	$52.0 \pm 3.1^{**}$	$48.8 \pm 1.5^{**}$	
10^{-2}	$53.1 \pm 3.7^{**}$	$50.0 \pm 2.0^{**}$	
10^{-1}	$52.2 \pm 1.7^{**}$	$50.2 \pm 1.3^{**}$	
	TV, s		
10^{-6}	25.0 ± 1.3	24.8 ± 1.6	24.2 ± 0.9
10^{-5}	$28.1 \pm 1.1^*$	24.6 ± 2.0	
10^{-4}	$30.4 \pm 4.1^*$	25.1 ± 2.4	
10^{-3}	$41.0 \pm 2.3^{**}$	$39.4 \pm 1.6^{**}$	
10^{-2}	$41.5 \pm 3.0^{**}$	$40.5 \pm 1.9^{**}$	
10^{-1}	$41.2 \pm 1.5^{**}$	$40.1 \pm 1.7^{**}$	
	PV, s		
10^{-6}	20.4 ± 1.7	20.6 ± 0.7	20.5 ± 1.1
10^{-5}	22.4 ± 1.7	22.4 ± 0.8	
10^{-4}	23.0 ± 2.6	$24.7 \pm 1.0^{**}$	
10^{-3}	$23.6 \pm 1.1^*$	$24.8 \pm 0.9^{**}$	
10^{-2}	$24.4 \pm 0.7^{**}$	$25.6 \pm 0.7^{**}$	
10^{-1}	$27.0 \pm 0.9^{**}$	$27.7 \pm 0.7^{**}$	
	FDPA, mm2		
10^{-6}	$18.0 \pm 3.2^{**}$	$18.7 \pm 2.4^{**}$	0.8 ± 0.1
10^{-5}	$18.8 \pm 1.1^{**}$	$18.8 \pm 1.7^{**}$	
10^{-4}	$20.1 \pm 0.8^{**}$	$19.4 \pm 2.2^{**}$	
10^{-3}	$24.5 \pm 1.3^{**}$	$20.3 \pm 2.2^{**}$	
10^{-2}	$25.0 \pm 0.9^{**}$	$20.4 \pm 2.1^{**}$	
10^{-1}	$26.1 \pm 1.1^{**}$	$22.5 \pm 1.7^{**}$	

Note. Statistical indicators were calculated relative to the corresponding Control samples, taken as 100%. Significance of differences: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

According to the PV test, RGP 1 increased the anticoagulant properties of rat plasma at heparinoid concentrations of 10^{-1} to 10^{-2} , whereas at other concentrations, the PV did not undergo significant changes.

Based on these data, it can be concluded that the greatest anticoagulant effects of RGP 1 are mediated through both the common and intrinsic pathways of blood coagulation.

Investigation of the anticoagulant activity of RGP 2 preparations revealed a similar trend, albeit to a somewhat lesser extent according to APTT and TV data than in RGP 1 preparations; specifically, APTT at RGP 2 concentrations ranging from 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} mg/ml increased by 1.27-fold compared to control samples. Starting from a concentration of RGP 2 at 10^{-4} mg/mL in the system, APTT decreased but had not yet reached Control values. TV was significantly increased after the addition of RGP 2 to plasma at concentrations from 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} mg/mL. PV was significantly increased with the use of GP 2 at concentrations from 10^{-1} to 10^{-4} mg/mL [25].

Notably, a more pronounced prolongation (by 1.25 times) of PV was observed using RGP 2 at a concentration of 10^{-2} mg/mL, whereas under the same conditions RGP 1 prolonged PV by 1.14 times. Regarding the study of the FDPA of each heparinoid, the presence of this activity has been demonstrated following the application of both heparinoids (see Table 3), indicating the complex heparin nature of the studied RGP 1 and RGP 2, as established in other studies with different heparin preparations [5].

In animal experiments, following multiple intranasal administrations over 5 days at 24-hour intervals of each heparinoid from bark or core, it was demonstrated that 20 hours after the last administration, rats showed increased anticoagulant and fibrinolytic properties of diverse origin in their blood plasma.

The increase in anticoagulant activity of plasma under the influence of drugs derived from the bark or heartwood of KPZh was demonstrated by the prolongation of APTT, TV, and PV by 1.8, 2.0, and 1.4 times, respectively, following administration of RGP 1. Administration of RGP 2 resulted in the prolongation of APTT, TV, and PV by 1.7, 2.0, and 1.3 times, respectively.

The following results indicated an increase in fibrinolytic activity of blood plasma under the influence of preparations from KPZh: in rat blood plasma after administration of RGP 1 and RGP 2, a high level of non-enzymatic fibrinolytic activity was detected according to the FDPA test (lysis zones on unstabilized fibrin ranged from 32 to 44 mm², compared to Control samples where FDPA reached only 12-15 mm² (Table 5). Furthermore, preparations from both the bark and the core increased the GP of rat blood plasma by 35-40% compared to the Control.

Thus, the KPZh-derived preparations exhibited high anticoagulant activity in the TV and APTT tests, indicating that the studied peony-derived preparations inhibit factors of both the common and intrinsic coagulation pathways. Furthermore, these

preparations demonstrated significant fibrin de-polymerization (non-enzymatic fibrinolytic) activity exceeding the Control values by 190-280% (see Table 5).

Table 5.

Changes in anticoagulant parameters (assessed by APTT — activated partial thromboplastin time, TV — thrombin time, PV — prothrombin time tests) and fibrin depolymerization activity (FDPA) of plasma from healthy rats 20 hours after intranasal fivefold administration of heparinoids from the bark (RGP 1) and heartwood (RGP 2) of roots of *P. lutea* at doses of 0.5 mg/kg body weight (M±m)

Tested preparations	APTT, s (%)	TV, s (%)	PV, s (%)	FDPA, mm2(%)
Control (NaCl)	41.8 ± 6.3 (100%)	24.2 ± 3.1 (100%)	20.3 ± 1.1 (100%)	60.0 ± 4.8 (100%)
RGP 1	53.6 ± 5.0** (180%)	57.7 ± 6.0** (200%)	25.5 ± 0.7** (154%)	230.0 ± 5.03 (380%)
RGP 2	53.0 ± 3.6** (170%)	57.4 ± 4.5** (200%)	39.0 ± 1.6** (142%)	175.0 ± 9.7 (290%)

Note: sstatistical indicators were calculated relative to the respective Control samples, taken as 100%. Significance of differences: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

Conclusion

Thus, the heparinoids we investigated exhibit a unique combined effect on the phases of blood coagulation, enhancing the anticoagulant and fibrinolytic properties of blood plasma, as well as inhibiting fibrin formation processes which, under adverse conditions, subsequently lead to thrombosis, thereby contributing to the restoration of impaired functions of the insular apparatus. These heparinoids can be classified as anticoagulant, fibrinolytic, antithrombotic, and hypoglycemic agents. The most pronounced and consistent positive effect on the organism was exerted by heparinoids contained in the bark of the roots of the yellow peony.

References

1. Barkagan Z. S., Kostyuchenko G. I. *Metabolic-inflammatory concept of atherothrombosis and new therapeutic approaches for patients // Bulletin of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences. 2006. No. 2 (120). — Pp. 132-138.*
2. Berkovsky A. L., Sergeeva E. V., Suvorov A. V., Melkumyan A. L., Kozlov A. A., Neshkova E. A., Yarovaya G. A. *Methods for determining heparin activity. — Moscow: GBOU DPO RMAPO, 2015. — 64 p.*

3. Kudryashov B. A., Ammosova Ya. M., Lyapina L. A., Osipova N. N., Azieva L. D., Lyapin G. Yu., Basanova A. V. Heparin from meadowsweet (*Spiraea ulmaria*) and its properties // *Izv. AN SSSR. Biological Series*. 1991, No. 6, pp. 939-943.

4. Lyapina L. A., Pastorova V. E., Novikov V. S., Uspenskaya M. S., Ziadetdinova G. A., Ulyanov A. M., Tarasov Yu. A. Anticoagulant-fibrinolytic and hypoglycemic effects of preparations derived from higher plants // *Vestnik Moskov University. Series 16. Biology*. 2001, No. 2, pp. 3-7.

5. Lyapina L. A., Pastorova V. E., Uspenskaya M. S., Novikov V. S. Anticoagulant-fibrinolytic component in extracts of peony roots // *Bulletin of Moscow University. Biology Series*. 16, 1995, No. 4, pp. 15-19.

6. Uspenskaya M. S., Murashev V. V., Lyapina L. A. *The King of Flowers — a Source of Promising Medicinal Agents*. Moscow: Kim L. A., 2023. 117 p.

7. Lyapina M. G., Uspenskaya M. S., Maistrenko E. S. On the mechanism of the anticoagulant action of the extract from roots of the milk-flowered peony // *International Journal of Applied and Fundamental Research*. 2016, Vol. 11(6), pp. 1091-1093.

8. Lyapina L. A., Grigoryeva M. E., Obergann T. Yu., Shubina T. A. *Theoretical and practical aspects of studying the functional state of the blood anticoagulation system*. Moscow: Advanced Solutions, 2012. 160 pp.

9. Shreter A. I., Valentinov B. G., Naumova E. M. *Natural raw materials of Chinese medicine (reference in 3 volumes)*. — Moscow: Terevinf, 2004. Vol. I. — 506 p.

10. *Chinese Pharmacopoeia*. China Medical Science Press, 2010.

11. Ling-Hua Wei, Tian-Ran Chen, Hong-Bo Fang, Qiang Jin, Shui-Jun Zhang, Jie Hou, Yang Yu, Tong-Yi Dou, Yun-Feng Cao, Wen-Zhi Guo, Guang-Bo Ge. Natural constituents of *St. John's Wort* inhibit the proteolytic activity of human thrombin // *J. Biol. Macromol*. 2019. 134 — P. 622-630.

12. Wang R., Bai J., Yan G., Xiao Z., Chen K., Li K., Tang J., Lu D. The enzymatic hydrolysate of fucoidan from *Sargassum hemiphyllum* triggers immunity in plants // *J. Plant Physiol*. 2023. V. 283. — P. 153967

13. Zhang S. B. *In vitro* antithrombotic activities of peanut protein hydrolysates // *Food Chem*. 2016. V. 202. — P. 1-8.

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ON THE IMPACT OF URBAN DEVELOPMENT ON THE ROCK PIGEON POPULATION IN DUSHANBE (TAJIKISTAN)

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This article, based on year-round rock pigeon censuses in Dushanbe, describes its distribution across the city's habitats. The influence of urban development on the pigeon's lifestyle and behavior in Dushanbe is demonstrated. A unique urban population has developed here, differing from the wild population in its timing and choice of nesting sites, as well as its behavior.

Key words: *Dushanbe city, rock pigeon, nesting, urban population, biotopes, seasonal migrations, numbers, occurrence dynamics, behavior.*

The rock pigeon (***Columba livia neglecta***) (**Hume, 1873**) is a sedentary bird that undertakes seasonal vertical migrations. It is widespread in Tajikistan, its range covering all regions of the republic, with the exception of some areas of the Pamirs (Abdusalyamov I., 1971).

The rock pigeon typically nests on cliffs, in crevices of rocky or loess cliffs, in gypsum sinkholes, and in various buildings. In desert regions, nesting is known to occur in the walls of old abandoned wells. In such cases, nests are built between the stones and logs that reinforce the well walls.

In the Hissar Valley, A. I. Ivanov encountered rock pigeons during nesting wherever suitable habitats exist, most often loess or conglomerate cliffs.

In the early 1930s, rock pigeons rarely settled in large villages and cities. G. Georgievsky observed them in Gissar (11 females), on May 2, 1934, and in the vicinity of Stalinabad. A. I. Ivanov observed them on May 25, 1935 (13 fledglings), and on January 23, 1935 (14 males). (Popov, 1959; Ivanov, 1969).

In the winter of 1946, in January, February, and March, near Dushanbe, A. I. Ivanov observed flocks of pigeons flying from the mountains to the valley, to feed in the fields and on the foothills. The migration can usually be observed in the morning, when the sun is already up, and lasts only 20-30 minutes, no more. In January, this event occurred between 10 and 11 a.m., and earlier in March. The birds fly in very dense flocks of 50-200 individuals; 10-12 such flocks were observed during a single flight. The flocks either remained isolated or merged into masses of several hundred; some birds, without landing to feed, flew south, crossing the valley transversely (Ivanov, 1969).

Currently, the rock pigeon is found throughout Dushanbe. It typically nests under the roofs and in the attics of two-, three-, and multi-story buildings (schools, administrative buildings, and residential buildings), in places inaccessible to predators (such as cats). Nests are also found in the attics of single-story buildings, as well as in the workshops of industrial enterprises.

In years with favorable conditions and sufficient food, they can breed from March to December, and sometimes throughout the year.

According to our data, rock pigeon nesting was observed on August 28, November 2, December 16, and January 12.

We observed mass mating of rock pigeons in the first ten days of March 2011. In the first ten days of April, two nests with a full clutch were found. The nests were located on the roof of a house under the eaves. The first nest was constructed from 15-20 stems of annual plants, and the second nest was built directly on the clay floor, without any bedding. Each nest contained two eggs. In the second ten days of April, naked and blind chicks hatched in these nests, and by the end of the third ten days of April, they had already grown and were slightly smaller than their parents. According to expert estimates, the rock pigeon population in Dushanbe in the 1980s was 4,000-4,500 individuals (oral communication by Kh. Imamov). Over the past 30-40 years, due to the city's expansion and the construction of high-rise buildings, rock pigeons have begun to inhabit the rooftops of these buildings, where they also began nesting (Muratov R., Talbonov Kh., 2021). In 2016, we counted 35,903 rock pigeons in Dushanbe across all the city's habitats.

their occurrence decreases. (Muratov R., 2021).

A total of 7,532 birds were recorded in January, accounting for 21.0% of all recorded birds of this species. In February, 7,854 birds were recorded (21.9%), in March, 3,479 birds (9.7%), in April, 800 birds (2.2%), in May, 796 birds (2.2%), in June, 1,888 birds (5.3%), in July, 1,262 birds (3.5%), in August, 4,921 birds (13.7%), in September, 3,869 birds (10.8%), in October, 2,388 birds (6.7%), in November, 416 birds (1.2%), and in December, 698 birds (1.9%).

The rock pigeon's primary food source is plant seeds, such as wheat, sunflower, corn, etc. Within the city, the highest concentration of rock pigeons was observed

during feeding, mainly in the outskirts of the city (in agricultural lands) — 9,974 individuals (27.8%), and during resting — on industrial, residential and administrative buildings — 10,844 birds (30.2%). A slightly smaller number of them were recorded around open water sources, where they flew to drink — 2,710 individuals (7.5%). During nesting or migration through the city: in gardens, parks, squares and cemeteries, the number was 2,710 birds (7.5%), in the area of single-story buildings — 2,368 individuals (6.6%) and multi-story buildings — 2,484 individuals (6.9%). At the airport, 4,813 individuals were recorded, which amounted to (13.4%) of all pigeons noted in the city (Figure 1).

Figure 1.— Distribution of the rock pigeon population in Dushanbe by biotope, in %

Thus, under the influence of Dushanbe's urban development, a unique urban population of rock pigeons has formed in the city. Unlike the wild population, the urban population has shifted its nesting sites to residential and industrial buildings, and their numbers are growing in the city in line with the emergence of new types of high-rise buildings. Rock pigeon behavior within the city has also changed. Nesting occurs throughout the year. They no longer make long seasonal migrations to the southern regions of the republic, but instead spend their time around the city, flying in to spend the night in residential, industrial, and administrative buildings.

References

1. *Abdusalyamov I. A. Fauna of the Tajik SSR, Vol. 19, Part 1, Birds.* // Dushanbe, Donish, 1971. — 404 p.
2. *Ivanov A. I. Birds of the Pamir-Alay.* — L.: Science. Leningrad Department, 1969. — 448 p.
3. *Popov A. V. Birds of Gissar-Karategin.* // — Stalinabad. Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of the Tajik SSR, 1959. — 183 p.
4. *Muratov R. Sh. Bird Migrations in the Pamir-Alay Territory.* // — Dushanbe, Donish, 2021. — 234 p.
5. *Muratov R. Sh., Talbonov H. M. Birds of the City of Dushanbe.* // — Dushanbe, Donish, 2021. — 222 p.

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USING GEOMETRIC COMPARISON OF TOPOLOGIES IN GEOINFORMATION ANALYSIS

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Abstract: *Manufacturing processes often require modeling complex objects as topologies. Such models are used to track changes in the object under study, perform calculations, and make forecasts. A key element of change monitoring is geometric comparison, which allows for identifying changed areas of topologies. This paper examines the application of geometric comparison results for topological models in geoinformation analysis. The findings from geoinformation analysis can be incorporated into future manufacturing operations.*

Keywords: *Geoinformation analysis, geometric comparison of topologies, digital map of changes.*

Modeling complex spatial objects is a common task in various industries related to manufacturing and construction. The structure of such objects allows them to be represented as a topology: a set of nodes and the branches connecting them. Using topologies, spatial objects can be modeled for solving problems such as traffic flow analysis, pedestrian, marine, and air navigation [1]. Another area of application for geometric graphs is the coal industry. Coal mines and underground mines are hazardous production facilities, and ensuring their emergency response is a mandatory component of every enterprise's operation. This includes solving numerous important problems, including calculating ventilation flows and water supply for the mine, determining the stability of ventilation systems, and calculating explosion-proof distances during gas explosions [2, 3]. The successful resolution of these issues affects not only the organization of underground production processes but also the lives and health of those in the mine in the event of an accident.

These tasks can often involve comparing successively created spatial object models represented as topologies. By comparing successively created topologies,

it's possible to automatically update maps and detect changes in road networks and mine network models. Identifying changes improves the quality control of the models being created, as it allows for the visual display of new or removed topological elements and their validity verification [4].

The essence of the geometric comparison approach is that the user receives information about each section of both compared models, which are marked as removed (compared to the newer model), added (compared to the older model), or preserved. This allows for a more accurate assessment of how the changes are spatially distributed and how they may impact other objects within the study area.

Using geospatial data in modeling topological objects allows for the creation of cartographic materials — digital change maps. Digital change maps are used to display transformations observed during a given time period. The digital map displays branches or portions of a more recently created topology, constructed using the geospatial coordinates of nodes, as well as branches of an older topology marked as “removed.” Different groups of branches are visualized in different styles to clearly depict the identified changes.

Geospatial data also enables GIS analysis based on the results of geometric comparisons. Among the types of GIS analysis that can be applied to the obtained data are the following [5]:

1. Creating buffer zones. Creating buffers around removed or added objects allows us to identify areas affected by changes identified during model comparison.

2. Zoning. The next step after creating buffer zones around branches can be to define zones within the study area based on criteria that determine the nature of the identified changes. Thus, the study area is divided into small, uniform sections, each of which is identified by the presence of added or removed branches, or branches with attribute changes. Combining these fragments based on the presence of similar changes allows us to identify deformation zones.

3. Overlay operations. To provide context to the identified changes, as well as the buffers and zones created based on the data on the identified changes, this data should be combined with existing information about the study area. This is achieved using overlay operations, which allow us to combine layers containing different types of data.

Let's consider the use of geometric analysis results for geospatial analysis using a specific example. Two successively created mine network models were compared. The resulting change map is shown in Figure 1.

The red lines represent branches that were removed. The green lines represent branches that were added. The areas around the removed and added branches are shown in similar colors.

As a result of research conducted in the study area, ground subsidence depth values were obtained in the given grid sections before and after coal mining operations,

the results of which are displayed on a change map. The values are visualized in Figure 2. To illustrate the subsidence changes, an additional grid was constructed, in which elements are colored according to the magnitude of the difference in subsidence after and before mining operations. Darker areas indicate zones of greatest subsidence, while lighter areas indicate zones of least subsidence or no subsidence.

Figure 1 — Identifying the zones of influence of the identified changes: A) dividing the study space into a grid; B) buffering; C) identifying the zones of influence of the changes.

Figure 2 — Zones of earth's surface subsidence: A) before mining operations; B) after mining operations; C) increase in subsidence.

For the final stage of geospatial analysis, a grid representing the increase in land subsidence was superimposed on the grid displaying the nature of the changes identified through geometric comparison of the topologies. For clarity, the coloring of the line segments depends on the nature of the identified changes, and the shading of the grid segments depends on the increase in subsidence. The resulting map is shown in Figure 3.

The resulting map shows that the most severe subsidence due to mining operations occurs in the zone where new elements of the mine working network were added. This suggests that continued mining operations in this area and subsequent expansion of workings in this direction will lead to further subsidence.

Figure 3 — Overlaying the subsidence change layer on the topology change layer

Thus, conducting a geometric analysis enabled us to identify opportunities to improve the efficiency and safety of production and construction operations. Information on the detected changes can be used for further planning of changes to the studied object, updating cartographic materials, and solving problems related

to the subject area of the studied object, such as navigation calculations or calculating the physical characteristics of processes dependent on the spatial characteristics of the environment.

Reference

1. Kalogianni, E., van Oosterom, P., Dimopoulou, E., & Lemmen, C. (2020). *3D Land Administration: A Review and a Future Vision in the Context of the Spatial Development Lifecycle*. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(2), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi9020107>
2. Goffart, T. V. (2019). *Practical safety tasks in coal mines*. *Physics of combustion and explosion*, 55(4), 138-145. — DOI 10.15372/FGV20190418.
3. Paleev D. Ju., Lukashov O. Ju., Kosterenko V. N., Timchenko A. N., Vasenin I. M., Shrager Je. R., Krajinov A. Ju. (2011). *Computer technologies for solving the problems of the accident elimination plan*. Moscow: Mining, 160 p
4. Krassakis P., Pyrgaki K., Gemeni V., Roumpos C., Louloudis G., Koukouzas N. (2022). *GIS-Based Subsurface Analysis and 3D Geological Modeling as a Tool for Combined Conventional Mining and In-Situ Coal Conversion: The Case of Kardia Lignite Mine, Western Greece*. *Mining*, 2(2), 297-314. —<https://doi.org/10.3390/mining2020016>
5. Huisman, O., de By, R. A. (2009). *Principles of geographic information systems: an introductory textbook*. (ITC Educational Textbook Series; Vol. 1). International Institute for Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation.

CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF MINUTE BLOOD VOLUME IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY

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Abstract. *Within the first 24 hours, all children with SCTBI exhibited an increased mesor of the circadian rhythm of minute blood volume (CR CO), indicating a hyperdynamic response of the circulatory system to SCTBI. A more effective stress-protective comprehensive conservative therapy for SCTBI in children was demonstrated in the second group. The hyperdynamic response of the circulatory system was directly related to the severity of the hyperthermic reaction in the 3rd subgroup. In the 2nd group, a strong direct correlation between COA and CO was observed across three subgroups during the first 10 days, significantly weakening only in the 3rd subgroup. This can be explained by the development of an energy-deficient myocardial state in patients undergoing cranial and extracranial corrective surgeries.*

Keywords: *circadian rhythm, cardiac output, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children*

Relevance. Based on the understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms of cerebral injury, the following urgent interventions for acute cerebral insufficiency caused by SCTBI are currently identified: restoration of cerebral perfusion, neuroprotective therapy, and timely correction of extracranial homeostasis disturbances. Extracranial complications typically arise at the time of injury, progressing or, conversely, diminishing during the patient's stay in the intensive care unit. These complications can affect both mortality and neurological outcomes in patients with SCTBI. Among these extracranial complications, cardiac injury is a relatively common occurrence, affecting approximately 25-35% of patients with TBI. One of the body's initial protective responses to trauma is a hemodynamic stress reaction, resulting in the formation of a more physiological hyperdynamic circulation. In more severe and complicated injuries, we have previously

documented the onset of a hypodynamic hemodynamic pattern. The pathophysiology underlying cardiac injury in TBI involves a complex interaction between the brain and the heart. Acute cerebral injury induces a systemic inflammatory response and catecholamine release, resulting in the discharge of neurotransmitters and cytokines that exacerbate brain injury and cellular dysfunction. Secondary brain injuries, such as intracranial hypertension, seizures, and tissue hypoxia, can contribute to the development of various extracranial complications depending on the severity of TBI, which in turn further complicate cerebral hemodynamics, leading to secondary tissue hypoxia and aggravating damage to uninjured brain regions. Post-traumatic extracranial complications affect the respiratory system (neurogenic pulmonary edema, ventilator-associated pneumonia), coagulation (increased local release of tissue factor with a high risk of thrombosis, disseminated coagulopathy), as well as the liver and/or kidneys (acute kidney injury, hypoxic hepatitis). Moreover, cardiac injury following TBI is a relatively common complication with a complex pathophysiology and may potentially contribute to the high mortality rate in patients with TBI. Cardiac injuries such as regional wall motion abnormalities, troponin elevation, myocardial stunning, or Takotsubo cardiomyopathy (a non-ischemic cardiomyopathy characterized by typical involvement of the left ventricular apex) have been described [1-5]. Due to a lack of information on the specific changes in minute blood volume (CO) in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury, we aimed to study the alterations in the phase characteristic structure and to provide a comparative assessment of the circadian rhythm response of CO to severe combined traumatic brain injury during different stages of intensive comprehensive conservative therapy and early surgical correction of traumatic injuries.

Aim of the study. To study and conduct a comparative evaluation of changes in the circadian rhythm of minute blood volume in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods of the study. Thirty-six children (group 1) hospitalized at RNCEEMP from 2016 to 2021 and 35 children (group 2) from 2023 to 2024 with severe combined TBI were admitted to the clinic due to road traffic accidents (30) and falls from height (5). Each patient group was divided and studied in 3 subgroups. Traumatized patients in Group 1 were studied in randomized subgroups: in Subgroup 1 (13 patients), conservative therapy was administered according to indications; in Subgroup 2 (14 children), extracranial surgical corrective operations were performed according to indications; and in Subgroup 3, 9 patients underwent intracranial and extracranial surgical interventions within the first 3 days according to indications. Patients in Group 2 were represented as follows: Subgroup 1 included 13 children without surgery; extracranial operations were performed in 14 patients; and within the first hours of admission, according to indications, cranial and extracranial

surgeries involving a neurosurgeon, abdominal surgeon, and traumatologist were performed on 8 children. No significant age differences were observed between the groups. Monitoring was conducted through comprehensive hourly recording of body temperature, hemodynamic, and respiratory parameters. Mechanical respiratory support was initiated with artificial lung ventilation (ALV) for a short period, followed by transition to SIMV. As the patients' conditions improved, with stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and recovery of reflexes and consciousness, they were transferred to the specialized department.

Results and Discussion.

Table 1. Comparative Evaluation of Mean Values of the Phase Structure of CR CO.

Groups	Mesor, l/min	In Acrophase, l/min	In Bathypase, l/min	Amplitude, l/min	Range, l/min.
Group 1 Subgroup 1, 10 Days	5,5±0,4	6,5±0,7	4,8±0,4	1,0±0,5	1,7±0,5
Group 2 Subgroup 1, 10 Days	4,7±0,9	5,8±1,0	4,1±1,0	1,1±0,4	1,7±0,4
Group 1 Subgroup 2, 10 Days	5,7±0,3	6,9±0,9	4,8±0,5	1,2±0,9	2,1±1,2
Group 2 Subgroup 2, 10 Days	4,7±0,4*	5,7±0,8	3,6±0,7	1,0±0,5	2,1±0,9
Group 1 Subgroup 3, 10 Days	6,1±0,4	7,2±0,3	5,3±0,4	0,4±1,3	1,7±0,5
Group 2 Subgroup 3, 10 Days	6,2±0,6	8,3±0,9	4,4±0,9	2,1±0,7	3,9±1,1
Group 1 Subgroup 1 26 days	5,6±0,5	6,8±0,8	4,6±0,4	1,2±0,5	2,3±0,9
Group 2 Subgroup 1 29 days	4,4±0,7	5,8±1,0	3,3±0,7*	1,4±0,5	2,5±0,9
Group 1 Subgroup 2 30 days	5,7±0,5	7,2±1,0	4,6±0,6	1,5±0,8	2,6±1,1
Group 2 Subgroup 2 21 days	4,8±0,3*	6,0±0,8	3,6±0,6	1,2±0,6	2,4±1,1
Group 1 Subgroup 3 30 days	5,8±0,4	7,0±0,5	4,8±0,5	1,2±0,4	2,2±0,5
Group 2 Subgroup 3 28 days	6,2±0,6	8,6±0,9	4,1±0,8	2,4±0,7*	4,4±1,1*

*-difference is statistically significant compared to the indicator in Group 1.

In the comparative assessment of the mean values of the phase structure of CR CO, a statistically significant decrease in mesor CR CO was found in Subgroup 2 of Group 2 by 17% (p<0.05) during the first 10 days after surgery, as well as during 21 days of treatment in the ICU by 19% (p<0.05) (Table 1). A decrease in CO during the bathypase was also observed in Subgroup 1 of Group 2 by 28% (p<0.05). Notably, in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group, a 100% increase in the amplitude of CR CO was observed (p<0.05), along with a 100% increase in the daily fluctuation of CO (p<0.05) (Table 1). On the first day, in all patients from both groups, the mesor CR CO exceeded the calculated normative level according to literature sources (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparative assessment of the mesor CR CO in two groups

Days	Group 1, Subgroup 1	Group 2, Subgroup 1	1 grp 2 subgrp	2 grp 2 subgrp	1 grp 3 subgrp	2 grp 3 subgrp
1	6,0±0,5	6,3±0,8	6,2±0,9	5,3±0,5	5,7±0,6	4,9±1,0
2	6,0±0,2	6,5±0,5	6,3±0,3	5,6±0,4	6,6±0,4	6,8±0,6*
3	5,9±0,5	5,5±0,4	5,9±0,2	5,2±0,2 ^{'''}	6,8±0,4*	7,4±0,8*
4	5,5±0,3	5,1±0,4	5,3±0,3	4,6±0,3 ^{'''}	6,7±0,4	7,1±0,7*
5	5,1±0,3*	4,5±0,2* ^{'''}	5,7±0,3	4,3±0,3* ^{'''}	6,0±0,3	5,7±0,4
6	4,9±0,3*	4,6±0,4*	5,7±0,3	4,4±0,4 ^{'''}	5,7±0,2	5,6±0,5
7	5,1±0,3*	3,8±0,3* ^{'''}	5,5±0,3	4,4±0,4 ^{'''}	5,5±0,3	6,0±0,7
8	5,1±0,3*	3,5±0,2* ^{'''}	5,9±0,3	4,6±0,3 ^{'''}	6,0±0,4	6,0±1,0
9	5,5±0,3	3,5±0,2* ^{'''}	5,2±0,3	4,6±0,4	6,2±0,4	6,1±0,9
10	6,0±0,4	3,7±0,3* ^{'''}	5,7±0,4	4,6±0,4 ^{'''}	6,0±0,5	6,2±1,2
11	5,2±0,4	4,2±0,4* ^{'''}	6,2±0,6	4,9±0,5 ^{'''}	5,7±0,5	6,1±0,7
12	5,5±0,3	4,3±0,5* ^{'''}	5,8±0,5	4,9±0,6	6,2±0,4	6,6±0,7
13	4,9±0,3*	5,0±0,9	5,8±0,5	4,5±0,5	6,0±0,5	7,7±1,1*
14	5,5±0,4	4,3±0,7*	5,2±0,3	4,5±0,3 ^{'''}	5,2±0,2	7,4±1,1* ^{'''}
15	4,9±0,2*	4,1±0,6*	5,6±0,3	4,8±0,4 ^{'''}	5,7±0,4	7,0±0,8* ^{'''}
16	4,9±0,4*	3,7±0,3* ^{'''}	5,3±0,4	4,4±0,4	6,1±0,3	7,8±0,6* ^{'''}
17	5,5±0,4	4,2±0,5* ^{'''}	4,8±0,5	4,5±0,4	6,4±0,5	5,9±0,7
18	5,0±0,6	4,3±0,6*	4,7±0,4	4,5±0,3	5,4±0,3	5,8±0,5
19	5,5±0,6	3,7±0,5* ^{'''}	6,1±0,5	5,7±0,6	5,7±0,4	6,7±0,7
20	5,9±0,6	3,5±0,3* ^{'''}	5,3±0,5	5,0±0,8	5,8±0,4	5,3±0,7
21	5,8±0,4	3,6±0,4 ^{'''}	6,0±0,6	4,9±1,5	6,5±0,4	5,7±0,7
22	5,3±0,6	3,6±0,5 ^{'''}	6,3±0,6		6,3±0,7	5,7±0,9
23	6,1±0,5	3,9±0,4 ^{'''}	6,5±0,5		5,2±0,3	6,3±1,1
24	7,0±0,8	2,6±0,4 ^{'''}	6,6±0,6		6,0±0,5	5,7±1,2
25	7,3±0,7	3,5±0,7 ^{'''}	5,2±0,6		5,5±0,4	5,5±0,9
26	7,0±0,9	6,3±1,0	4,5±0,7		5,2±0,4	5,4±0,7
27		4,7±0,5	5,6±0,5		5,6±0,8	4,5±1,0
28		5,0±0,9	5,5±0,6		5,2±0,4	6,1±1,1
29		4,9±0,5	6,4±0,5		5,2±0,7	
30			7,3±1,1		4,2±0,2	

* — significant relative to the indicator on day 1.

''' — significant relative to the indicator in group 1.

On the first day, the observed increase in mesor CR CO relative to the age norm indicated a tendency of the circulatory system's response to develop a hyperdynamic type of hemodynamics. During conservative intensive therapy in

children of group 1, a 15%-18% decrease in the indicator was noted on days 5, 6, 7, 8, 13, 15, and 16. In group 2, by day 5, the indicator decreased by 27%, and by day 8, CO decreased by 44% ($p < 0.05$, respectively). The indicator remained within normal limits up to day 25. These findings indicate a more effective stress-protective comprehensive correction with conservative therapy in SCTBI in children of group 2 (Table 2). After successful extracranial surgeries in group 1, no significant change in the mesor CR CO indicator was observed; that is, the indicator did not differ from the mesor CR CO on day 1. In children of group 2, a statistically significant decrease in the mesor CR CO was observed on day 5 by 18% ($p < 0.05$), with this level maintained until the end of treatment. Compared to group 1, the mesor CR CO after extracranial surgeries in group 2 remained significantly lower throughout the entire observation period. In the most severe subgroup 3 of group 1, the mesor CR CO at the peak of the inflammatory response increased by 19% on day 3 ($p < 0.05$), and in the subsequent days did not differ from the value on day 1. In the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group, an increase in the mesor CR CO was observed on days 2, 3, and 4 by 38%, 51%, and 44%, respectively, and further on days 13, 14, 15, and 16, the mesor CR CO increased by 57%, 51%, 42%, and 58% ($p < 0.05$, respectively). This was apparently associated with insufficiently effective blocking of factors causing secondary brain injury, accompanied by a hyperdynamic pattern of hemodynamic changes, indicating compensatory mobilization of cardiovascular function in response to prolonged systemic inflammatory reaction at later stages (after day 13) of acute cerebral insufficiency following brain surgeries accompanied by extracranial surgical corrections of the sustained traumatic injuries.

Fig. 1. Amplitude of CR CO in the 1st subgroup.

Fig. 2. Amplitude of CR CO in the 2nd subgroup.

Fig. 3. Amplitude of CR CO in the 3rd subgroup.

Fig. 4. Daily fluctuations of CO in the 1st subgroup.

Fig. 5. Daily fluctuations of CO in the 2nd subgroup.

Fig. 6. Daily fluctuations of CO in the 3rd subgroup.

The longest inversion of CR CO was observed in the 2nd subgroup of the 1st group, corresponding to a prolonged systemic vascular resistance after extracranial surgeries, prior to the adoption of the ‘golden hour’ principle, due to the insufficient effectiveness of delayed surgical corrective interventions following severe combined TBI.

Table 3. Inversion of CR CO.

Groups	9-11 hours (normal)	12-22 hours (moderate shift)	23-8 hours (inversion)
Group 1, Subgroup 1	15% (4)	57% (15)	28% (7)
Group 2, Subgroup 1	24% (7)	44% (13)	32% (9)
Group 1, Subgroup 2	23% (7)	16% (5)	51% (18)
Group 2, Subgroup 2	28% (6)	47% (10)	25% (5)
Group 1, Subgroup 3	46% (14)	20% (6)	34% (10)
Group 2, Subgroup 3	31% (9)	38% (10)	31% (9)

The longest inversion of the circadian rhythm of CO was observed in Subgroup 2 of Group 1, indicating the most pronounced mobilization of compensatory activity of the phase structure components of CR CO in children undergoing extracranial surgeries (Table 3). This can be explained by the negative effect on compensatory mechanisms of adaptive reserves of the body systems due to delayed, primarily organizational, factors related to the surgical correction of injuries

caused by SCTBI. It is well known that the shift of the peak increase of CO to nighttime hours is one of the pathogenetic factors leading to the development of acute cardiac decompensation. In the 2nd subgroup of the 2nd group, specialized surgical care during the first hours after injury resulted in a twofold decrease in the duration of inversion of the circadian rhythm of CO.

Fig. 7. CR CO in the 1st subgroup

Fig. 8. CR CO in the 2nd subgroup

Fig. 9. CR CO in the 3rd subgroup

Таблица 4. Корреляционные связи мезора ЦРМОК в 1 группе

Параметры	10 суток			11-30 сутки			Время лечения в ОРИТ		
	Group 1, Sub-group 1	1 gr 2 subgrp	1 gr 3 subgrp	Group 1, Sub-group 1	1 gr 2 subgrp	1 gr 3 subgrp	Group 1, Sub-group 1	1 gr 2 subgrp	1 gr 3 subgrp
МОК/УОК	0,93	0,74	0,62	0,92	0,42	0,91	0,90	0,45	0,86
МОК/СрАД	-0,56	-0,45	-0,12	-0,04	-0,24	-0,53	-0,06	-0,23	-0,41
МОК/ПАД	0,58	0,64	0,68	0,39	0,63	0,74	0,40	0,63	0,75
МОК/ДАД	-0,77	-0,79	-0,42	-0,29	-0,14	-0,71	-0,34	-0,16	-0,66
МОК/САД	-0,65	-0,49	-0,30	-0,07	0,06	-0,20	-0,17	-0,08	-0,27
МОК/Т	-0,58	-0,46	0,84	-0,39	0,81		-0,44	0,40	0,84

During the first 10 days after injury, conservative therapy was associated with CO values relatively closer to physiological norms in subgroup 1 of group 2 (4.7 ± 0.1 l/min) compared to group 1 (5.5 ± 0.1 l/min) (Fig. 7). A similar degree of difference was observed in the extracranial surgeries group, where the average circadian rhythm (CR) of CO in group 1 was 5.7 ± 0.1 l/min, and in group 2 was

4.7±0.1 l/min, representing a 17% reduction compared to group 1 (p<0.05) (Fig. 8). Only in the most severely affected patients in group 1 did the CR CO reach 6.1±0.1 l/min, compared to 6.2±0.3 l/min in group 2. То есть гипердинамический тип кровообращения наблюдался в 1 и 2 группах увеличением СЦР МОК почти на 30% (рис. 9).

В первой группе в первой декаде интенсивной терапии травмированных детей обнаружена прямая связь УОК и МОК в 1 подгруппе (0,93), 2 подгруппе (0,74), в 3 подгруппе (0,62) (таб.4). Которая в последующие дни сохранилась в 1 подгруппе (0,90), в 3 подгруппе (0,86), и в меньшей степени во 2 подгруппе (0,45). During the first 10 days, a significant inverse correlation between CO and DBP, amounting to -0.77 in subgroup 1, -0.79 in subgroup 2, and less pronounced at -0.42 in subgroup 3, confirmed the development of a hyperdynamic type of hemodynamics in response to traumatic stress. This correlation somewhat weakened in subgroups 1 and 2 (-0.34; -0.08) and, conversely, intensified in subgroup 3 (-0.66). Notably, in subgroup 3 of children in group 1, the strongest direct correlation of CO with temperature response persisted throughout the entire observation period, amounting to 0.84. Thus, the hyperdynamic reaction of the circulatory system was directly related to the severity of the systemic inflammatory response. These findings further underscore the paramount importance of infection, alongside the area of damaged tissue, in determining the severity of condition in SCTBI. In group 2, a strong direct correlation between COA and CO was observed across three subgroups during the first 10 days, significantly weakening only in subgroup 3 (0.47), which can be attributed to the development of a myocardial energy-deficit state following cranial and extracranial corrective surgeries. A negative correlation between mesor CR CO and mesor CR DBP was also observed in group 1. A trend toward a direct relationship between body temperature and mesor CR CO was noted in subgroup 3 throughout intensive therapy in the ICU (Table 5).

Table 5. Correlation relationships of mesor CR CO in group 2.

Параметры	10 days			11-30 сутки			Время лечения в ОРИТ		
	Group 2, Sub-group 1	2 grp 2 subgrp	2 grp 3 subgrp	Group 2, Sub-group 1	2 grp 2 subgrp	2 grp 3 subgrp	Group 2, Sub-group 1	2 grp 2 subgrp	2 grp 3 subgrp
МОК/УОК	0,95	0,93	0,84	-0,06	0,76	0,29	0,82	0,84	0,47
МОК/СрАД	-0,58	-0,87	-0,33	0,50	-0,33	0,43	-0,10	-0,55	0,23
МОК/ПАД	-0,40	0,40	0,36	0,58	-0,31	0,71	0,35	-0,07	0,60
МОК/ДАД	-0,72	-0,86	-0,61	0,33	-0,25	0,36	-0,17	-0,51	0,12
МОК/САД	-0,74	-0,74	-0,24	0,66	-0,36	0,52	0,09	-0,48	0,33
МОК/Т	-0,54	-0,17	0,68	-0,78	0,43		-0,24	0,15	0,68

Conclusion. On the first day, an increase in mesor CR CO was observed in all injured patients, indicating a hyperdynamic response of the circulatory system to SCTBI. A more effective stress-protective comprehensive conservative therapy for SCTBI in children was demonstrated in the second group. The hyperdynamic response of the circulatory system was directly related to the severity of the hyperthermic reaction in the 3rd subgroup. In the 2nd group, a strong direct correlation between COA and CO was observed across three subgroups during the first 10 days, significantly weakening only in the 3rd subgroup. This can be explained by the development of an energy-deficient myocardial state in patients undergoing cranial and extracranial corrective surgeries.

References

- 1) *Kuldashev K. A. Severe combined traumatic brain injury: comprehensive diagnostics at the stages of medical care. Journal 'Questions of Neurosurgery' named after N. N. Burdenko. 2012; 76(6):40-44.*
- 2) <https://medbe.ru/materials/cherepno-mozgovye-narusheniya/printsipy-intensivnoy-terapii-tyazheloy-cherepno-mozgovoy-travmy/>
- 3) <http://www.stm-journal.ru/en/numbers/2010/4/685/pdf>
- 4) https://meduniver.com/Medical/Xirurgia/serdce_i_sosudi_pri_travme_mozga.
- 5) *NeurocritCare (2024) 40:477-485* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12028-023-01777-3>

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WILL TAKE TREATMENT TO THE NEXT LEVEL

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Abstract. *Currently, we live in an information society where technologies have become an integral part of our lives; yet few truly realize how far science has progressed. Human-made technologies are, in many ways, already capable of surpassing us. At present, numerous servers with artificial intelligence are being developed that can predict all steps in advance. The implementation of digital technologies has led to significant changes in economic and social infrastructures. Addressing the challenges of machine learning and AI in the Internet of Things for medical applications enables the acquisition of a vast amount of data. The rapid development of hardware, software, and communication technologies has facilitated the emergence of sensor devices connected to the Internet that provide monitoring and measurement of data from the physical world.*

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, neural modeling, functions, internet theory of optimal control*

The technology of Internet-connected devices, known as the Internet of Things (IoT), continues to expand the existing Internet by enabling communication and interaction between the physical world and cyberspace. The Internet of Things undoubtedly transforms the healthcare industry, redefining the landscape of devices and human interaction in delivering medical solutions, resulting in applications that benefit patients, families, physicians, hospitals, and insurance companies. The use of remote monitoring in the healthcare sector, enabled by neural networks, can potentially ensure patient safety and health, providing physicians with the opportunity to deliver superior care, thereby enhancing patient engagement and satisfaction through their interactions with doctors. becomes simpler and more efficient. Moreover, remote monitoring of patients' health status helps reduce hospital stay

duration and prevent readmissions, significantly lowering healthcare costs and improving treatment outcomes.

Artificial Intelligence is the capability of technological inventions to imitate human intelligent behavior. They must search for, process, and perceive constantly changing information to make correct decisions promptly. It can process an enormous volume of information, pages per second. Its algorithms are widely applied in medicine, assisting doctors in detecting various diseases and prescribing treatments. Currently, specialists are developing numerous AI-based services. Such services can not only monitor patient conditions but also prescribe approximate treatment plans; thus, according to developers, AI can help address problems such as the incorrect interpretation of medical information and clinical indicators. For instance, researchers at Duke University have developed the applications *Autism & Beyond* and *mPower*, which can track symptoms of diseases such as Parkinson's disease, autism, and others. Similar 'smart' services and applications are also being developed and used by various corporations, including Google, IBM, Apple, General Electric, and others [1]. Among the most prominent examples of AI in medicine are the developments by Google and IBM: the services *Deepmind Health* and *Watson Health* [2]. For example, a service developed by Google is already in use in several British hospitals and clinics. Currently, *DeepMind Health* is collaborating with a leading British ophthalmology clinic. With the help of artificial intelligence, doctors can analyze numerous images to identify, for example, early signs of blindness or predict acute kidney diseases, as well as prepare recommendation sheets for patients. To monitor kidney function, the program uses blood test results. It determines the content of various substances capable of causing acute diseases. The research results are automatically sent to healthcare professionals as a report [3]. However, this is not the only technological giant whose capabilities facilitate the work of modern medical professionals [4]. In addition, specialists from another company, IBM, one of the largest software producers globally, developed the *Watson Health* service [5]. *IBM Watson* is already extensively assisting doctors in conducting various diagnostics and detecting diseases. For example, this service was already able to identify a serious disease in a patient at a foreign clinic, although the doctors were convinced it was an entirely different diagnosis.

The *Watson* computer has access to various data sources: encyclopedias, scientific articles, electronic libraries, and other resources.

Thanks to its vast computing and data processing capabilities, *IBM Watson* has analyzed more than 30 billion medical images and 50 million anonymous electronic medical records. Recently, *IBM Watson* developers have begun collaborating with the American Heart Association [6].

Author's definition of Artificial Intelligence: "*Artificial Intelligence represents a collective term for a wide range of technical and information technologies based on imitating certain functions of the human brain.*"

Artificial Intelligence is the factor that enables the creation of a simulation model for virtually any disease progression. We set the initial state of the patient using the function $F_1(x_1, x_2 \dots x_n)$, x_i — factors describing the patient's condition. We denote the objective function $F_2(y_1, y_2 \dots y_n)$, y_i — factors describing the patient's optimal condition

Then the task is formulated as follows: it is necessary to transition from $F_1(x_1, x_2 \dots x_n)$ to $F_2(y_1, y_2 \dots y_n, t)$, where x_i — indicators describing the initial condition, y_i — indicators describing the desired patient condition, t — the time after which the transition occurs F_1 to F_2 . Possible scenarios:

- the initial condition allows achieving the desired state; it is necessary to calculate the time value (t) after which the patient will be healthy;
- The initial state does not allow achieving the desired state;
- The initial state allows achieving the desired state, but additional intervention is required, and the timing is uncertain.

It is necessary to develop a simulation model of this process by leveraging the capabilities of artificial intelligence. This has been quite successfully implemented so far in certain areas of medicine. In the future, it will be implemented across all fields of medicine without a doubt! Such a simulation model enables imitation through artificial intelligence until the optimal values of intervention parameters and decision-making time are determined. That is, the practice of treatment dynamics through trial and error will be eliminated. The neural network developed by the author for diabetes diagnosis [7] has a practical orientation and may be highly in demand. The neural network is based on the analysis of a large dataset. Sample: over one million patients, with approximately 12 medical parameters per patient. Such a dataset allowed the construction of a sufficiently deterministic mathematical model. Moreover, the neural network allows simulating the actual process of disease progression. By simulating all possible outcomes, the process can be optimized.

Most importantly, the Network can be integrated into the registration system of Clinic A, allowing the database of patients from this specific clinic to be uploaded into the network. The neural network will then provide information about patients who have a predisposition to diabetes mellitus, and this at an early stage.

Thus, thanks to AI technology, the work of medical professionals has become significantly easier. Innovations enable more precise studies, the detection of various diseases, faster identification of appropriate treatments, and continuous monitoring of patient health. And this is just a small part of what Artificial Intelligence has contributed to healthcare.

Conclusion

One of the most promising directions in medicine, in my opinion, is the transition from a probabilistic model to a simulation model.

References

- 1. The future is already here: how Artificial Intelligence is applied in medicine // vc.ru URL: <https://mhealthcongress.ru/ru/article/vozmognosti-ii-v-medicine>*
- 2. Capabilities of AI in medicine: examples of application // mhealthcongress.ru URL: [meditsine-primeri-primeneniya-96282](https://mhealthcongress.ru/meditsine-primeri-primeneniya-96282)*
- 3. Google DeepMind can detect kidney disease exacerbation earlier than physicians // habr.com URL: <https://habr.com/ru/news/t/462561/>.*
- 4. Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Examples of Applications Worldwide and in Russia // cossa.ru URL: <https://www.cossa.ru/special/medicine/215186/>*
- 5. Artificial Intelligence in Medicine // blog.mednote.life URL: <https://blog.mednote.life/articles/technology/iskusstvenny-intellekt-v-medicine>*
- 6. Mathematical Analysis of Biomedical Data. \Murtuzaliev M. M. UMP. Alef Makhachkala 2022*
- 7. Certificate of registration of the electronic educational resource No. ROSS RU.31618.04PKHNO.*

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BIOLOGICAL METHOD OF PULPITIS TREATMENT

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Abstract. *Currently, in our country, the proportion of patients diagnosed with pulpitis, according to various authors, ranges from 20.6% to 46.3% of all individuals seeking dental care. In the treatment of accidentally exposed pulp chambers, initial stages, and reversible forms of pulpitis, conservative treatment methods are employed: the technique of vital amputation followed by the application of therapeutic agents for direct and indirect pulp capping. Additionally, some dentists incorporate various physical factors into the treatment regimen that contribute to controlling inflammation and improving the regenerative potential of tissues.*

Keywords: *pulpitis, biological treatment method, root canal, biocompatibility, osteogenesis*

Primarily, pulpitis is the most common complication of caries, as the pulp responds to the carious process with an inflammatory reaction upon the penetration of pathogenic microbes and their toxins into the dentinal tubules. However, other predisposing factors have also been identified that lead to the development of this disease, such as iatrogenic factors — accidental pulp exposure during preparation, heating of the pulp causing its complete or partial necrosis, overdrying the tooth with air, or pulp irritation by filling and medicinal materials. A third possible cause of pulpitis development is tooth trauma.

Literature review. The predominant etiological factors of pulpitis are usually various microorganisms, their metabolic products — toxins, degradation products of dentin's organic substance, chemical and toxic substances, as well as thermal, mechanical, and physical irritants. Pulpitis is characterized by a polymorphic microbial flora predominantly consisting of streptococci and other putrefactive microbes. Pulp inflammation can occur in intact teeth due to the penetration of microorganisms from adjacent teeth with infectious foci, retrogradely through one of the apical foramina, as well as through the root canals from the periodontal pocket into the pulp, especially in cases of periodontitis or after certain surgical interventions. The course of the inflammatory process in the pulp primarily depends on the overall reactivity of the organism and can proceed according to either hyperergic or hypoergic types of immunological reactions. The characteristics of pulp inflammation involve the process occurring within the tooth cavity, confined by rigid walls, leading to increased intrapulpal pressure that impairs blood circulation, causing compression, subsequent hypoxia, and local necrosis; therefore, inflammation in the pulp progresses more rapidly than in other tissues.

Complete removal of the pulp typically has a negative impact on the properties of the tooth — disrupting protective, trophic, and reparative functions — which results in the loss of the tooth's functional significance, development of complications in the periapical tissues, and eventual tooth loss, considered an unfavorable treatment outcome.

Despite the advisability of using the biological method for the treatment of pulpitis, especially at the early stages of the pathological process, in cases of accidental exposure of the tooth cavity in patients of different age groups without complicating somatic pathology, this method has not secured a dominant position among other pulpitis treatment approaches.

The unique ability of the pulp to mineralize and thereby protect itself forms a basis for an optimistic prognosis regarding the preservation of its viability.

It is known that the bacterial factor must be taken into account for the rapid restoration of pulp vitality after a short-term inflammatory reaction. Calcium hydroxide is most often recommended as a dressing, as it provides: 1) bactericidal action; coagulation and dissolution of necrotic tissues; 2) prevention of bone tissue resorption; 3) induction of osteocemental apical barrier formation; 4) stimulation of dentin bridge formation (in direct pulp capping).

At the same time, calcium-containing preparations have several disadvantages: 1) resorption of the material in a moist environment; 2) reduced effectiveness upon contact with air due to partial carbonation.

Current methods of biological treatment of pulpitis aim to remove necrotic and altered coronal pulp while preserving its vitality. Vital amputation is performed following aseptic and antiseptic protocols, under anesthesia; the tooth cavity is

opened and exposed using a bur, and amputation is then performed — using a sharp excavator or pulpoextractor with undermining movements from the walls along the floor to remove the coronal pulp. At present, this method is employed with the application on the pulp of a mixture of an antibiotic with sulfanilamide drugs, calcium hydroxide, and antibiotics combined with glucocorticoids.

Treatment using antibiotic-glucocorticoid pastes. The treatment is performed in two stages: during the first stage, the paste is applied for 2-7 days; in the second stage, if no pain is present, the paste is removed and an odontotropic zinc-eugenol or calcium hydroxide-containing paste that stimulates the dentinogenic function of the pulp is applied. Clinical experience has shown that at present this technique yields the best results.

Today, the dental market offers a wide variety of therapeutic liners with pronounced anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects, aimed at preserving pulp vitality. Calcium hydroxide is used quite successfully for treating pulpitis. It is used both in its pure form and in combination with burnt magnesia, soda, potassium bromide, eugenol, antibiotics, and antiseptics. The drug Kalmetsin, besides calcium hydroxide, contains zinc oxide, dry blood plasma, and Albuclid. A methylcellulose solution is used as the base; the paste hardens within 2-3 minutes. Calcin is produced as a paste containing calcium hydroxide and zinc oxide; the base is a mixture of glycerin and petrolatum. The widespread use of calcium hydroxide is due to its antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and odontotropic effects; however, it also has significant drawbacks.

Certain successes in preserving the pulp have been achieved through the use of corticosteroid medications. Glucocorticoid-containing pastes are prepared based on roughly the same principle; they include a glucocorticoid, an antibiotic, and an anesthetic agent. Some authors believe that these reduce the reactive capacity of the pulp and do not promote dentinogenesis; however, most authors acknowledge that, under specific indications, corticosteroids — with anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, and anti-proliferative effects — lead to rapid clinical recovery with restoration of pulp vitality.

New possibilities for the biological treatment method of pulpitis have been introduced by the material 'ProRoot MTA' (Dentsply). The basis of the material is Portland cement, a mixture of calcium silicates and calcium-containing aluminum and iron compounds. However, the high cost of this preparation makes the effective treatment method inaccessible to patients in budget healthcare facilities.

Currently, dentists frequently use ProRoot MTA, TrioxideDent, and Rudent in their practice for treating reversible forms of pulpitis.

ProRoot MTA properties: biocompatibility, stimulation of osteogenesis, moisture resistance, antimicrobial properties, absence of mutagenic activity, and low cytotoxicity. A disadvantage is poor handling properties due to insufficient plasticity and flow when mixed with water. ProRoot MTA should not be used to fill the tooth

crown; it is intended only for use within the root canals and pulp chamber, as it may cause tooth discoloration. Indications: exposure of the pulp horn, retrograde filling of root canals, and tooth perforations.

TrioxideDent and Rutdent are Russian analogs of ProRoot MTA. Their properties include biocompatibility, stimulation of apexogenesis and osteogenesis, promotion of dentin bridge formation during pulp capping, bactericidal effects, low solubility, high mechanical strength, and impermeability to microorganisms. The drawback of this material is that it imparts a grayish tint to the tooth crown. It is used as a therapeutic and insulating pulp capping material, for retrograde filling, and for filling the upper apical part of the canal with incomplete root formation.

In experiments on animals, it was found that after the application of the therapeutic dressing, within a few days there is an increase in the number of leukocytes, macrophages, and plasma cells in the subodontoblastic layer of the pulp, which corresponds to the norm. Subsequently, the growth of fibroblasts increases, the concentration of fibrous structures in the pulp rises, and by the sixth month, a zone of reparative replacement dentin is formed. Observations have shown that the changes in the pulp structures were functional in nature, with activation of reactive and regenerative processes and restoration of the dentinogenic function of the tooth pulp.

Patients after biological treatment should remain under observation. The first follow-up is performed after 1.5 to 3 months, then after 6 months and 1 year. The absence of changes in the bone tissue indicates the effectiveness of the specified method and the necessity of placing a permanent filling. Clinical criteria for successful treatment are the absence of pain, normal pulp electric excitability indices, and no changes in the periodontium.

The effectiveness of treatment by conservative methods depends on several factors, such as the time factor — the duration of pulpitis development does not exceed 1-3 days — as well as the patient's age, general condition, and the correct selection of the treatment method.

Conclusion. Thus, without timely treatment, pulpitis can develop into a chronic, advanced form, which may eventually result in tooth loss. Current methods for treating reversible forms of pulpitis involve the appropriate selection and rational application of a treatment method tailored to the specific clinical case. Currently, the dental market offers numerous medications for treating pulpitis; it is essential to properly choose the treatment method and select the appropriate drug for each patient.

Prevention of pulpitis involves timely treatment of caries, visiting the dentist twice a year, careful maintenance of oral hygiene, and monitoring overall health.

References

1. *Oral cavity diseases in COVID-19* / Karakov K. G., Kasimova G. V., Alfimova O. A., Mordasov N. A. Stavropol, 2025
2. *Clinical Course of Therapeutic Dentistry* / Karakov K. G., Vlasova T. N., Kasimova G. V., Alfimova O. A. Stavropol, 2025
3. *The influence of metabolic syndrome components on the development of chronic generalized periodontitis.* Karakov K. G., Kasimova G. V., Eremenko A. V., Markarova E. V., Vanchenko N. B. *Periodontology*. 2017. Vol. 22. No. 1 (82). Pp. 15-19.
4. *Ultrasonic irrigation in root canal treatment.* Alfimova O. A., Mordasov N. A., Kalita Z. O. In the collection: *New Developments in the Theory and Practice of Dentistry. Proceedings of the 21st Forum of the Scientific and Practical Conference of Dentists of Southern Russia 'Topical Issues in Clinical Dentistry,' dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor V. I. Grechishnikov.* 2022. pp. 18-20.
5. *Use of diode laser in endodontics.* Alfimova O. A., Mordasov N. A., Kasimova G. V., Denisova Z. O., Solovyova O. A., Talybova M. A., Karakov K. G. In the collection: *New developments in the theory and practice of dentistry. Proceedings of the XXII Forum within the framework of the scientific-practical conference of dentists of Southern Russia 'Dentistry of the XXI Century,' dedicated to the 85th anniversary of Stavropol State Medical University and the 65th anniversary of the Faculty of Dentistry.* 2023. pp. 13-14.
6. *Study of the quality of mechanical preparation of root canals in teeth using reciprocal and rotary endodontic systems.* Zelensky A. K., Alieva P. A., Alfimova O. A. In the collection: *Medical Science Without Borders. Proceedings of the International Youth Forum.* Stavropol, 2024. pp. 564-565.
7. *Use of the drug "Apexdent" with iodoform in the treatment of destructive forms of periodontitis complicated by maxillary sinusitis* Alfimova O. A., Mordasov N. A., Kasimova G. V., Denisova Z. O., Talybova M. A. In the collection: *New developments in the theory and practice of dentistry. Proceedings of the XXII Forum within the scientific-practical conference of dentists of Southern Russia 'Dentistry of the 21st Century,' dedicated to the 85th anniversary of Stavropol State Medical University and the 65th anniversary of the Faculty of Dentistry.* 2023. pp. 15-17.

8. *Artificial Intelligence as an Assistant to the Dental Therapist and Specific Features of Working with It* Kasimova G. V., Mordasov N. A., Alfimova O. A., Kuznetsova O. V., Samvelyan A. V., Shaugenova M. K. In: *New Developments in the Theory and Practice of Dentistry. Proceedings of the XXII Forum within the framework of the scientific-practical conference of dentists of Southern Russia 'Dentistry of the 21st Century,' dedicated to the 85th anniversary of Stavropol State Medical University and the 65th anniversary of the Faculty of Dentistry.* 2023. pp. 26-30.

9. *Therapeutic approach to the treatment of chronic generalized periodontitis against the background of systemic osteoporosis using a humanized monoclonal antibody (IgG2)* Mordasov N. A., Kasimova G. V., Alfimova O. A., Shatskaya N. V., Usnunts Yu.K.

In the collection: New developments in the theory and practice of dentistry. Proceedings of the XXI Forum of the Scientific and Practical Conference of Dentists of Southern Russia, 'Topical Issues in Clinical Dentistry,' dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor V. I. Grechishnikov. 2022. pp. 47-52.

10. *Doctor and patient at the dental appointment.* Alfimova O. A., Kalita Z. O., Mordasov N. A., Babayan E. G., Markarova G. V. In: *'New Trends in Theory and Practice of Dentistry.'* Proceedings of the 20th Forum of the Scientific and Practical Conference of Dentists of Southern Russia 'Current Issues in Clinical Dentistry,' dedicated to the 80th anniversary of Professor A. I. Volozhin. 2021. pp. 13-17.

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ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH DENTAL HYPERESTHESIA AND GINGIVAL RECESSION

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Abstract. *Inflammatory diseases of the periodontium rank among the leading dental conditions. Pathological changes in the periodontium tissues may contribute to the occurrence of gingival recession. This process is observed as a result of bone tissue atrophy, associated with improper use of ultrasonic equipment causing mechanical damage to the tooth structures. Comprehensive therapy for hypersensitivity of the hard dental tissues involves remineralization of these tissues. We conducted a survey of 75 patients with increased sensitivity of the hard dental tissues, accompanied by gingival recession and diseases of the periodontium. The age of the patients ranged from 25 to 45 years. In patients who adhered to the recommended set of preventive measures, the level of tooth sensitivity decreased. It can be concluded that the development, implementation, and monitoring of a prevention and treatment program are essential; this program should include recommendations for maintaining a healthy lifestyle, eliminating harmful habits, establishing proper balanced nutrition, performing oral sanitation, and professional hygiene.*

Keywords: dental hypersensitivity, gingival recession, periodontium diseases, questionnaire.

Relevance

The analysis of scientific dental literature has led us to conclude that in recent years there has been an increase in the prevalence of periodontium diseases. Research findings demonstrate an increased prevalence of periodontium diseases among the Russian population. Pathology of the periodontium may contribute to the development of gingival margin recession due to the process of bone tissue atrophy. Localized gingival recession in patients with periodontium diseases may lead to increased complaints of heightened sensitivity of tooth hard tissues, as well as symptoms of discomfort in the oral cavity. A classification of medicinal products used for the treatment of dental hypersensitivity is presented. These include dentin adhesive agents, fluoride-containing varnishes and gels, and desensitizing therapeutic and preventive toothpastes and mouthwashes.

Comprehensive treatment of increased sensitivity of the hard dental tissues includes remineralization procedures of these tissues. Minerals such as calcium, phosphorus, fluoride, as well as macro- and microelements, are components of remineralizing agents that contribute to the restoration of hard dental tissues. Currently, remineralizing agents manufactured in Russia are being introduced into clinical practice. A comprehensive approach to treating increased sensitivity of the hard dental tissues in the context of gingival recession is lacking. We deem it necessary to develop and conduct research to implement a treatment method for dental hypersensitivity accompanied by gingival recession into clinical practice. The results derived from the review of scientific studies indicate that the use of Russian-made desensitizing agents for phased therapy in patients with dental hypersensitivity and gingival recession is inadequate.

Materials and Methods

We examined and provided therapeutic treatment to 75 patients with hypersensitivity of the hard dental tissues and gingival recession in the context of inflammatory diseases of the periodontium. The age of patients ranged from 25 to 45 years (Tables 1, 2).

Table 1 — Age and gender characteristics of patients who participated in the study

Characteristics	Number	
Total patients	75	100%
Women 25-25 years	44	58,7%
Men 25-55 years	31	41,3%

brush. In the 3rd group, 7 patients (28%) answered 'yes'; among them, 6 patients (24%) used dental floss and 2 patients (25%) used a tongue brush. Three months after the start of the study, in the first group, 14 patients (56%) began using additional oral hygiene aids, such as a tongue brush and dental floss; among them, 14 patients (56%) used dental floss and 9 patients (36%) used a tongue brush. In the second group, 18 patients (72%) used additional oral hygiene aids; among them, 18 patients (72%) used dental floss and 14 patients (56%) used a tongue brush. In the third group, 23 patients (92%) used additional oral hygiene aids; among them, 23 patients (92%) used dental floss and 19 patients (76%) used a tongue brush.

Question 6. In response to the question 'Do you use irrigators for oral care?', only 6 patients in the 1st group (24%), 6 patients in the 2nd group (24%), and 4 patients in the 3rd group (16%) answered 'yes'. Three months after the start of the study, a positive response to this question was given by 15 patients in the 1st group (60%), 20 patients in the 2nd group (80%), and 24 patients (96%) in the 3rd group.

Question 7. In response to the question 'Do you always experience increased sensitivity when exposed to thermal stimuli?', all patients (100%) gave a positive response before the start of therapy. Three months after the start of the study, a positive response to this question was given by 20 patients (88%) in the 1st group and 15 patients (60%) in the 2nd group; In the 3rd group, patients did not report any problems with dental sensitivity during tooth brushing.

Question 8. In response to the question, 'Do dairy products, such as cottage cheese, appear in your diet?' 22 patients in the 1st group (88%), 21 patients in the 2nd group (84%), and 24 patients in the 3rd group (96%) answered 'yes.' Three months after the start of the study, a positive response to this question was given by 24 patients in Group 1 (96%); 23 patients in Group 2 (92%); and 24 patients (96%) in Group 3.

Question 9. In response to the question, 'Do you include fresh vegetables in your diet during the winter season?' all subjects in all groups answered affirmatively (100%) both before the study and three months after the initiation of therapy.

Question 10. In response to the question, 'Do you include fresh fruits in your diet during the winter season?' all subjects in all groups answered affirmatively (100%) both before the study and three months after the initiation of therapy.

Question 11. In response to the question, 'Do you have harmful habits such as biting pencils, pens, or nails?' 7 patients in the 1st group (28%), 9 patients in the 2nd group (36%), and 7 patients in the 3rd group (28%) answered affirmatively. Three months after the start of the study, 4 patients in the 1st group (16%), 3 patients in the 2nd group (12%), and 2 patients (8%) in the 3rd group responded positively to this question.

Question 12. In response to the question, 'Do you smoke? If yes, what type of smoking do you use?', 8 patients in the 1st group (32%) answered affirmatively; among them, 2 patients (8%) smoked cigarettes, and 6 patients (24%) preferred

alternative types of smoking. In the 2nd group, 7 patients (28%) answered affirmatively; among them, 2 patients (8%) smoked cigarettes, and 5 patients (20%) preferred alternative types of smoking. In the 3rd group, 6 respondents (24%) smoked; among them, 1 patient (4%) smoked cigarettes, and the remaining 5 patients (20%) preferred alternative types of smoking. Three months after the start of the study, a positive response to this question was given by 5 patients in the 1st group (20%), of whom 1 patient smoked cigarettes (4%), and 4 patients preferred alternative types of smoking (16%). In the 2nd group, 4 patients (16%) responded positively, of whom 1 patient reported cigarette smoking (4%), and 3 patients (12%) preferred alternative types of smoking. In the 3rd group, 4 respondents (16%) smoked, of whom 1 patient noted cigarette smoking (4%), and the remaining 3 patients (12%) preferred alternative types of smoking.

Question 13. To the question, 'Do you believe in the success of the upcoming treatment?' 14 patients in the 1st group (56%), 15 patients in the 2nd group (60%), and 17 patients in the 3rd group (68%) answered affirmatively.

Conclusions

The survey conducted among patients from three groups, with a three-month interval, revealed an improvement in the implementation of individual oral hygiene; more patients began using additional oral hygiene aids, such as the tongue brush and dental floss. In patients of the third group who used the prophylactic complex we developed, the level of dental sensitivity decreased. Furthermore, as a result of the motivation provided, patients began consuming more dairy products, fresh vegetables, and fruits, while the proportion of harmful habits decreased. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a clear necessity for the development, implementation, and monitoring of a prevention and treatment program that includes the promotion of a healthy lifestyle, combatting harmful habits, rational nutrition, oral cavity sanitation, professional hygiene procedures, and training in appropriate individual oral hygiene.

References

1. Borisova, E. G. *Assessment of quality of life in patients following dental intervention* / E. G. Borisova, K. D. Balin, M. K. Fedichkina // *Problems of Dentistry*. — 2021. — Volume 17, No. 1. — pp. 5-11.
2. Gazhva, S. I. *Prevalence and severity of inflammatory diseases of the periodontium (literature review)* / S. I. Gazhva, R. S. Guluyev. — *Text: electronic // StomPort: [website]*. — URL: <https://stomport.ru/articles/rasprostranennost-i-intensivnost-vospalitelnyh-zabolevaniy-parodonty-obzor-literatury>. — *Publication Date: July 10, 2014.*

3. *Dental Hypersensitivity: A Textbook* / O. A. Uspenskaya, A. A. Plishkina, M. L. Zhdanova. — Nizhny Novgorod: Publishing House of the Nizhny Novgorod State Medical Academy, 2017. — 68 p. — ISBN 978-5-7032-1151-9.
4. Zhurbenko, V. A. *The Prevalence of Increased Sensitivity of Dental Hard Tissues in Different Age Groups* / V. A. Zhurbenko, A. A. Marinkina // *Regional Bulletin*. — 2020. — No. 12 (51). — pp. 9-11.
5. *Individual approach to the examination of patients and selection of treatment methods for increased dental hypersensitivity* / N. F. Aleshina, N. V. Piperskaya, I. V. Starikova. — DOI 10.19163/1994-9480-2020-3(75)-60-64 // *Bulletin of Volgograd State Medical University*. — 2020. — No. 3 (75). — pp. 60-64.
6. *Clinical and laboratory justification of the efficacy of treatment of inflammatory diseases of the periodontium with adaptogen-based drugs* / A. E. Petrosyan, N. V. Chirkova, A. B. Antonyan, Zh. V. Vecherkina // *Applied Informational Aspects of Medicine*. — 2021. — Vol. 24, No. 1. — pp. 58-61.
7. *Comprehensive approach to the treatment of dental hypersensitivity accompanied by gingival recession in patients with periodontitis* / Chirkova N. V., Tokarev V. A., Vecherkina Zh. V., Aliev A. A., Pshenichnikova D. I., Kharitonov I. D. // *System Analysis and Control in Biomedical Systems*. 2022. Vol. 21. No. 2. pp. 18-24.
8. *A new perspective on the prevention and treatment of periodontium diseases* / O. O. Novikov, E. T. Zhilyakova, A. V. Tsimbalistov [et al.]. — DOI 10.18413/2313-8955-2016-2-3-64-69 // *Scientific Result. Medicine and Pharmacy*. — 2016. — Volume 2, No. 3. — P. 64-69.
9. *Prevalence of dental diseases* / A. G. Zharmagambetova, S. T. Tuleutaeva, S. B. Akhmetova // *Astana Medical Journal*. — 2017. — No. 2 (92). — P. 51-59.
10. *Contemporary aspects of gingival recession treatment* / I. R. Kadyrov, A. K. Khusaenova, M. S. Shatur, A. V. Osipova // *Problems of Scientific Thought*. — 2022. — Vol. 2, No. 4. — pp. 30-32.
11. *Composition of oral microflora as a factor determining the clinical course of chronic generalized catarrhal gingivitis* / Plutakhina A. A., Chirkova N. V., Polushkina N. A., Vecherkina Zh. V., Bobeshko M. N. // *Applied Informational Aspects of Medicine*. 2022. Vol. 25. No. 3. pp. 79-84.

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DENTAL MICROSCOPE IS JUST A FINDING FOR DENTISTS IN THE TREATMENT OF PULPITIS IN BABY AND PERMANENT TEETH IN CHILDREN

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The results of the research study of the abstract concept of nanostructures, microstructures, nanotechnologies and materials, the synthesis and application of nanomaterials in medicine, surface engineering in microstructures and nanotechnologies are discussed. Functionalized nanomaterials, replication in microstructures and nanostructures, template synthesis of arrays of nanorods or nanowires, nanoimprint lithography, application of microstructures and nanotechnologies in stem cell research and technology. Isolation and clinical significance of circulating tumor cells based on microstructures and nanotechnologies. Nanoparticles and microparticles for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases. Scanning microscopy: operating principle, devices and sensors. Nanotheranostics: application of nanoparticles, prospects and problems. Relevance of the study The study of a review of the methodology in dentistry of the method of treating caries under a microscope in milk and permanent teeth in children in Russia, in an experimental study was conducted at the Department of Dentistry and Otorhinolaryngology of the Tambov State University named after G. R. Derzhavin in modern society is undeniable. Based on the data obtained in the course of a dental study, the study of treatment methods lies in the fact that the practical significance of the study and its theoretical provisions in the empirical results obtained can be used by dentists.

Keywords: *methods of caries treatment, in milk and permanent teeth, electron microscope.*

Transmission and reflection microscopes are used to study structure, and properties are assessed using mechanical tensile testing, hardness, and microhardness (V. P. Shelokhovostov). For this purpose, the department has metallographic and

biological microscopes, as well as microhardness testers. In laboratory work, students study powdered raw materials and the microstructure of metals, ceramics, and plastics, which form the basis of technologies in dental practice (V. P. Shelokhovostov). The video can show a series of microscopes with students performing the actions necessary for preparing objects, installing samples, and viewing them in the instrument (alternating between wide-angle and close-up views) (V. P. Shelokhovostov).

The better the doctor can see the true extent of the lesion, the less they drill into healthy tissue beneath the inflamed area. This way, when treating under a microscope, the living and intact portion of the tooth is preserved as much as possible. Already during the initial examination, you will learn much more about the condition of the tooth, your teeth, and what needs to be addressed — that is, strengthen, treat, and replace them promptly before the problem becomes serious. Dental treatment is carried out with the utmost care (information prepared by the doctor).

Fig. 1. Research method: electron microscopy: (a), (b), (c), (d), (e).

Analysis of the grain size distribution curves of carbon nanowall synthesis products:

A — Macrostructure of synthesis products, 50x; 1-5 — Microstructure of carbon nanowalls, 22,000x.

B — Carbon nanotubes.

C — Schematic diagram of the carbon nanowall synthesis process. Plasma flows are formed on evaporator 2 and arc 13;

Sequential condensation of catalyst and carbon on substrate 14 of rotating carousel 3;

The light microscope has clearly defined fields of application due to its limited resolution. As a result, a schematic diagram of an electron microscope depicting electron trajectories is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of an electron microscope showing electron trajectories.

A — Macrostructure of the synthesis products.

B — Nanocomposite structure.

C — Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images in a column.

D — Cross-section of the nanocomposite with an ion beam. It is known that using the resulting image, one can determine that the results of the study.

The study of a dental microscope is a real godsend for dentists. The experimental study was conducted at the Department of Dentistry at Tambov State University named after G. R. Derzhavin in 2023.

References

1. Panchenko E. V., Skakov Yu. A., Krimer B. I., et al. *Metallographic Laboratory*. Moscow: Metallurgy, 1965. pp. 172-243.
2. *Caries and Non-Carious Lesions of Hard Dental Tissues: Textbook for Students of the Faculty of Dentistry* / S. I. Borodovitsyna; Ryazan State Medical University, Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation. — Ryazan: OCiOP, 2019. — 172 p.
3. Belikov A. V., Grisimov V. N., Skripnik A. V., Shatilova K. V. *Lasers in Dentistry (Part 1)*. — St. Petersburg: ITMO University, 2015. — 108 p.
4. *Electron Microscopy: Textbook* / A. I. Vlasov, K. A. El- Sukov, I. A. Kosolapov. — M.: Publishing house of MSTU im. N. E. Bauman, 2011.
5. Nikolaev A. I., Tsepov L. M. *Practical therapeutic dentistry*. St. Petersburg, 2010.
6. Persin L. S., Elizarova V. M., Dyakova S. V. *Pediatric dentistry*. M. "Medicine" 2003.
7. Kolesov A. A. *Pediatric dentistry*. M. "Medicine" 1991.

A POLYMORBID PATIENT AND LATE PRESENTATION: A CLINICAL CASE STUDY

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Abstract. *Late patient presentation entails difficulties in timely diagnosis and delays in providing specialized treatment. The article provides a clinical example of a polymorbid patient with a medical background, where late access to specialized medical care did not prevent a fatal outcome.*

Keywords: *comorbidity, late presentation, fatal outcome*

Introduction. Currently, most patients of working age in the therapeutic profile have several chronic non-infectious diseases of various etiologies, which determines the problem of polymorbidity in medicine. Patients also demonstrate low adherence to treatment and late seeking help, which is associated with ignoring the recommended examination for timely diagnosis of diseases [1]. The problem of late seeking specialized medical care has irreversible consequences and is presented in a clinical case analysis with a colleague as a polymorbid patient.

Clinical case. Patient K., born on March 1, 1966, visited a general practitioner in the emergency department of a multidisciplinary hospital in the Stavropol Territory of the Russian Federation on February 19, 2024, at 09:36, with complaints of chest pain, weakness, and abdominal pain. Anamnesis: the patient informed the therapist that he was a practicing clinical medicine physician and had conditions such as atherosclerotic heart disease, hypertension, and type 2 diabetes, but he did not provide information about the medications he was taking for these conditions, nor did he provide a copy of his previous electrocardiogram, nor did he provide information about his blood pressure and glycated hemoglobin targets and whether

he had achieved them. According to the patient, on the night of 18.02.2024 to 19.02.2024, the patient felt discomfort in the chest and abdominal discomfort at home. Objective examination: the patient's condition is of moderate severity, the skin is pale, and there are no peripheral edema. During auscultation, the patient's breathing is vesicular, and their heart sounds are muffled and rhythmic. The patient's blood pressure is 130/80 mmHg, their heart rate is 79 beats per minute, their respiratory rate is 19 breaths per minute, their oxygen saturation is 98 %, and their body temperature is 36.0 °C. According to the electrocardiographic study (19.02.2024 at 09:36 a.m.), the rhythm is sinus, the heart rate is about 75 beats/min, the electrical axis of the heart is to the left, and the ST segment is on the isoelectric line in all leads; there are no signs of acute myocardial damage. The patient was given a preliminary diagnosis based on their complaints and clinical examination, which required further differentiation: "Pancreatitis? Intercostal neuralgia? Acute coronary syndrome without ST segment elevation?" For the purpose of examination, the patient was urgently prescribed an ultrasound examination of the chest organs, a complete blood count, and a biochemical blood test (indicators: troponin, total bilirubin, liver enzymes, creatinine, urea), chest X-ray, abdominal X-ray and thoracic spine X-ray, consultations with a surgeon and a neurologist. Symptomatic treatment was also performed: platiphylline solution intramuscularly, nitroglycerin solution as a spray 2 times under the tongue.

During a follow-up examination by a general practitioner on February 19, 2024 at 10:10 a.m., patient K. complained of discomfort in the chest, upper abdomen, between the shoulder blades, and weakness. He also mentioned that the abdominal discomfort had occurred at night after a heavy meal, and he had previously experienced similar pain during an exacerbation of cholecystitis.

According to the surgeon's consultation on February 19, 2024 at 10:18:59, it is known that patient K. reported complaints of dull chest pain, interscapular pain, and epigastric pain. When asked about the circumstances surrounding the onset of the pain, the patient stated that he had a heavy meal the night before, but there was no nausea or vomiting. However, during the night, he experienced severe pain in the interscapular region, so he took the medication "Mebeverine" with limited effectiveness. However, in the morning, the pain intensified and spread to the anterior chest wall. The surgeon made a preliminary diagnosis: "Acute gastroduodenitis? Thoracalgia?" and recommended a consultation with a neurologist, repeating the tests previously ordered by the general practitioner for differential diagnosis.

During the consultation, the neurologist did not note any acute neurological disorders during the clinical examination and repeated the instrumental tests previously ordered by the doctors for differential diagnosis.

During a subsequent examination by a general practitioner on February 19, 2024 at 10:35 a.m., the patient's complaints changed, and he reported chest and

abdominal pain with radiation to the shoulder blades, cold sweats, and weakness. Based on the results of the objective examination, the diagnosis of “Acute Myocardial Infarction?” was added to the diagnostic search, followed by the appropriate recommendations for a second electrocardiogram and the call for a cardiologist to determine the patient’s hospitalization in the cardiology department.

The result of a complete blood count: white blood cells 14.34; red blood cells 5.53; hemoglobin 161; hematocrit 45.5; platelets 234.

The result of a biochemical blood test: total bilirubin 4.13; urea 6.6; creatinine 121; glucose 9.8; liver enzymes — normal, troponin 36.

Chest X-ray examination from 19.02.2024 at 10:25 a. m.: the lungs are straightened, focal and infiltrative shadows in the lung parenchyma are not detected, the pulmonary pattern is diffusely enhanced in the middle-lower sections on both sides, the small interlobular fissure on the right is emphasized, the roots are poorly structured, the median shadow is not displaced, not expanded, the shadow of the heart is not expanded, The domes of the diaphragm are usually spread out, the contours are smooth and clear, the right sinuses are free, bone-traumatic changes are not detected at the examination level, and the soft tissues of the chest are not visually altered at the examination level.

Abdominal X-ray examination on 19.02.2024 at 10:29 a. m.: no additional shadows or free gas are detected at the examination level, and a single horizontal fluid level is detected in the left half of the abdomen.

Electrocardiographic examination from 19.02.2024 at 10:40 a. m.— with a persistent sinus rhythm and a heart rate of about 60 beats per minute, there is a negative trend compared to the ECG from 02/19/2024 at 08:20 a. m.— there is an increase in the ST segment above the isoline in lead I with reciprocal changes in lead II and III, where the ST segment is below the isoline, and also elevation of the ST segment above the isoline in the aVL lead with reciprocal changes in the aVF lead (ST segment below the isoline), while in all thoracic leads (V1 to V6) there is also a negative trend in the form of elevation of the ST segment above the isoline, which suggests acute focal changes in the myocardium of the left ventricle in the anterior septal zone This requires comparison with the clinical picture of the patient’s condition and laboratory markers of acute myocardial injury.

However, on February 19, 2024, at 10:45 a. m., after an electrocardiogram was performed before a cardiologist’s consultation, patient K. ’s condition deteriorated rapidly: The patient’s blood pressure dropped to 60/20 mmHg, and he developed facial cyanosis and mental confusion, which were interpreted as a shock condition that required immediate resuscitation. A resuscitation specialist was called in, and appropriate therapy was administered (intravenous administration of atropine and adrenaline solutions, and intravenous drip administration of mezaton). An electrocardiogram showed large-wave ventricular fibrillation, and defibrillation was

performed without success. Resuscitation measures were carried out in full within 30 minutes, but to no effect, and on 19.02.2024 at 11:20, the biological death of patient K. was confirmed.

Forensic-histological diagnosis: Small-focal replacement, perivascular cardio-sclerosis; focal-generalized hypertrophy, lipofuscinosis of cardiomyocytes. Arterioarteriolosclerosis in the myocardium. Hemocirculatory disorders in the presented organs with a predominance of veno-capillary plethora. Edema, dystrophic and necrobiotic changes of neurons in the brain. Diffuse emphysema, focal dys- and atelectasias, and intra-alveolar hemorrhages in the lung. Edema and hemorrhages in the myocardial stroma; focal hyper-eosinophilia, dissociation, and fragmentation of cardiomyocytes. Arterioarteriolosclerosis in the brain, liver, and pancreas. Morphological signs of angiencephalopathy. Chronic hepatitis with low histological activity and moderate fibrosis. Fibrosis and focal lipomatosis in the pancreas. Chronic bronchitis with hyperplasia of bronchial-associated lymphoid tissue, and diffuse pneumosclerosis.

Discussion. On the night of 18.02.2024 to 19.02.2024, patient K. felt discomfort in his chest. Knowing his chronic conditions and being a practicing doctor, he only sought medical attention on the morning of 19.02.2024 at 09:36. Consequently, patient K., who was aware of his chronic conditions (atherosclerotic heart disease, hypertension, and type 2 diabetes), delayed seeking specialized medical care, including the diagnosis of a possible heart condition, until the next morning. This delay in diagnosis and/or differential diagnosis of an acute condition resulted in a potential adverse outcome due to the late seeking of medical assistance.

Since patient K. did not provide any medical documents about his diagnoses when he visited a multidisciplinary hospital and did not disclose information about the medications he was taking, the hospital staff was unable to objectively assess the risk factors for cardiovascular risks and complications, which, combined with the late visit, led to an irreversible outcome.

It should be noted that patient K., who was a doctor himself and knew all his diagnoses, did not provide any electrocardiograms taken earlier on 19.02.2024 when contacting the hospital therapist, therefore it was not possible to compare the electrocardiogram data from 19.02.2024 at 09:36, which is extremely important for diagnosis, as indicated in the Clinical Recommendations according to the “Acute coronary syndrome without ST segment elevation” from 2020 [2]: “The absence of ischemic changes on the ECG should not exclude the diagnosis of “Acute coronary syndrome without ST segment elevation”. An important diagnostic technique is comparing the electrocardiogram recorded before the onset of the current attack with the electrocardiogram recorded after the onset of the attack. The Clinical Guidelines also note that “additional examination methods are required to confirm myocardial ischemia when the electrocardiogram is insufficiently informative, to

exclude diseases with similar clinical symptoms, to detect myocardial infarction, and to assess (stratify) the risk of an unfavorable course of the disease, as well as to identify conditions that affect the patient's management." Accordingly, after a clinical examination and taking into account the patient's complaints, the general practitioner prescribed the necessary examination and consultation plan, and the patient received symptomatic treatment during the diagnostic process to establish a final diagnosis. However, the late seeking of medical assistance prevented the timely diagnosis and initiation of specialized treatment, leading to acute cardiovascular death, as confirmed by postmortem histological examination.

It should be noted retrospectively that patient K. underwent a timely biochemical blood test for markers of acute myocardial damage, which showed an increase in troponin levels to 36, indicating acute myocardial damage. However, the sudden deterioration and death of patient K. were unexpected. The patient was unable to receive the necessary specialized treatment due to the late presentation of the diagnosis, which occurred on February 19, 2024 at 09:36, despite the fact that the patient had been experiencing pain since the night of February 18-19, 2024.

Conclusion: Patient K., being a doctor who was aware of his chronic diseases, evaluated his complaints on his own and did not seek specialized medical assistance. Additionally, Patient K. made a decision to use a medication that he believed was appropriate based on his self-diagnosis of his condition, which led to a delay in seeking professional medical care.

References:

1. Vikentev V. V., Sapunova D. A. Case study of giant cell myocarditis. *Russian Medical Inquiry*. 2025;9(9):567-573 (in Russ.). DOI: 10.32364/2587-6821-2025-9-9.
2. Barbarash O. L., Duplyakov D. V., Zateischikov D. A., Panchenko E. P., Shakhnovich R. M., Yavelov I. S., Yakovlev A. N., Abugov S. A., Alekhan B. G., Arkhipov M. V., Vasilieva E. Yu., Galyavich A. S., Ganyukov V. I., Gilyarevskiy S. R., Golubev E. P., Golukhova E. Z., Gratsiansky N. A., Karpov Yu. A., Kosmacheva E. D., Lopatin Yu. M., Markov V. A., Nikulina N. N., Pevzner D. V., Pogosova N. V., Protopopov A. V., Skrypnik D. V., Tereshchenko S. N., Ustyugov S. A., Khripun A. V., Shalaev S. V., Shpektor V. A., Yakushin S. S. 2020 Clinical practice guidelines for Acute coronary syndrome without ST segment elevation. *Russian Journal of Cardiology*. 2021;26(4):4449. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.15829/1560-4071-2021-4449>.

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SURGICAL TREATMENT OF SILENT MYOCARDIAL ISCHEMIA: CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM

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Abstract. *Silent myocardial ischemia (SMI) is a heterogeneous clinical and pathophysiological phenomenon characterized by objective evidence of transient myocardial ischemia (ECG changes, perfusion or metabolic abnormalities, regional contractile dysfunction) in the complete absence of pain syndrome or its equivalents (dyspnea, weakness, arrhythmia). Despite the absence of symptoms, AMI is associated with a prognosis comparable to, and in some subgroups (type 2 diabetes mellitus, elderly patients) even exceeding, that of stable exertional angina. This review systematizes current knowledge of the pathophysiological mechanisms (autonomic neuropathy, afferent nociceptive system dysfunction, endogenous opioid modulation), diagnostic strategies (stress imaging, gadolinium-enhanced MRI, PET/CT with assessment of coronary flow reserve), and the evolution of indications for surgical revascularization (CABG, PCI) in light of the latest ESC 2024 guidelines. On chronic coronary syndromes. Particular attention is given to the issue of ‘silent’ graft occlusion after CABG (prevalence 8.5%), as well as to the controversial aspects of screening and treatment in patients with ischemia due to non-obstructive coronary artery disease (INOCA). An algorithm for risk stratification and treatment strategy selection based on the concept of atherosclerotic burden and assessment of myocardial viability is proposed.*

Keywords: *silent myocardial ischemia, painless ischemia, coronary artery bypass grafting, percutaneous coronary intervention, chronic coronary syndrome,*

ESC 2024 guidelines, atherosclerotic burden, coronary calcium index, graft occlusion, ischemic cardiomyopathy, INOCA, myocardial viability.

List of abbreviations:

AMI — silent myocardial ischemia

CAD — coronary artery disease

CABG — coronary artery bypass grafting

LV — left ventricle

MRI — magnetic resonance imaging

OMT — optimal medical therapy

PET/CT — positron emission tomography / computed tomography

CVD — cardiovascular diseases

EF — ejection fraction

CCS — chronic coronary syndrome

PCI — percutaneous coronary intervention

INOCA — ischemia with no obstructive coronary artery disease

CAC — coronary artery calcium

FFR — fractional flow reserve

1. Introduction

Coronary artery disease (CAD) remains the leading cause of mortality and disability in populations of industrialized countries. Traditionally, the clinical presentation of CAD is associated with angina pectoris — a pain syndrome that arises from a mismatch between the myocardium's oxygen demand and its supply via the coronary arteries. However, as early as the 1980s, P. Cohn et al. convincingly demonstrated that a significant portion of ischemic episodes recorded during Holter ECG monitoring and exercise tests are asymptomatic [1].

The relevance of the problem of silent myocardial ischemia is determined by the following facts:

1. High prevalence: According to the Framingham Study, up to 25-30% of myocardial infarctions are diagnosed retrospectively (based on ECG data) and occur in an asymptomatic or minimally symptomatic form [2]. Among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, the prevalence of AMI reaches 35-60% [3].

2. Adverse prognosis: Prospective studies demonstrate that the risk of cardiovascular death and non-fatal MI in patients with documented AMI is 3 to 5 times higher than in individuals without ischemia and is comparable to the risk in symptomatic patients [4]. In 70% of individuals who survived sudden cardiac death, episodes of silent ischemia preceded, as detected by Holter monitoring [5].

3. The complexity of risk stratification lies in the absence of a 'warning signal' such as pain, which deprives both patient and physician of an important clinical landmark, resulting in late diagnosis and underestimation of disease severity.

The aim of this review is to present a contemporary perspective on the pathophysiology, diagnosis, and, above all, surgical approaches to the treatment of silent myocardial ischemia, based on an analysis of recent clinical studies and recommendations.

2. Pathophysiology of silent ischemia: current concepts

The classic ischemic cascade develops sequentially: perfusion defect → metabolic disturbances → diastolic dysfunction → systolic dysfunction → ECG changes → angina pectoris.

Pain syndrome is the latest and optional component of this cascade. The mechanisms that ‘switch off’ pain are diverse.

2.1. Afferent neuropathy and diabetic involvement

The most studied mechanism is diabetic autonomic neuropathy. In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), the following are observed:

- Axonal degeneration of thin unmyelinated C fibers and lightly myelinated A δ fibers conducting pain impulses from the myocardium.
- Decreased expression of nerve growth factor (NGF) in the myocardium, which impairs the trophic support of sensory neurons [6].
- Demyelination with a slowing of impulse conduction velocity.

2.2. Endogenous opioid modulation

In response to ischemic stress in the myocardium and central nervous system, production of endogenous opioids (β -endorphins, enkephalins) increases. It has been established that patients with AMI have higher baseline plasma levels of β -endorphins, and their increase in response to exertion is more pronounced than in patients with angina pectoris [7]. These peptides, by binding to μ - and κ -opioid receptors, inhibit activation of nociceptive neurons at the dorsal horns of the spinal cord.

2.3. Central Mechanisms

Functional brain MRI has revealed differences in the activation of cortical structures in patients with AMI. They show:

- Hypoactivation of the insular cortex (the primary projection area of visceral sensitivity) and the anterior cingulate cortex (the emotional-affective component of pain) [8].
- Enhanced descending inhibitory influences from the periaqueductal gray matter and the rostral ventromedial region of the medulla oblongata.

2.4. Hemodynamic Features

It has been demonstrated that episodes of AMI more frequently occur at lower heart rates and arterial blood pressure levels than angina attacks. This suggests that the ischemic threshold (the minimal level of exertion triggering ischemia) in patients with AMI may be lower, and the duration of ischemic episodes longer [9].

3. Evolution of Concepts: from Stenosis to Atherosclerotic Burden

The publication of the 2024 ESC guidelines on chronic coronary syndromes (CCS) marked a paradigm shift [10]. The static concept of ‘stable angina’ has been replaced by a dynamic concept of CAD, encompassing various clinical scenarios.

Key changes:

1. Asymptomatic patients with pathological tests are now categorized under a separate clinical scenario of CAD. This implies that the presence of ischemia (even in the absence of symptoms) classifies the patient as requiring active surveillance and treatment.

2. The concept of atherosclerotic burden. Studies have demonstrated that the risk of events correlates not so much with the degree of stenosis, but rather with the total volume of atherosclerotic plaque.

3. Definition of the category ‘widespread subclinical atherosclerosis.’ Asymptomatic individuals with a coronary artery calcium (CAC) score >300 (or above the 75th percentile for age and sex) possess cardiovascular risk equivalent to that of patients with documented CAD [11]. Thus, the boundary between ‘primary’ and ‘secondary’ prevention becomes indistinct.

4. Diagnostic Strategy for Silent Ischemia

Detection of AMI requires active vigilance. Screening is not recommended for the general population but is indicated in high-risk groups (Table 1).

Table 1. Risk Groups for AMI Screening (adapted from [10,12])

Risk Category	Screening Recommendation	Preferred Method
Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus + >40 years + presence of ≥ 2 FR	Recommended (Class I, Level B)	Stress Echocardiography / Perfusion Scintigraphy
Peripheral atherosclerosis	Recommended (Class I, Level B)	CT angiography of the coronary arteries
CKD (GFR <60 ml/min)	May be considered (Class IIb)	Stress MRI
High CAC (>300) according to CT data	May be considered (Class IIb)	Functional test (PET/CT with assessment of MCR)

Note: FR — risk factors, CKD — chronic kidney disease, GFR — glomerular filtration rate, MCR — myocardial coronary reserve.

4.1. The role of modern imaging methods

· PET/CT with rubidium-82 or ammonia-N13: allows quantitative assessment of myocardial blood flow (MBF) and coronary flow reserve (CFR). A reduction in

CFR below 2.0 is an independent predictor of mortality and a marker of diffuse microcirculatory damage [13].

- Cardiac MRI with pharmacological stress (adenosine/regadenoson) enables assessment of first-pass perfusion and detection of scarred areas (late gadolinium enhancement), which is critically important for decision-making regarding revascularization.

- CT angiography with FFR_{ct} assessment allows noninvasive evaluation of the hemodynamic significance of stenoses. In AMI, the presence of FFR_{ct} ≤0.80 combined with a large ischemic area may serve as an indication for revascularization [14].

5. Surgical treatment: indications, evidence base, and contemporary challenges

The decision to perform myocardial revascularization in an asymptomatic patient is made not to alleviate symptoms but solely to improve prognosis. This places particular responsibility on the heart team.

5.1. Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting (CABG)

CABG remains the “gold standard” for anatomically complex lesions, providing more complete and durable revascularization.

Indications for CABG in AMI (according to ESC 2024) [10]:

- Left main coronary artery (LCA) disease with stenosis >50%: CABG is recommended to improve survival (I A) and is preferred over PCI to reduce the risk of spontaneous MI and repeat revascularizations (I A). With a low SYNTAX score (≤22), PCI is an acceptable alternative (I A).

- Proximal LAD lesion combined with multivessel disease: CABG is recommended to improve survival (Class I, Level A), especially in cases of complex anatomy (SYNTAX score >22).

- Three-vessel disease: CABG is recommended (Class I, Level A) to reduce long-term cardiovascular mortality and the risk of spontaneous MI. This differs from the AHA/ACC recommendations, which will be discussed below.

- LV dysfunction (EF ≤35%): CABG is recommended (Class I, Level B) in the presence of viable myocardium and multivessel disease.

Key study: A meta-analysis of 11 randomized trials including 11,518 patients demonstrated that in patients with multivessel disease, CABG significantly reduces the risk of all-cause mortality (OR 0.84; 95% CI 0.73-0.97) and the risk of myocardial infarction (OR 0.69; 95% CI 0.55-0.86) compared to PCI, with the benefit increasing after 5 years of follow-up [15]. These data formed the basis of the European guidelines.

5.2. Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI)

PCI in asymptomatic patients is indicated only in anatomical scenarios where its long-term outcomes are comparable to CABG, and procedural risk is minimal.

Indications for PCI in AMI:

- Isolated left main coronary artery (LCA) disease with a low SYNTAX score (≤ 22) (IA).
- Isolated proximal left anterior descending artery (LAD) lesion (IA).
- Two-vessel disease without involvement of the proximal LAD, provided complete anatomical revascularization is expected.

Important: Performing PCI in an asymptomatic patient with incomplete revascularization does not improve prognosis and is not recommended [10].

5.3. Discussion: ESC 2024 vs. AHA/ACC

There is a notable discrepancy between European and American guidelines regarding the management of stable (including asymptomatic) patients with multivessel disease.

- ESC 2024: CABG remains class I A, based on observational studies and meta-analyses demonstrating the long-term benefit of CABG in reducing spontaneous MI.
- AHA/ACC 2021: downgraded the recommendation class for CABG to IIa (moderate LV dysfunction) and IIb (normal EF), based on the results of the ISCHEMIA trial, which did not show an advantage of an invasive strategy over OMT in reducing mortality [16].

Comment: It is important to note that the ISCHEMIA trial predominantly included patients with moderate ischemia without left main coronary artery (LCA) disease. Extrapolation of its results to all patients with AMI is inappropriate. The decision should be made individually, taking into account anatomy (SYNTAX score), comorbidities, surgical risk, and patient preferences.

6. A special cohort: patients with LV dysfunction (ischemic cardiomyopathy).

Patients with an LV EF $\leq 35\%$ and AMI pose the greatest challenge. Key question: do they have viable myocardium ('hibernating' or 'stunned') that will 'awaken' after revascularization?

The role of viability testing:

- The STICH study (Surgical Treatment for Ischemic Heart Failure) did not confirm the initial hypothesis that the presence of viable myocardium predicts benefit from CABG [17].

· However, post-hoc analyses and subsequent meta-analyses demonstrate that in patients with an extensive area of viable myocardium ($>10\%$ of LV mass), revascularization is associated with improved prognosis and an increase in EF [18].

· Current approach: The presence of viability is not a mandatory criterion for referral to CABG but assists in identifying patients who will obtain the greatest improvements in functional status and, likely, survival. Selection methods: dobutamine stress echocardiography, MRI with late gadolinium enhancement, PET with ^{18}F -FDG.

7. New issue: 'silent' occlusion of grafts following CABG.

For a long time, early occlusion of grafts (venous and mammary-coronary) was considered to manifest clinically (perioperative MI, unstable hemodynamics). However, the prospective study by Salikhanov I. et al. (2025) refuted this concept [19].

7.1. Study Design and Results

The study included 292 consecutive patients who underwent isolated CABG. All patients underwent CT angiography of the grafts prior to discharge (median 7 days), regardless of clinical status.

Results:

- Frequency: Early 'silent' occlusion was identified in 25 patients (8.5%).
- Localization: Venous grafts were occluded more frequently (92%) than mammary grafts (8%).
- Risk factors: An independent predictor was the duration of surgery >240 minutes (OR 3.2; $p=0.02$). Neither troponin level nor ECG changes reliably predicted occlusion.
- Prognosis: During 14.5 months of follow-up, patients with graft occlusion exhibited an 8.5-fold increased risk of recurrent hospitalization for cardiovascular causes (95% CI 3.2-22.6) and a 15.1-fold increased risk of repeat revascularization (95% CI 4.9-46.7) [19].

7.2. Clinical consequences

1. The need for routine imaging: This study raises the question of the appropriateness of routine CT angiography of all grafts prior to discharge to detect silent occlusions.
2. Management upon detection: When an occlusion is identified after 3 months, PET/CT is indicated to evaluate myocardial viability in the territory supplied by the occluded graft. In cases of extensive ischemia, repeat revascularization may be considered (PCI of the native artery or repeat CABG).

8. Special issue: ischemia with non-obstructive coronary artery disease (INOCA)

Up to 40-50% of patients referred for coronary angiography due to ischemia have no obstructive stenoses ($\geq 50\%$) [20]. INOCA is a heterogeneous condition that includes:

- Microvascular angina (microcirculatory dysfunction).
- Vasospastic angina (Prinzmetal's angina).
- Mixed forms.

8.1. Diagnosis

The gold standard is invasive physiological testing with acetylcholine/adenosine (assessment of coronary flow reserve, index of microvascular resistance, and spasm provocation test).

8.2. Treatment

Surgical methods in INOCA play a minimal role.

- Pharmacotherapy: statins, ACE inhibitors, beta-blockers, calcium channel blockers (for spasm), nicorandil.
- Experimental approaches: transmyocardial laser revascularization (TMLR), spinal neurostimulation — efficacy not demonstrated in large RCTs and not recommended for widespread use.

9. Integrative algorithm for the management of patients with AMI

The proposed algorithm is based on the synthesis of current guidelines.

Stage 1. Confirmation of ischemia and risk stratification.

In an asymptomatic patient from a risk group, a functional test is performed (stress echocardiography, MRI, PET). Upon identification of an ischemic area, its volume is assessed (% of LV mass). Ischemia >10% is considered hemodynamically significant [21].

Stage 2. Invasive coronary angiography or CT angiography.

Assessment of coronary anatomy (presence of LCA trunk lesion, proximal LAD involvement, SYNTAX score).

Stage 3. Heart Team Decision Making.

- **High anatomical risk (LCA trunk, SYNTAX >22, three-vessel disease + diabetes):** CABG (I A). The patient is referred for surgery.
- **Intermediate risk (Two-vessel disease with proximal LAD, SYNTAX ≤22):** Discussion of CABG versus PCI. Priority — complete revascularization. Consider SYNTAX score, STS risk, and comorbidities.
- **Low risk (One- or two-vessel disease without proximal LAD, ischemia <10%):** Return to OMT. Revascularization is not routinely indicated. Ischemia monitoring at 1-2 years.

Stage 4. Postoperative monitoring.

After CABG — consider CT angiography before discharge. After PCI — dual antiplatelet therapy for at least 6 months.

10. Conclusion and prospects.

Surgical treatment of silent myocardial ischemia is currently undergoing a phase of reassessment. The abandonment of the simplified ‘symptom = disease’ model in favor of an integral risk assessment (atherosclerotic burden, coronary reserve, myocardial viability) enables a more precise determination of candidates for revascularization.

Key conclusions:

1. Silent ischemia is not a benign condition but a marker of high risk that necessitates active diagnosis and treatment.

2. Coronary artery bypass grafting maintains a leading role in multivessel disease and LCA trunk lesions in asymptomatic patients with the aim of improving prognosis.

3. The ESC 2024 recommendations advocate a more aggressive strategy for CABG compared to American guidelines, necessitating alignment of perspectives.

4. The problem of 'silent' graft occlusion raises the issue of the necessity for postoperative screening to prevent long-term complications.

5. INOCA remains a 'gray zone' where the role of surgery is minimal, and priority is given to pharmacotherapy.

Promising directions:

- Implementation of hybrid revascularization (mammary graft on the LAD + PCI to other territories).

- Utilization of artificial intelligence for analysis of CT angiograms and PET images to automatically identify high-risk patients.

- Investigation of the role of new anticoagulants and antiplatelet agents in patients with silent ischemia following revascularization.

- Development of minimally invasive direct myocardial revascularization techniques (MIDCAB, robot-assisted surgeries) to reduce surgical risk in asymptomatic patients with severe comorbidities.

References

1. Cohn PF, Fox KM, Daly C. Silent myocardial ischemia. *Circulation*. 2003;108(10):1263-1277.

2. Kannel WB, Abbott RD. Incidence and prognosis of unrecognized myocardial infarction. An update on the Framingham study. *N Engl J Med*. 1984;311(18):1144-1147.

3. Wackers FJ, Young LH, Inzucchi SE, et al. Detection of silent myocardial ischemia in asymptomatic diabetic subjects: the DIAD study. *Diabetes Care*. 2004;27(8):1954-1961.

4. Conti CR, Bavry AA, Petersen JW. Silent ischemia: clinical relevance. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2012;59(5):435-441.

5. Whitfield J, Mulcahy D. The clinical significance of silent myocardial ischaemia. *Eur Heart J*. 2000;21(17):1388-1395.

6. Ieda M, Kanazawa H, Ieda Y, et al. Nerve growth factor is critical for cardiac sensory innervation and rescues neuropathy in diabetic hearts. *Circulation*. 2006;114(22):2351-2360.

7. Falcone C, Auguadro C, Sconocchia R, et al. Endogenous beta-endorphin and silent myocardial ischemia. *Cardiologia*. 1993;38(12 Suppl 1):357-361.

8. Rosen SD, Paulesu E, Wise RJ, Camici PG. Central neural mechanisms contributing to the perception of angina pectoris: a positron emission tomography study. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 1997;29(2):396-404.
9. Langer A, Freeman MR, Josse RG, Armstrong PW. Detection of silent myocardial ischemia in diabetes mellitus. *Am J Cardiol.* 1991;67(12):1073-1078.
10. Vrints C, Andreotti F, Koskinas KC, et al. 2024 ESC Guidelines for the management of chronic coronary syndromes. *Eur Heart J.* 2024;45(35):3415-3537.
11. Blaha MJ, Cainzos-Achirica M, Greenland P, et al. Role of Coronary Artery Calcium Score of Zero and Other Negative Risk Markers for Cardiovascular Disease: The Multi-Ethnic Study of Atherosclerosis (MESA). *Circulation.* 2016;133(9):849-858.
12. Cosentino F, Grant PJ, Aboyans V, et al. 2019 ESC Guidelines on diabetes, pre-diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases. *Eur Heart J.* 2020;41(2):255-323.
13. Murthy VL, Naya M, Foster CR, et al. Improved cardiac risk assessment with noninvasive measures of coronary flow reserve. *Circulation.* 2011;124(20):2215-2224.
14. Nørgaard BL, Leipsic J, Gaur S, et al. Diagnostic performance of noninvasive fractional flow reserve derived from coronary computed tomography angiography in suspected coronary artery disease: the NXT trial. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2014;63(12):1145-1155.
15. Head SJ, Milojevic M, Daemen J, et al. Mortality after coronary artery bypass grafting versus percutaneous coronary intervention with stenting for coronary artery disease: a pooled analysis of individual patient data. *Lancet.* 2018;391(10124):939-948.
16. Maron DJ, Hochman JS, Reynolds HR, et al. Initial Invasive or Conservative Strategy for Stable Coronary Disease. *N Engl J Med.* 2020;382(15):1395-1407.
17. Bonow RO, Maurer G, Lee KL, et al. Myocardial viability and survival in ischemic left ventricular dysfunction. *N Engl J Med.* 2011;364(17):1617-1625.
18. Ling LF, Marwick TH, Flores DR, et al. Identification of therapeutic benefit from revascularization in patients with left ventricular systolic dysfunction and inducible ischemia. *Circ Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2013;6(3):363-372.
19. Salikhanov I, et al. Survival, adverse events and management of silent in-hospital coronary bypass graft occlusion. *Open Heart.* 2025;12(2): e003368.
20. Kunadian V, Chieffo A, Camici PG, et al. An EAPCI Expert Consensus Document on Ischaemia with Non-Obstructive Coronary Arteries in Collaboration with European Society of Cardiology Working Group on Coronary Pathophysiology & Microcirculation. *Eur Heart J.* 2020;41(37):3504-3520.
21. Shaw LJ, Berman DS, Maron DJ, et al. Optimal medical therapy with or without percutaneous coronary intervention to reduce ischemic burden: results from the COURAGE trial nuclear substudy. *Circulation.* 2008;117(10):1283-1291.

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**CHARACTERISTICS AND PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS,
ANALYSIS OF QUALITY OF LIFE AFTER SIMULTANEOUS
OPERATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH OBESITY, COMBINED INTRA-
ABDOMINAL DISEASES AND ABDOMINAL DEFORMITIES**

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to investigate complications and the characteristics of quality of life in patients with obesity following simultaneous and combined surgical interventions on the anterior abdominal wall and abdominal cavity, as well as to develop a systematic methodological approach and implement new technologies in the treatment of this patient population.

Methods and materials. *The study included 739 patients who were treated at the State Budgetary Institution of the Rostov Region 'Regional Clinical Hospital' and the State Budgetary Institution of the Rostov Region 'City Clinical Hospital of Emergency Medical Care' in Ryazan from 1998 to 2024. Among them, 615 (83.22%) were women and 124 (16.78%) were men presenting with various forms of anterior abdominal wall deformities. The mean age of the patients was 36.8±8.6 years.*

All subjects were divided into two groups. The main group comprised 117 individuals (15.83%) who underwent surgery during the period from 2019 to 2022, with a differentiated approach to MAC correction and the use of measures to prevent ischemic complications. The comparison group included 622 patients (84.17%) who underwent surgery between 1998 and 2018, without a differentiated approach to MAC correction and without measures for prevention of ischemic complications, as well as patients in the main group who underwent surgery from 2009 to 2013.

In each group, five patient subgroups were identified based on the type of deformity of the anterior abdominal wall (PBS). Comparison of results between groups was performed using correlation analysis.

Results. *Early postoperative complications are typically associated with ischemic disorders in the skin during PBS reconstruction. Late complaints are predominantly related to the aesthetics of the abdominal contour, as well as hernia recurrence and the development of other hernia types. Unsatisfactory outcomes are more commonly observed in patients who underwent mini-abdominoplasty or the classic procedure with transposition of the navel. Comprehensive preventive measures and consideration of the type of PBS deformity allowed reduction of complication risks at various stages, accelerated recovery of respiratory function, and normalization of intra-abdominal pressure, significantly improving patients' quality of life in the early postoperative period.*

Conclusion. *The success of abdominal wall reconstruction and improvement in patients' quality of life depend on a differentiated approach to surgical treatment, identification of risk groups, and implementation of preventive measures.*

Keywords: *simultaneous reconstruction, combined reconstruction, abdominal wall pathology, reconstructive lipoabdominoplasty, postoperative period, postoperative complications, quality of life.*

Introduction. Over the past 10 years, there has been an increase in diseases of the abdominal organs, including combined conditions associated with anterior abdominal wall pathology. According to some data, deformation of the PBS occurs in 10-13% of cases [5, 8], with a progressive tendency to increase in patients with obesity.

Deformity of the anterior abdominal wall represents a discrepancy between the abdominal shape and its actual condition, manifesting as skin laxity, diastasis of the rectus abdominis muscles, scar changes following surgical interventions, and the development of various forms of hernias. As a rule, this condition is of a combined nature [11].

Normally, changes in the shape of the PBS occur due to age-related and physiological characteristics. In pathological deformity, the most significant etiological factors are metabolic disorders (obesity), increased intra-abdominal pressure, pregnancy and childbirth, abdominal wall trauma, and surgical interventions. Risk factors include comorbidities affecting the hormonal, digestive, cardiovascular, respiratory, and even genitourinary systems [10]. It can be stated that PBS deformity is not only an aesthetic issue but also poses a risk to the patient's health and life.

Currently, the most informative diagnostic methods for this pathology are visual examination, ultrasound, and Doppler studies, which allow determination of the deformity type and the condition of local areas, ultimately assisting in the selection of surgical interventions with minimal postoperative complications.

At present, the combined pathology of PBS and the abdominal cavity, as well as non-neoplastic pelvic diseases, is one of the poorly studied problems in surgery

and attracts increased interest from researchers and practicing clinicians. Simultaneous and combined operations are being used increasingly frequently. According to WHO data, 21-32% of patients indicated for surgical treatment are diagnosed with multiple surgical diseases; however, simultaneous surgical interventions (SSIs) are performed in only 1.5-7% of patients [2, 9]. This is explained by incomplete patient examination prior to surgery, insufficient exploration of abdominal organs during surgery, overestimation of operative risk, surgeon responsibility in case of a possible poor surgical outcome, and the psychological unpreparedness of surgeons and anesthesiologists to expand the scope of the operation.

In practice, combined surgical interventions are performed more frequently (up to 15%) [3, 7]. An advantage is the implementation of more thorough preoperative diagnostics and preparation, as well as performing operations of small and medium, or medium and medium scope, which reduces the risk of postoperative complications.

Despite this, surgical treatment of anterior abdominal wall deformities is associated with a relatively high risk of postoperative complications in both the early and late postoperative periods, especially when performing simultaneous operations.

Among the most common complications in the early postoperative period are prolonged sedation, hypercapnia, and pain [12]; bleeding and hemorrhages into the subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT); necrosis of the skin-fat flap (SFF); Seroma and others [1, 10]. Late postoperative complications include ventral hernias of various localizations and adhesive disease; pathological scarring and abscesses; suppuration of the postoperative wound; as well as dissatisfaction with the final result (shape of the abdomen, subcutaneous adipose tissue, symmetry of areas of the anterior abdominal wall, location of the navel, and others) [4, 6, 8].

It should be noted that at the current stage of surgical development, issues regarding the correction of possible postoperative complications due to extended operative time and surgical trauma, in the context of the planned volume of surgical intervention, remain insufficiently studied. Improving the quality of life of patients after abdominal wall reconstruction is one of the priority tasks.

The aim of the study is to investigate complications and quality of life characteristics in patients following simultaneous and combined surgical interventions, and to enhance it through prevention and correction of complications in the early and late postoperative periods.

Methods and materials of the study. The study included 739 patients who were treated at the State Budgetary Institution of the Rostov Region 'Regional Clinical Hospital' and the State Budgetary Institution of the Rostov Region 'City Clinical Hospital of Emergency Medical Care' in the city. Ryazan from 1998 to 2024. Among them, 615 (83.22%) were women and 124 (16.78%) were men presenting with various forms of anterior abdominal wall deformities. The mean age of the patients was 36.8 ± 8.6 years.

All subjects were divided into two groups. The main group comprised 117 individuals (15.83%) who underwent surgery during the period from 2019 to 2022, with a differentiated approach to MAC correction and the use of measures to prevent ischemic complications. The comparison group included 622 patients (84.17%) who underwent surgery between 1998 and 2018, without a differentiated approach to MAC correction and without measures for prevention of ischemic complications, as well as patients in the main group who underwent surgery from 2009 to 2013.

In each group, five patient subgroups were identified depending on the type of anterior abdominal wall (AAW) deformity (PBS): subgroup 1 (type 1) — 101 patients without signs of impaired AAW MAC, without excess subcutaneous adipose tissue, presenting minor AAW deformity due to deforming scars and/or dermal dystrophy; subgroup 2 (type 2) — 84 patients without signs of impaired AAW MAC, with excess adipose tissue predominantly in the mesogastrium and hypogastrium, exhibiting slight abdominal ptosis with or without skin 'stretch marks' in the lower regions; subgroup 3 (type 3) — 222 patients with isolated diastasis, subdivided into three subgroups according to the level of rectus abdominis muscle (RAM) diastasis; subgroup 4 (type 4) — 76 patients with RAM diastasis and relaxation of the lateral abdominal muscles, without excess subcutaneous adipose tissue or with minor excess in all regions; subgroup 5 (type 5) — 139 patients with morbid obesity (two subgroups depending on RAM diastasis and relaxation of the lateral abdominal muscles).

All patients underwent visual examination and palpation assessment of the PBS. In the main group, computed tomography and pathomorphological examination were also performed to clarify the condition of local tissues and characteristics of blood supply.

Surgical intervention in the main group was performed considering the type of PBS deformity (type 1 — mini-abdominoplasty; type 2 — liposuction alone or combined with mini- or classical abdominoplasty; type 3 — endoscopic abdominoplasty; type 4 — abdominoplasty with MAC correction; type 5 — abdominoplasty supplemented by liposuction and MAC correction). In the comparison group, regardless of the deformity type, mini-abdominoplasty and classical abdominoplasty were predominantly performed, supplemented with liposuction when necessary.

A risk group was also identified (subcutaneous adipose tissue thickness greater than 5 cm, expected operation duration exceeding 3.5 hours, and prior abdominal interventions via midline abdominal access, with impaired inflows from the contralateral side), for whom prophylaxis of ischemic complications was implemented during the intraoperative and early postoperative periods.

Among diseases of the abdominal cavity and pelvis, interventions on the hepatobiliary system predominated (685 patients, 92.7%). Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed in 612 patients, and laparoscopic cholecystectomy with

choledocholithotomy in 73. Areflex interventions were performed in 176 patients; resection of liver cysts, spleen, and abdominal cavity in 38.

Simultaneous operations on pelvic organs were performed in 234 women. A total of 138 cystectomies, 45 myomectomies, 12 tubectomies, and 34 adnexectomies were performed. Supracervical hysterectomy was performed in 54 patients, and excision in 12.

The number of simultaneous stages ranged from one to three.

The assessment of postoperative complications was conducted through daily clinical observation. Statistical data processing was performed using Statistica 10 software.

Research results and their discussion. In the main group, surgical intervention was performed depending on the type of deformity of the anterior abdominal wall.

Early postoperative complications in this group were practically absent. Complications more frequently developed in patients with type 5 deformity of the PBS, who underwent abdominoplasty supplemented with liposuction and MAC correction. Among them, transient ischemia of subcutaneous fat, ischemia of the navel, and subcutaneous fat necrosis occurred equally (1.7% in the overall structure). The greatest number of cases of transient ischemia of subcutaneous fat was identified in patients with type 3 deformity who underwent endoscopic abdominoplasty. It was also found that seroma developed with equal frequency across most patient groups (1.7% in the overall structure) (Table 1).

Table 1 — Frequency of early postoperative complications in the main group

Complication	Type of PBS deformity				
	1 (n=16)	2 (n=31)	3 (n=44)	4 (n=14)	5 (n=22)
Transient ischemia of subcutaneous fat	-	-	4	-	2
Transient ischemia of the navel	-	-	-	-	2
Seroma	-	2	-	2	2
Subcutaneous fat necrosis	-	-	1	-	2
Necrosis of the navel	-	-	-	-	1
No complications	16	19	39	12	13

The comparison group exhibited a greater variety and frequency of early postoperative complications. In patients with type 3 PBS deformity, all listed types of complications were diagnosed, with transient ischemia of subcutaneous fat being the most frequent (6.9% of the total), followed by necrosis of the navel (5.5% of the total), including across the entire group. Patients in the 5th subgroup also frequently experienced complications, among which subcutaneous fat necrosis (5.1%) and necrosis of the navel (4.8%) occurred more often. It is noteworthy that no complications were identified in patients with type 1 deformity (Table 2).

Table 2 — Frequency of early postoperative complications in the comparison group

Complication	Type of PBS deformity				
	1 (n=101)	2 (n=84)	3 (n=214)	4 (n=76)	5 (n=139)
Hematoma	-	-	1	8	-
Transient ischemia of subcutaneous fat	-	16	43	9	14
Transient ischemia of the navel	-	1	22	-	7
Seroma	-	5	17	17	9
Subcutaneous fat necrosis	-	1	24	-	32
Necrosis of the navel	-	-	34	-	30
No complications	101	61	92	42	47

In the late postoperative period, complications were observed in both groups, primarily associated with the aesthetic results of the surgery.

Thus, in the main group, patients with types 3 and 5 deformities of the PBS exhibited all the complications listed below. The most common complications were unevenness of subcutaneous adipose tissue (9.4%) and dissatisfaction with the shape and location of the navel (6.8% of the total). At the same time, patients with types 1 and 4 deformities had virtually no late postoperative complications or none at all (Table 3).

Table 3 — Frequency of complications during the late postoperative period in the main group

Complication	Type of PBS deformity				
	1 (n=16)	2 (n=31)	3 (n=44)	4 (n=14)	5 (n=22)
Asymmetry areas of PBS	-	2	2	1	5
Unevenness of subcutaneous adipose tissue	-	-	5	-	6
Unsatisfactory postoperative scars	-	-	2	-	3
Unsatisfactory shape and location of the navel	-	2	5	-	3
No complications	16	27	30	13	5

A high frequency of late postoperative complications was observed in the comparison group. Patients with type 5 deformity were the most susceptible. Asymmetry of the areas of PBS was diagnosed in all subgroups (15.1%). The largest proportion of patients had an unsatisfactory shape of the abdomen and waist contours due to MAC-22.2% (Table 4).

Table 4 — Frequency of complications in the late postoperative period in the control group.

Complication	Type of PBS deformity				
	1 (n=101)	2 (n=84)	3 (n=214)	4 (n=76)	5 (n=139)
Unsatisfactory abdominal shape and waist contours due to MAC.	-	-	-	76	62
Asymmetry areas of PBS	8	15	24	7	40
Unevenness of subcutaneous adipose tissue	-	-	39	-	57
Unsatisfactory postoperative scars	-	7	38	9	38
Unsatisfactory shape and location of the navel	-	16	49	17	36
No complications	93	46	64	-	-

Thus, we concluded that early postoperative complications were diagnosed in 45.02% of operated patients (n = 280) in the control group, while in the main group only 15.8% of patients (n = 18) were affected. To reduce their incidence in the main group, preventive measures were implemented (skeletization and mobilization of perforating arteries of the PBS, repositioning of the dissected ADS into the donor area, compression of the PBS from day 2, and infusion therapy). Late complications in the control group were observed in 59.32% of patients (n=369), while in the primary group, 21.37% of operated patients (n=25) experienced them. The implemented set of preventive measures reduced the number of complications in the late postoperative period, as statistically confirmed (p<0.01).

An assessment of intra-abdominal pressure and external respiratory function was also conducted before and after surgery, which further affects the quality of life of patients in the primary group with types 3-5 PBS deformities.

It was established that prior to surgery, all patients exhibited elevated intra-abdominal pressure (IAP), including as a result of constant bandage use. In the early postoperative period, intra-abdominal pressure normalized in almost all patients.

Vital capacity (VC) and forced vital capacity (FVC) values were below the normal range in all patients. These indicators normalized already in the early postoperative period. Furthermore, in the late postoperative period, the duration of breath-holding on inspiration and expiration increased.

Correlational relationships were identified between WBD and weight (r=0.94), BMI (r=0.86), and FEV (r = -0.65).

The following intra-abdominal complications were observed during the analysis:

Intra-abdominal hemorrhages occurred during LCCE in one case, and in interventions on pelvic organs in three female patients. These were managed by relaparoscopy, hemorrhage control, sanitation, and drainage of the abdominal cavity. Bile leakage with localized peritonitis was observed in one patient. Corrected by relaparoscopy; the cause was the course of Luschka.

Systemic complications in the form of DVT were observed in 8 patients despite ongoing therapy.

Thus, a detailed analysis of the medical histories of all studied patients demonstrated a correlation between the choice of surgical intervention and patients' quality of life during the early and late postoperative periods.

Conclusions.

1. At present, various techniques are employed to correct abdominal shape and to form waist contours depending on the type of PBS deformity. The absence of a differentiated approach to MAC correction leads to recurrence of PBS deformity in the late postoperative period.

2. In the early postoperative period, ischemic complications most frequently develop, posing a threat to patients' lives. In the late postoperative period, complications are usually associated with the aesthetic aspect, which adversely affects patients' psychological state.

3. To prevent postoperative complications and improve patients' quality of life, the following measures should be implemented:

- expansion of diagnostic measures to clarify tissue condition and specific patient health characteristics;
- identification of risk groups;
- combination of proposed preventive surgical measures with administration of drugs targeting improvement of microcirculation and blood rheology during the early postoperative period;
- differentiated approach to the selection of surgical intervention;
- early patient mobilization.

4. The performance of the simultaneous intra-abdominal stage does not significantly influence the incidence of early postoperative complications.

References

1. Aslanov A. D., Logvina O. E., Kugotov R. M. and others. Tension-free hernioplasty and abdominoplasty in patients with morbid obesity // Moscow Surgical Journal. 2020. Vol. 2. P. 45-53.

2. Gerbali O. Yu., Kosenko A. V. *Simultaneous interventions in patients with complicated forms of postoperative ventral hernias and deformities of the anterior abdominal wall // Kuban Scientific Medical Bulletin. 2019. Vol. 1. T. 26. P. 88-93.*
3. Marinicheva I. G., Manturova N. E., Ganshin I. B., Sidorenkov D. A. *Options for abdominoplasty in patients with a BMI up to 28 kg/m² // Plastic surgery and aesthetic medicine. 2022. Vol. 4. P. 41-48.*
4. Matveev N. L., Makarov S. A., Kupriyanova A. S., Armashiv V. P. *Modern synthetic implants in reconstructive surgery of the abdominal wall // Bulletin of the Medical Institute «REAVIZ». Rehabilitation, Doctor and Health. 2020. Vol. 3. P. 74-84.*
5. Okhunov A. R., Pulatov U. I., Marupov I. O. and others. *Anthropometric changes in various types of deformation of the anterior abdominal wall // Bulletin of Science and Education. 2018. Vol. 9 (45). P. 93-98.*
6. Parshikov V. V. *Inflammatory complications of prosthetic abdominal wall surgery: diagnosis, treatment and prevention (review) // Modern technologies in medicine. 2019. Vol. 3. T. 11. P. 158-178.*
7. Pakhomova R. A., Babajanyan A. M., Kochetova L. V., Fedotov I. A. *Beautiful belly: types of operations, complications // Moscow Surgical Journal. 2021. Vol. 4. P. 65-71.*
8. Timerbulatov M. V., Shornina A. S., Likhter A. S., Kaipov A. E. *Correction of the anterior abdominal wall in patients with ventral hernias of midline localization // Creative Surgery and Oncology. 2022. Vol. 12 (4). P. 301-308.*
9. Terminbulatov M. V., Shornina A. S., Likhter A. S., Kaipov A. E. *Comparative analysis of isolated abdominoplasty and combined hernia-abdominoplasty // Creative Surgery and Oncology. 2023. Vol. 13 (1). P. 39-44.*
10. Folomeeva L. I., Ilchenko F. N. *Features of surgical treatment of abdominoptosis and abdominal wall hernias after bariatric interventions: effectiveness criteria and risk factors // Tauride Medical and Biological Bulletin. 2023. Vol. 1. T. 26. P. 80-89.*
11. Kriener K., Lala R., Homes R. A.P. et al. *Mechanical Characterization of the Human Abdominal Wall Using Uniaxial Tensile Testing // Bioengineering (Basel). 2023. Vol. 10 (10). P. 12-13.*
12. Olmi S., Uccelli M., Oldani G. C. et al. *Laparoscopic Abdominal Wall Hernia Repair // JSLS. 2020. Vol. 24 (1). P. 65-74.*

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ACTIVATION OF GRANULOCYTE MITOCHONDRIA DURING INCUBATION WITH PYRROLOQUINOLINE QUINONE (PQQ): IN VITRO FUNCTIONAL ACTIVITY ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. Pyrroloquinoline quinone (PQQ) is a redox-active compound of the orthoquinone class capable of modulating cellular metabolism through activation of mitochondrial biogenesis and antioxidant protection. Despite the accumulated data on its organ protective effects, the effect of PQQ on the functional activity of granulocytes remains poorly researched.

The purpose of the study. To evaluate the effect of PQQ on the functional activity of neutrophils (namely, protein metabolism, mitochondrial activity, oxidative stress, oxygen metabolism and phagocytosis) in vitro and to substantiate the mechanism of its action as an electron donor for the mitochondrial respiratory chain.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted on venous blood samples from 20 practically healthy donors. The functional activity of neutrophils was assessed by luminescent microscopy using reagents before and after incubation with PQQ (10 microns, 1 hour, 38 °C). PQQ manufactured by MedChemExpress (CAS Number: 72909-34-3)) was used as a research reagent. The NADH level was determined by the intensity of autofluorescence in the UV range. Statistical processing was performed using the Student's paired t-test ($p < 0.05$).

Results. Incubation with PQQ resulted in a statistically significant increase in mitochondrial activity by 147.8% (from 18.4 to 45.6 units, $p < 0.05$) while

maintaining level of protein metabolism. The level of oxidative stress decreased by 36.2% (from 35.4 to 22.6 units, $p < 0.05$). The parameters of oxygen metabolism and phagocytosis did not change significantly. A significant decrease in the NADH pool by 42.9% (from 35.0 to 20.0 conl. units, $p < 0.05$) was revealed against the background of an increase in mitochondrial activity.

Conclusion. *PQQ acts as an effective electron donor for the mitochondrial respiratory chain, presumably at the level of complexes III-IV, which is confirmed by a decrease in the NADH pool while stimulating mitochondrial activity and reducing oxidative stress. The data obtained substantiate the prospects for further study of PQQ as a mitochondrial cytoprotector for the correction of mitochondrial dysfunctions in various immunodeficiency and metabolic conditions.*

Key words: *Pyrrroloquinoline quinone, mitochondria, functional activity of neutrophils, mitochondrial biogenesis, oxidative stress.*

Introduction.

In recent years, pyrroloquinoline quinone (PQQ) has attracted the attention of researchers as a powerful regulator of cellular metabolism. Being a cofactor of bacterial dehydrogenases and an antioxidant, PQQ is able to influence the energy status of mammalian cells through activation of the SIRT1/PGC-1 α signaling pathways, which leads to an increase in the number and functionality of mitochondria [1, 3]. In early studies, it was shown that PQQ can restore nitro blue(NBT) in neutrophils, indicating that its involvement in cellular redox processes [2]. Of particular interest for clinical practice is the effect of PQQ on cells of the immune system, in particular on granulocytes, which critically depend on oxygen explosion and mitochondrial energy in their effector function.

Pyrrroloquinoline quinone (PQQ) is a low-molecular-weight redox-active compound of the orthoquinone class, which was initially identified as a cofactor of bacterial dehydrogenases, but subsequently attracted considerable attention from researchers due to its ability to modulate key physiological processes in mammals [8]. The chemical properties of PQQ are unique and, according to some authors, combine the features of ascorbic acid, riboflavin, and pyridoxal-5-phosphate, which determines its high efficiency in redox cycling reactions [6, 8]. Both the oxidized form of PQQ and its reduced form PQQH₂ are capable of multiple cyclic transformations, which allows this compound to act as a powerful catalyst for electron transfer from various organic substrates to molecular oxygen [4].

In the context of the regulation of cellular metabolism, the ability of PQQ to influence mitochondrial function is central. Numerous studies demonstrate that PQQ stimulates mitochondrial biogenesis through activation of the SIRT1/PGC-1 α signaling pathway, which is considered the main regulator of mitochondrial biogenesis. [1, 3, 8, 9]. The mechanism of this action is an increase in intracellular NAD⁺ levels under

the influence of PQQ, which leads to the activation of NAD⁺-dependent deacetylase SIRT1. Activated SIRT1 deacetylates PGC-1 α , promoting its nuclear translocation and triggering the expression of mitochondrial genes, including nuclear respiratory factor 1 (NRF-1) and mitochondrial transcription factor A (TFAM) [8, 9]. In experiments on NIH/3T3 fibroblasts, it was shown that incubation with PQQ in physiologically significant concentrations leads to an increase in the amount of mitochondrial DNA and an increase in the expression of cytochrome c oxidase (MTCO1) subunit 1, and this effect was blocked by a specific SIRT1 inhibitor EX-527 [9].

The antioxidant properties of PQQ deserve separate consideration, as they are directly related to the protection of mitochondria from oxidative stress. PQQH₂, a reduced form of the compound, is able to effectively neutralize superoxide anion and hydroxyl radicals, and its activity is several times higher than that of ascorbic acid, traditionally considered as a reference water-soluble antioxidant [4, 8]. In addition, PQQH₂ participates in the regeneration of α -tocopherol from α -tocopheroxyl radicals formed during the oxidation of polyunsaturated lipids, thereby enhancing the antioxidant protection of cell membranes [7, 9]. It is important to note that PQQ is able to catalyze continuous redox reactions, and due to this property, picomolar amounts of PQQ can ensure the conversion of micromolar amounts of the substrate, which distinguishes it from many other antioxidant compounds [4].

The question of the PQQ receptor interaction has remained open for a long time, but recent studies have shed light on this problem. The work of Ando and co-authors demonstrated that PQQ selectively activates G-protein-coupled receptor 35 (GPR35), which is expressed in various tissues, including the gastrointestinal tract and adipose tissue [3]. Using TGF α -dropping analysis and photoaffinity labeling, direct binding of PQQ to GPR35 was shown, with the hydrogen bonds of the 2-carboxyl group of PQQ with the amino acid residues Arg100, Tyr101, and Arg151 of the receptor playing a key role in the interaction [3]. This discovery allows us to take a fresh look at the molecular mechanisms of action of PQQ and consider it as a food agonist of a specific receptor.

The anti-inflammatory effects of PQQ are realized through the suppression of pro-inflammatory signaling pathways. It has been shown that PQQ inhibits the activation of the nuclear factor NF- κ B, reducing the expression of proinflammatory cytokines TNF- α , IL-6 and IL-1 β [4, 7]. In a model of lung radiation damage in mice, PQQ effectively suppressed the inflammatory response and apoptosis of epithelial cells, and the protective effect was realized through the MOTS-c-dependent mechanism and was associated with the preservation of mitochondrial function [7]. In addition, PQQ modulates the activity of MAP kinases, including JNK and p38 MAPK, which also contributes to its anti-inflammatory effect [8].

The effect of PQQ on immune cells is of particular interest in the context of the present study. Deficiency of PQQ in the diet of experimental animals leads to

impaired immune response, decreased proliferative activity of lymphocytes, and increased susceptibility to infections [6]. At the same time, the addition of PQQ accelerates the recovery of the leukocyte pool after gamma irradiation and protects the hematopoietic system [4]. Early work by Bishop and co-authors demonstrated the involvement of PQQ in redox processes in guinea pig neutrophils, where PQQ affected the reduction of nitro blue[2]. Modern concepts allow us to consider PQQ as a modulator of the immune system, which suppresses excessive inflammatory activation, but at the same time maintains an adequate level of immune response [4].

The organ protective effects of PQQ have been demonstrated in many studies. In the central nervous system, PQQ protects neurons from glutamate excitotoxicity and oxidative stress through modulation of the Akt/GSK-3 β signaling pathway, which justifies its potential use in neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases [2, 3]. In the heart, PQQ reduces the area of infarction with ischemic reperfusion injury and improves the restoration of myocardial function [4]. In the liver and adipose tissue, PQQ helps to reduce lipid accumulation and improve insulin sensitivity, which makes it a promising tool for correcting metabolic disorders [4, 6]. In the reproductive system, PQQ protects the ovaries from ischemic reperfusion injury, reducing edema and leukocyte infiltration [4].

The regulatory status of PQQ varies from country to country, which is important to consider when planning clinical trials. In the United States, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has not approved PQQ as a medicinal product, but has assigned it GRAS (Generally Recognized As Safe) status, which allows the use of PQQ in food and dietary supplements [4, 5]. In 2009, the first product containing PQQ was approved, and in the following years, several manufacturers, including Howtian with the PureQQ® product, successfully completed the self-approved GRAS procedure [5]. In the European Union, the salt form of PQQ (PQQ-Na) is approved as Novel Food (a new food raw material) with a set consumption limit of up to 20 mg per day for the adult population [4]. In China, PQQ was approved as a new food raw material in 2022 [5]. In Canada, PQQ is allowed in the category of natural health products, and in Japan it is used as an ingredient in functional foods [4, 5]. Thus, PQQ is currently positioned as a nutraceutical with vitamin-like properties, rather than as a classical pharmacological agent, which does not detract from its potential as a therapeutic agent for the correction of mitochondrial dysfunctions [4, 8].

Thus, the range of pathological conditions in which the effectiveness of PQQ is studied is extremely wide and continues to expand. In addition to the already mentioned neurodegenerative and cardiovascular diseases, the role of PQQ in metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease is being actively investigated [4, 6]. Oncological studies have shown that PQQ is able to selectively induce apoptosis of tumor cells, although clinical use in this area is still far away [4]. Of particular interest are studies on the radioprotective

properties of PQQ, demonstrating its ability to protect the hematopoietic system and reduce mortality under radiation [7]. All these data together substantiate the relevance of further study of PQQ, including its effect on the functional activity of granulocytes, which was the subject of this study.

Materials and methods.

The study was performed on the basis of the laboratory of Mitotech LMB (Almaty). The venous blood of 20 practically healthy donors, comparable in age and gender composition, served as the material for the study. Blood sampling was performed in the morning on an empty stomach in vacuum tubes with lithium heparin. The leukocyte suspension was isolated and the subsequent assessment of the functional activity of neutrophils (FAN) was carried out according to the standard laboratory protocol adopted at the institution and described in the relevant methodological recommendations [3].

The study used pyrroloquinoline quinone(PQQ) manufactured by MedChem-Express (CAS Number: 72909-34-3) with a purity of 99.82%. The choice of this reagent is due to its high purity, documented bioactivity, and widespread use in experimental studies, which is confirmed by a number of publications [4, 8]. PQQ is a redox-active cofactor capable of cyclic redox transformations and stimulation of mitochondrial biogenesis through activation of the SIRT1/PGC-1 α signaling pathway, which is described in detail in literature [1, 8, 9].

Blood samples were incubated in two parallel modes: the control mode, where saline was added to the leukocyte suspension, and the experimental mode, where cells were incubated with a PQQ solution at a final concentration of 10 microns. The choice of concentration was based on literature data on physiologically significant doses used in *in vitro* studies [9]. Incubation was carried out for 1 hour at a temperature of 38 °C according to the standard protocol for setting the FAN reaction, which ensures comparability of the results obtained with routine laboratory parameters.

The level of recovered NADH equivalents was assessed indirectly by the intensity of NADH-dependent autofluorescence in the UV range (excitation wavelength 340 nm, emission 460 nm) using a fluorescence microscope equipped with an appropriate filter unit. This approach is based on the ability of the reduced form of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide to fluoresce in UV light, whereas the oxidized form of NAD⁺ does not have fluorescent properties.

Statistical processing of the obtained data was carried out using the Microsoft Excel software package. The arithmetic mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) were calculated for each indicator. The normality of the distribution was checked using the Shapiro-Wilk criterion. The significance of the differences between the control and experimental groups was assessed using a paired Student's t-test. The differences were considered statistically significant at a $p < 0.05$ level.

Results and discussion.

As a result of the experiment, data reflecting the effect of PQQ on key functional parameters of peripheral blood granulocytes were obtained. The dynamics of changes is presented in Table 1, which shows the absolute values of the indicators in the control and experimental groups, as well as percentage changes relative to the control.

Table 1: The effect of PQQ on indicators of functional activity of neutrophils (M ± SD)

Indicator	Control group (units)	Experimental group (PQQ) (units)	% of change	Trend
Protein metabolism	25,3 ± 2,1	24,1 ± 1,9	-4,7%	Stable
Oxidative stress	35,4 ± 3,2	22,6 ± 2,5*	-36,2%	Level decrease
Oxygen metabolism	15,2 ± 1,8	14,8 ± 1,6	-2,6%	Stable
Phagocytosis	28,7 ± 2,5	24,3 ± 2,2	-15,3%	Slight level decrease
Mitochondrial activity	18,4 ± 2,0	45,6 ± 3,5*	+147,8%	Significant level increase
NADH level (conl. units)	35,0 ± 2,8	20,0 ± 1,9*	-42,9%	Pool decrease

** — the differences with the control group are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).*

As seen from the data presented, the addition of PQQ to the incubation medium led to a significant restructuring of the cellular metabolism of granulocytes, which manifested itself in multidirectional changes in the estimated parameters. The most pronounced effect of PQQ was demonstrated in relation to mitochondrial activity, assessed by reagent “M”. This indicator increased almost 2.5 times, increasing from 18.4 to 45.6 units, which was an increase of 147.8% relative to the control ($p < 0.05$). Such a significant increase in the proportion of cells with active mitochondrial conglomerates strongly indicates the stimulation of energy processes under the influence of PQQ. The results obtained are in good agreement with the literature data, according to which PQQ is able to activate mitochondrial biogenesis through the SIRT1/PGC-1 α signaling pathway [1, 8, 9]. It is important to note that the work of Chohanadisai and co-authors also showed an increase in mitochondrial mass and expression of mitochondrial proteins during incubation of cells with PQQ, and the effect was dose-dependent [1].

At the same time, the level of protein metabolism estimated by fluorescent reagent remained within the reference values (a decrease of only 4.7%) and did not

differ statistically significantly from the control. The absence of direct stimulation of plastic processes against the background of pronounced activation of mitochondrial function suggests that in the conditions of the experiment, PQQ acts primarily as an energy substrate or catalyst for energy processes, rather than an anabolic stimulant. Cells seem to redistribute resources in favor of maintaining and enhancing energy metabolism without increasing the intensity of protein synthesis.

An analysis of the oxidative stress indicators assessed by the specific reagent revealed a statistically significant decrease in this parameter from 35.4 to 22.6 units (a decrease of 36.2%, $p < 0.05$). This demonstrates the powerful antioxidant potential of PQQ, which corresponds to the numerous literature data on the ability of PQQ and its reduced form PQQH₂ to effectively neutralize reactive oxygen species, including superoxide anion and hydroxyl radicals [4, 6, 8]. It is known that PQQH₂ is superior in its antioxidant activity to ascorbic acid, traditionally considered as a reference water-soluble antioxidant, and is capable of regenerating alpha-tocopherol in cell membranes [8].

Special attention should be paid to the dynamics of the oxygen metabolism index, which reflects the lysosomal activity and the ability of cells to oxygen-dependent metabolism. This indicator did not change significantly, remaining within the values typical for functional rest (15.2 in the control versus 14.8 in the experiment, a decrease of 2.6%, $p > 0.05$). This fact is important because it indicates that PQQ does not seem to enhance the production of reactive oxygen species through activation of NADPH oxidase, but rather participates in alternative redox processes. This observation is in good agreement with the early work of Bishop and co-authors, who demonstrated the involvement of PQQ in redox processes in neutrophils, but did not observe direct activation of the oxygen explosion [2].

The phagocytic activity index decreased slightly relative to the control (from 28.7 to 24.3 units, a decrease of 15.3%), but this decrease did not reach the level of statistical significance and remained within normal physiological fluctuations. It is possible that *in vitro* PQQ promotes the redistribution of cellular energy to maintain intracellular homeostasis and mitochondrial function, temporarily reducing the readiness of cells for effector function. However, to confirm this assumption, additional studies are required to evaluate phagocytic activity under conditions of antigenic stimulation.

The most intriguing observation seems to be a significant decrease in the level of recovered NADH equivalents in the experimental group. The NADH level decreased from 35.0 to 20.0 conventional units (a decrease of 42.9%, $p < 0.05$) against the background of a simultaneous increase in mitochondrial activity. At first glance, this may seem paradoxical, since NADH is the main electron donor for the respiratory chain, and its decrease is usually associated with inhibition of energy metabolism. However, we believe that the observed phenomenon can be

explained by the unique redox properties of PQQ, which can act as an alternative electron donor for the mitochondrial respiratory chain.

It is known that the standard electron transport route is their transfer from NADH to complex I of the respiratory chain, followed by transfer to coenzyme Q, complex III, cytochrome c, complex IV, and finally to molecular oxygen. The redox potential of PQQ allows it to participate in redox reactions with various components of the respiratory chain. We assume that PQQ can act as a direct electron donor, bypassing complex I and reducing ubiquinone (coenzyme Q) or directly interacting with cytochromes at the level of complexes III and IV. This model explains the decrease in the NADH pool, since when electrons arrive from an alternative donor, the need for NADH oxidation through complex I decreases, and NADH can accumulate in reduced form only until it is consumed for other metabolic needs.

Experimental models using specific respiratory chain blockers can be proposed to test this hypothesis. Thus, when complex III is blocked by antimycin A, the flow of electrons from NADH through complexes I and III is interrupted. However, if PQQ is able to transfer electrons directly to cytochrome c (located between complexes III and IV) or to complex IV (cytochrome c oxidase), the work of complexes IV and V (ATP synthesis) should be maintained. Oxygen consumption will continue, although NADH will not be consumed at the complex I level. When the IV complex is blocked by cyanide, the final electron acceptor, molecular oxygen, becomes unavailable. However, if PQQ acts as a donor for earlier segments of the chain, the components of the respiratory chain can be restored, and the mitochondrial membrane potential will be maintained for some time due to the operation of complex III, which is able to translocate protons during electron transfer from ubiquinol to cytochrome c, even with cytochrome c oxidase blocked. PQQ, which has the properties of a dioxidant, is able to maintain this compensatory flow of electrons.

Thus, the decrease in NADH levels observed in our experiment against the background of an increase in mitochondrial activity can be explained by the fact that cells partially switch to using PQQ as a more efficient electron donor under these conditions. By “feeding” the respiratory chain at the level of ubiquinone or cytochromes, PQQ reduces the load on complex I, reduces superoxide production (which explains the decrease in the oxidative stress index) and simultaneously maintains a high level of mitochondrial activity and ATP synthesis.

Conclusion.

The study demonstrated that incubation of peripheral blood granulocytes with pyrroloquinoline quinone (PQQ) at a concentration of 10 microns leads to a statistically significant increase in the proportion of cells with high mitochondrial activity by 147.8% ($p < 0.05$) while maintaining normal plastic metabolism. PQQ exhibits pronounced protective properties in relation to oxidative stress, as evidenced by

a 36.2% decrease in the number of damaged cells. The revealed decrease in the NADH pool in cells by 42.9% against the background of an increase in mitochondrial activity suggests that the PQQ molecule is able to act as an alternative electron donor for the III-IV complexes of the mitochondrial respiratory chain, optimizing energy metabolism and reducing the production of reactive oxygen species. The data obtained substantiate the expediency of further studying PQQ as a mitochondrial cytoprotector in clinical practice, and are also in good agreement with the effects of PQQ on blood cells and mitochondrial function previously described in the literature. [1, 2, 4, 8].

References

1. Chowanadisai W, Bauerly KA, Tchapanian E, Wong A, Cortopassi GA, Rucker RB. Pyrroloquinoline quinone stimulates mitochondrial biogenesis through cAMP response element-binding protein phosphorylation and increased PGC-1 α expression. *J Biol Chem.* 2010 Jan 1;285(1):142-52. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M109.030130. Epub 2009 Oct 27. PMID: 19861415; PMCID: PMC2804159.
2. Bishop A, Paz MA, Gallop PM, Karnovsky ML. Methoxatin (PQQ) in guinea-pig neutrophils. *Free Radic Biol Med.* 1994 Oct;17(4):311-20. doi: 10.1016/0891-5849(94)90017-5. PMID: 8001835.
3. Ando H, Kanamori A, Wakabayashi M, Nakashima F, Sei H, Hattori H, Kita M, Inoue A, Murakami A, Akagawa M, Uchida K, Shibata T. Structural and Functional Basis of G Protein-Coupled Receptor 35 Activation by Pyrroloquinoline Quinone. *Biochemistry.* 2025 Dec 16;64(24):4758-4767. doi: 10.1021/acs.biochem.5c00566. Epub 2025 Nov 21. PMID: 41269875.
4. MedChemExpress. Pyrroloquinoline quinone (HY-100196): Product Data Sheet — Access mode: <https://www.medchemexpress.com/Pyrroloquinoline-quinone.html> (date of access: 02/14/2026).
5. Howtian Group. What is new food raw material PQQ? — Access mode: <https://longchangextracts.com/raw-material-pqq/> (date of access: 02/14/2026). Rucker R, Chowanadisai W, Nakano M. Potential physiological importance of pyrroloquinoline quinone. *Altern Med Rev.* 2009 Sep;14(3):268-77. PMID: 19803551.
6. Gao Y, Kamogashira T, Fujimoto C, Iwasaki S, Yamasoba T. Pyrroloquinoline quinone (PQQ) protects mitochondrial function of HEI-OCI cells under premature senescence. *NPJ Aging.* 2022 Apr 19;8(1):3. doi: 10.1038/s41514-022-00083-0. Erratum in: *NPJ Aging.* 2022 Oct 6;8(1):14. doi: 10.1038/s41514-022-00095-w. PMID: 35927260; PMCID: PMC9158787.

7. Jonscher KR, Chowanadisai W, Rucker RB. Pyrroloquinoline-Quinone Is More Than an Antioxidant: A Vitamin-like Accessory Factor Important in Health and Disease Prevention. *Biomolecules*. 2021 Sep 30;11(10):1441. doi: 10.3390/biom11101441. PMID: 34680074; PMCID: PMC8533503.

8. Saihara K, Kamikubo R, Ikemoto K, Uchida K, Akagawa M. Pyrroloquinoline Quinone, a Redox-Active o-Quinone, Stimulates Mitochondrial Biogenesis by Activating the SIRT1/PGC-1 α Signaling Pathway. *Biochemistry*. 2017 Dec 19;56(50):6615-6625. doi: 10.1021/acs.biochem.7b01185. Epub 2017 Dec 6. PMID: 29185343.

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**MORPHOMETRIC, HEMODYNAMIC INDICATORS
OF THE HEART, AND AUTONOMIC HOMEOSTASIS IN HIGHLY
QUALIFIED ATHLETES OF TEAM SPORTS DURING
THE COMPETITIVE PERIOD**

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Abstract. *The article examines adaptive changes in the cardiovascular system of highly qualified handball players in response to various types of loads. Data on morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of the heart in athletes competing in the Russian Championship Super League are studied and analyzed. Attention is focused on anthropometric data in relation to morphometric and hemodynamic parameters, considering the correlation with temporal indicators of heart rate variability. Morphometric and hemodynamic indicators of the heart are examined during different phases of the cardiac cycle. Indicators reflecting the heart's capacity to effectively manage loads of various types resulting from long-term handball training are identified.*

Keywords: *adaptation, transmitral blood flow, myocardial morphometric indicators, hemodynamics, physical load, highly qualified athletes.*

Introduction. Training and competitive processes in team sports encompass loads of diverse nature. Handball is classified as a sport with substantial volumes of speed-strength workload [4]. According to research data [3], the heart volume of team sport athletes is among the largest. This may reflect an adaptive form

of response to physical loads of various types (predominantly speed-strength in nature). Considering fluctuations in maximal oxygen consumption indicators (50-60 ml/kg/min), the VO₂max values of basketball and handball players are at a comparable level [4], which may suggest similarity in the types of competitive loads within the long-term training system. An important aspect in monitoring the competitive readiness of team sport athletes during the competitive period is the assessment of overtraining and excessive fatigue [1]. A recommended method for assessing the functional state of an athlete and for preventing the development of cardiovascular diseases is the evaluation of heart rate variability [12]. We adhere to the position of L. A. Bokeria (2009) that the sensitivity and accuracy of heart rate variability assessment for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases increase when combined with other diagnostic methods (for example, echocardiographic evaluation of ejection fraction in %) [2]. One of the objectives of our study was to evaluate the morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of the athletes' hearts during the competitive period, determining the values of ejection fraction (EF%) and stroke volume (SV, ml) as indicators, the reduction of which, according to V. A. Badtieva (2018), may indicate a state of overstrain and overtraining [1]. Morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of the hearts of highly qualified handball players (n=19) were measured during the competitive period in accordance with the recommendations for the quantitative assessment of cardiac chamber structure and function [13]. The study was conducted during the 2024-2025 season (Table № 1).

Table № 1 — Selected indicators of physical development and myocardial morphometric parameters (Mean ± SE) of highly qualified handball players during the competitive period of the 2024-2025 season.

№	Indicators	Groups of examined athletes	
		EG Autumn 2024 (n=19)	EG Spring 2025 (n=19)
1.	BMI	25,4±2,6	25,6±2,4
2.	Body surface area, m ²	2,27±0,18	2,27±0,17
3.	LVM, g.	202,97±41,72	210,3±34,96
4.	LVMM, g/m ²	89,75±15,77	92,42±12,17
5.	LVOT	0,35±0,03	0,35±0,03
6.	IS	0,65±0,07	0,65±0,067
7.	EF %	64,9±5,6	65,7±5,1
8.	SV ml.	96±21,2	101,9±18,7
9.	HR beats/min at rest	57,9±3,6	56,6±3,7

Note: * indicates a significant difference between measurements (p < 0.05)

According to the data in Table 1, no significant differences in morphometric and hemodynamic parameters were detected during the competitive period in qualified handball players. At the same time, a slight increase in LVM (left ventricular myocardial mass) and LVMM (left ventricular myocardial mass index) was observed, combined with a slight increase in EF% and SV ml. This may indicate a positive aspect of cardiac adaptation to loads during the competitive period, which is fundamentally important for the overall sports outcome. Furthermore, this may have practical significance in differentiating loads throughout the annual training cycle. In our view, the degree of cardiovascular system adaptation to speed-strength oriented loads can serve as an indicator of the reserves in the organism's competitive readiness. Therefore, the issue of combining intensive training and competitive loads with psychological, pedagogical, and other permitted methods of influencing athletes to enhance sports performance appears entirely logical. The presented morphometric indicators of the heart fall within the physiological norm and correspond to the normal type of myocardial geometry [13]. The normative hemodynamic and morphometric indicators of the heart in handball players reflect the response to a harmoniously structured effective training process within the framework of long-term preparation (considering training experience), enabling both high sports performance and preservation of morphological homeostasis of the athlete's heart. The sphericity index (SI) values according to V. S. Alexandrov and A. P. Makhnov (2002) are within the normative range [7].

Hemodynamic parameters of the heart influenced by the vagus nerve, which induces vagotonic remodeling of the rhythm favoring bradycardia, require further investigation of the athlete's cardiac diastolic function, as most metabolic processes in the heart occur during diastole [6,12]. An important aspect, besides the assessment of autonomic rhythm regulation, is the determination of the hemodynamic parameters of athletes' hearts during the competitive period. Therefore, in addition to the morphometric parameters of the heart (data presented in Table 1), we studied the main hemodynamic parameters of diastolic function in athletes of various qualification groups (at rest) who exhibited a heart rate below 60 bpm (bradycardia) or a tendency toward a decreased heart rate approaching bradycardia with HR below 64 bpm [9,10]. To study the hemodynamic parameters of diastolic function, emphasis was placed on the indicators obtained during the competitive period in more highly trained handball players competing in the Russian Championship Super League, with results placing them in the upper ranks of the tournament table. In these athletes, HR was observed to be below 60 bpm at rest. The study of diastolic function was conducted according to the recommendations of Rybakova M. K. (2008). [6,8], where the periods of early and late diastole were determined [9]: IVRT, E/A, DT, ET (mitral), diastasis time. The study results are presented in Table 2. It should be noted that a relevant aspect in the study of diastolic function of the

heart in handball players is the view that the longer the diastolic period, the more efficient the systole [6]. The longer the diastolic period, the longer the isovolumetric relaxation time (IVRT), which promotes more complete actomyosin dissociation, thereby generating greater force of cardiac contractions [6]. Our studies involving highly qualified handball players competing in the top and super leagues of the Russian Handball Championship are consistent with the findings reported in [6]. Thus, during the measurement of morphometric and hemodynamic indices of the heart, the isovolumic relaxation time (IVRT) parameter was also considered. The results of our studies demonstrated that, from a sports perspective, both the isovolumic relaxation time itself and its correlations with other indicators reflecting various aspects of preparedness may have practical significance (figure 1). Thus, a high correlation is observed with the number of steps per minute during aerobic running exercise at an HR of 150-156 bpm (0.82). This is further supported by the Cooper test result in meters covered (0.82). Additionally, a negative correlation of IVRT with the '300 m Run' test result (s) (-0.62) was established. In our view, it can be assumed that a longer IVRT duration at rest positively influences the completion time of the glycolytic 300 m running test (performed at submaximal intensity). It has been established that blood lactate levels after running exercise are also associated with IVRT. Thus, at the 3rd minute of recovery after a 300 m run, the lactate level correlates with IVRT at 0.63. Athletes with a longer IVRT likely possess greater physiological capacity for recovery following glycolytic-type exertion. IVRT exhibits a negative correlation with indicators of major arterial circulation. At a level of -0.69, it is correlated with the magnitude of systolic BP after warm-up prior to the Cooper test. In better-prepared athletes, systolic BP values return to normal quite rapidly after warm-up, even when they are aware of the test to be performed. This confirms our hypothesis regarding the sequence of formation of the heart's work economization function during sports training. It is evident that the longer the IVRT, the better the BP values at rest and, consequently, the outcomes of running tests with both aerobic and anaerobic loads [11].

Figure 1 — Relationships of IVRT with indicators of physical performance, metabolism, and central circulation.

Table 2.— Hemodynamic indicators of the heart in team sport athletes (handball) during the annual competition cycle (Mean ± SE).

№	Indicators	Groups of examined athletes	
		EG autumn 2024 (n=19)	EG Spring 2025 (n=19)
1.	HR, beats/min at rest	57,9±3,6	56,6±3,7
2.	E/A, arbitrary units	2,43±0,51	2,32±0,30
3.	IVRT, ms	88,4±11,3	91,5±9,6
4.	Mitral ET, ms	766,4±149,7	789,3±138,6
7.	DT, ms	147,2±12,1	142,0±11,7
8.	Diastasis, ms	373,8±140,1	422,7±158,2
9.	EF %	64,9±5,6	65,7±5,1
10.	SV ml.	96±21,2	101,9±18,7

Note: * denotes a significant difference from the control group ($p < 0.05$).

In addition to determining transmitral hemodynamic diastolic parameters using pulsed-wave and continuous-wave Doppler echocardiography, we conducted an assessment of time-domain heart rate variability (HRV) parameters (RRNN, ms — mean duration of R-R intervals; SDNN, ms — standard deviation of normal R-R intervals; RMSSD — root mean square of successive differences between adjacent NN intervals; pNN50% — proportion of consecutive R-R intervals differing by 50 ms; TP (ms^2) — total power of the spectrum) [Zamakina]. Correlation analysis of transmitral hemodynamic parameters with time-domain HRV indices revealed that SDNN has a moderate correlation with the ratio of early (E) to late (A) diastolic filling E/A (0.68). This likely reflects a stable heart rate variability indicator, which directly depends on the athlete's level of competitive readiness (athletic form). This explains the higher level of correlation of RMSSD, which shows a strong correlation with the E/A ratio (0.74) and with diastasis duration (0.70). The total power spectral density TP (ms^2) exhibits a strong correlation with the E/A ratio (0.73). Based on the observed correlation relationships, it can be assumed that the autonomic influence of the cardioprotective properties of the vagus nerve during endurance training affects the hemodynamic parameters of remodeling of transmitral diastolic blood flow, favoring diastolic function indicators, as noted in resting HR parameters shown in Table 1 [12].

References

1. Badijeva V. A., Pavlov V. I., Sharykin A. S., Khokhlova M. N., Pachina A. V., Vybornov V. D. Overtraining syndrome as a functional disorder of the cardiovascular system caused by physical exercise // *Russian Cardiological Journal*. — 2018. — 23 (6). — P. 180-190.

2. Bokeria L. A., Bokeria O. L., Volkovskaya I. V. Heart rate variability: methods of measurement, interpretation, and clinical application // *Annals of Arrhythmology*. — 2009 — № 4. — P. 21-32.
3. Vasilyev A. P. "The Athletic Heart" / A. P. Vasilyev, N. N. Streltsova // *Medical Council*. — 2018. — No. 12. — pp. 185-188.
4. Issurin V. B. *Sports Talent: Prognosis and Realization* // LLC Publishing House "Sport". — 2017. — pp. 4-17.
5. Zamakina O. V. Left Ventricular Remodeling Depending on Autonomic Status in Patients After Myocardial Infarction / O. V. Zamakina et al. // *Contemporary Problems of Science and Education*. — 2016. — No. 3. — pp. 46-58.
6. Kovalenko V. N. *Physiology of the Heart (Physiology, Changes in Pathological Conditions)* / V. N. Kovalenko, N. I. Yabluchansky // *Bulletin of Kharkiv National University*. — 2003. — No. 597. — pp. 1-14.
7. Patent No. 2182456 Russian Federation, IPC A61B 5/02. Method for assessing the functional state of the left ventricular myocardium by determining the cardiac muscle dysfunction index: No. 2000104724/14: filed 27.12.2001: published 20.05.2002 / Alexandrov V. S., Makhnov A. P.; Applicant: I. I. Mechnikov Saint Petersburg Medical Academy. — 11 p.
8. Rybakova M. K. *Practical Guide to Ultrasound Diagnostics. Echocardiography* / M. K. Rybakova, M. N. Alekhin, V. V. Mitkov. — Moscow: Vidar Publishing House, 2008. — 512 p.
9. Chernozemova A. V. *Diastolic Function and Myocardial Remodeling in Patients after Coronary Bypass Surgery: Methodological Recommendations* / A. V. Chernozemov, I. A. Khlopina, E. N. Shatsova. — Arkhangelsk: Northern State Medical University (NSMU), 2009. — 32 pp.
10. Sherstiuk S. A. "Supernormal" diastolic function of the left ventricle — a functional indicator of the athlete's heart / S. A. Sherstiuk, A. Yu. Aseeva, V. I. Andreev [et al.] // *Human. Sport. Medicine*. — 2022. — Vol. 22. — No. 1. — pp. 56-62.
11. Sherstiuk S. A. *Adaptive capabilities of the physiologically normal heart of young men to aerobic and anaerobic loading: abstract of ... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Biological Sciences 1.5.5.* — Tomsk, 2022. — 24 pp.
12. Shlyk N. I., Gavrilova E. A. Bradycardia and heart rate variability in athletes // *Human. Sport. Medicine*. — 2023. — Vol. 23, No. S1. — Pp. 59-69
13. Roberto M Lang Recommendations for chamber quantification / Roberto M Lang, Michelle Bierig, Richard B Devereux [et al] // *Eur J Echocardiogr* / — 2006. Vol. 7(2). — P. 79-108. -DOI: 10.1016/j.euje.2005.12.014.

**EATING DISORDERS, PHYSICAL INACTIVITY,
AND WEAKENED IMMUNE FUNCTION AS FACTORS
IN THE NEGATIVE AND DETRIMENTAL IMPACT OF PASSIVE
SMOKING ON THE HEALTH AND PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT
OF SCHOOLCHILDREN, AND WAYS TO CREATE PREVENTIVE
MEASURES TO ELIMINATE
THIS NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASE**

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Abstract. *Key physical parameters: height, weight, and chest circumference. These parameters are measured to identify the physical characteristics of children exposed and unexposed to passive smoking. This is especially important in childhood. The χ^2 correlation coefficient was calculated. To establish a qualitative relationship between the degree of tobacco dependence, i.e., the number of cigarettes smoked per day in tobacco-dependent families, and the number of schoolchildren covered by our study, the study range was used. The aim of our study was to identify social and hygienic aspects of reducing children's exposure to passive smoking and develop preventive measures based on the questionnaire data obtained and the study of children's outpatient records, for the subsequent implementation of programs to radically eliminate this detrimental phenomenon to their health.*

Key words: *Passive smoking, immune system, morbidity, physical activity, noncommunicable diseases, artificial intelligence, body weight*

Tobacco smoking has a detrimental impact on the health of the world's population [1-3]. A significant number of people who are not addicted to smoking inhale tobacco smoke in one way or another, experiencing so-called secondhand smoke, which is no less dangerous to health than smoking itself. In addition to causing irreversible harm to the health of others, this habit hinders a healthy lifestyle and slows the personal and moral growth of young men and women [4]. Moreover, the negative impact of secondhand smoke on the body is not limited to the moment of exposure but also affects its subsequent growth. For children who are non-smokers, visiting heavily smoky areas (school restrooms, gym locker rooms, internet clubs) can result in secondhand smoke equivalent to fourteen cigarettes per day [5,6]. Passive smoking is more harmful than active smoking, as the smoker inhales portions of the smoke that pass through the filter. This portion accounts for only 35-40% of the smoke, while the remaining 60-65% is generated during the smoldering of the cigarette itself and is inhaled by others. The severity of diseases caused by secondhand smoke is greater the younger the child. However, it should be noted that most of the harm caused to a child by cigarette smoke will only become apparent after several decades [7-10]. Among the most dangerous changes in the normal functioning of the human body is a weakening of the immune system — the ability to adequately respond to external threats of disease, both infectious and non-infectious. According to official data, 40% of asthmatic children are passive smokers [11]. Children of smoking mothers typically experience delayed mental and physical development. The sedentary lifestyle of today's youth, especially in urban environments, is one of the main factors contributing to the increased incidence of illness among them. The most detrimental factor is the deviation of their anthropometric parameters from the norm, which are key indicators of schoolchildren's health [12-15]. After school and homework, schoolchildren spend all their free time in front of televisions and computers, use mobile phones, and visit internet clubs, which are now found in virtually every courtyard [16]. In recent years, a sharp decline in physical activity has been observed among both children and adults. Given the lack of awareness about passive smoking due to the low social status and financial well-being of many parents, children are exposed to passive smoking at home, are denied the opportunity to attend sports clubs due to their inability to pay for them, and are often excused from physical education classes due to various illnesses, appearance-related prejudices (such as those associated with obesity), and are also unable to afford sportswear [17-20]. The importance of artificial intelligence (AI) is finding its place in medicine for the treatment of various diseases, including harmful habits such as smoking and associated passive smoking [21]. A cutting-edge smoking cessation strategy has been developed by the Fred Hutchinson Cancer Center in Seattle, which has launched a free app with an AI-powered chatbot designed to help users quit. The app, known

as QuitBot, utilizes scientifically proven strategies developed by Fred Hutch experts based on more than 20 years of research. QuitBot is a comprehensive smoking cessation program consisting of 3-5 minute conversations conducted in two stages: 14 days before and 28 days after quitting, covering a wide range of topics and answering users' questions. Unlike similar resources, QuitBot provides users with personalized support via a mobile device whenever they feel the urge [22-25]. This unfavorable trend persists in modern society, as does the increasing incidence of children and adolescents with visual impairment, ophthalmological diseases, and, crucially, weakened immune systems. Causes of growth retardation associated with passive smoking in adolescents include inhibition of growth hormone production, as well as testosterone deficiency and insufficient oxygen supply to muscle tissue (hypoxia), which poses a high risk of growth retardation in children aged 6 to 8 years [26]. Excessive or unhealthy nutrition poses a particular risk for the spread of many socially significant chronic non-communicable diseases. Eating behavior is defined as food choice, eating regimen and schedule, and physiological, psychological, and socioeconomic factors influencing a person's living conditions [27,28]. Eating disorders can lead to the development of dangerous non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular and gastrointestinal diseases, contributing to the development of risk factors such as elevated blood cholesterol (hypercholesterolemia), overweight, and obesity [29]. Impaired cholesterol metabolism in the central nervous system leads to emotional distress, memory loss, and an increased risk of psychiatric disorders. Frequent stress increases the production of the hormone cortisol, which destroys protein tissue, leading to elevated blood glucose levels [30-32]. Impaired cholesterol metabolism in the central nervous system leads to emotional distress, memory loss, and an increased risk of psychiatric disorders. The higher the stress level, the less a person feels satiated, which means they consume more food. Considering that food is also high in calories, it's safe to say how susceptible a person is to excess weight, which causes metabolic disorders and, consequently, contributes to obesity [33]. An unbalanced, high-calorie diet leads to a decrease in important micronutrients in the body, such as magnesium, which influences bone growth and regulates blood sugar levels. Smoking cessation, in addition to withdrawal symptoms, is usually accompanied by weight gain. The food environment has a significant impact on people's eating behavior. It includes physical, economic, social, and cultural factors that facilitate or hinder food choices. Limited access to healthy food, its high cost, unavailability, poor quality or availability, the attractiveness and increased advertising of unhealthy foods can lead to an inability to develop healthy eating habits and increase the risk of developing eating disorders. Increasing access to healthy food makes it easier for people to choose healthy foods [34-37]. This can be achieved by reducing the price of healthy foods, increasing their availability (e.g., in neighborhood

stores, schools, workplaces, or public spaces), increasing healthy food advertising, conducting awareness campaigns about healthy eating, or organizing healthy eating programs. The consumption of fast foods, sugary soft drinks, baked goods, sweets, and other unhealthy, high-calorie foods, which are consumed not only by children but also by adults, especially when experiencing emotional distress and leading to disordered eating, is reflected in anthropometric indicators, especially in childhood. Restricting access to unhealthy foods makes it more difficult for people to choose them. This can be achieved by raising the prices of unhealthy foods (e.g., by taxing sugary drinks or fast food), restricting the sale of unhealthy foods (e.g., by banning the sale of unhealthy foods in schools and hospitals), banning the advertising of unhealthy foods, eliminating misleading information about unhealthy foods, or eliminating programs that promote unhealthy eating [38]. Food price regulation and healthy diet subsidies can help improve access to healthy food. This is especially important for low-income families, who face significant barriers to accessing healthy food. Food advertising has a significant impact on people's eating behavior. Regulating food advertising can help people make healthy choices [39,40]. This can be achieved by banning unhealthy food advertising, increasing healthy food advertising, preventing misleading information in food advertising, limiting food advertising aimed at children, or preventing negative messages about modeling in food advertising [41,42].

Purpose of work. To explore social and hygienic aspects of reducing children's exposure to passive smoking and to develop preventive measures based on the questionnaire data obtained and a study of children's outpatient records, for the further implementation of programs to radically eliminate this harmful phenomenon.

Materials and methods. We decided to measure height, weight, and chest circumference by dividing schoolchildren into two groups — those exposed to passive smoking and those not. This study was conducted as part of a study examining the impact of family passive smoking on children's health and academic performance. We developed a questionnaire containing seven sets of questions on various social and hygienic aspects of passive smoking. The questionnaires were divided into two parts: one completed by students and the other by their parents. The study was conducted in five city secondary schools (in the Khatai, Binagadi, and Sabail districts). Only fully completed questionnaires were included in the study. A total of 9,000 questionnaires were distributed to schoolchildren. Of these, 4,726 fully completed questionnaires contained responses from 7,790 parents—3,770 fathers and 4,020 mothers. Each of the 4,726 questionnaires represented one schoolchild, meaning that 4,726 families were surveyed. Depending on smoking intensity, all families were divided into two groups: 1,636 families (tobacco-dependent) and 3,090 families (tobacco-independent, i.e., the control group). Based on passive smoking intensity, the tobacco-dependent group of families was divided into: Group 1—408 families,

mild tobacco dependence, less than 7 cigarettes per day; The 2nd group — 504 families, moderate tobacco addiction — 7-18 cigarettes/day, and the 3rd group — 724 families, addictive smoking of parents, severe tobacco addiction, more than 18 cigarettes/day. Measurements were conducted separately for boys and girls. We simultaneously examined the outpatient records of children in children's clinics in the aforementioned districts to identify various types of visits and the degree of morbidity. Observations were conducted in the most anthropometrically significant age groups of schoolchildren. Along with the questionnaires, we also examined the outpatient records of schoolchildren in regional clinics. Considering the intensity of various diseases and their nosological forms noted in the questionnaires, we concluded that ophthalmological and dental morbidity was high among tobacco-dependent schoolchildren. Each anthropometric indicator — weight, height, and chest circumference — was analyzed separately and, where necessary, compared with others. To determine the extent to which passive smoking affects schoolchildren's physical activity, the following study was conducted. School attendance records were analyzed. The data of interest were obtained from 2,966 of the 4,726 students surveyed. Of these, 1,130 were exposed to passive smoking in their families, and 1,830 were not. The results are shown in Figure 2. Based on the analysis of class records, students' physical activity, or the nature of their attendance in physical education classes, was divided into the following categories: Group A — exempt from classes for medical reasons, not always for objective reasons; Group B — not exempt from classes, but failing to attend despite disciplinary measures; Group C — attend classes, but are inactive, partially completing the required lesson schedule. Group D — attend classes, are quite active, and complete all assigned tasks; Group E — attend classes and are quite active, and additionally do morning exercises or jog for 15-30 minutes; Group F — attend classes and are active, and additionally participate in various sports.

Results and discussion. Using Table 1, we calculated the correlation coefficient (χ^2). To establish a qualitative relationship between the degree of tobacco dependence, i.e., the number of cigarettes smoked per day in tobacco-dependent families, and the number of schoolchildren covered by our study range, we conducted the calculation in several stages. The first stage involved calculating the ratio of the family indicator, taking into account the degree of their tobacco dependence, to the total number of tobacco-dependent families, multiplied by 100%. The second stage involved calculating the ratio of each indicator from the first stage to the total number of each row as a percentage. The third stage involved calculating the correlation coefficient, the result of which for all three tobacco-dependent groups is 17.16. To estimate χ^2 and draw final conclusions, we use a table of χ^2 values. Using this table, we determine the value $n/a = (r-1)*(s-1)$, where r is the number of columns in the table (except the summary) and s is the number of rows. We then compare the calculated χ^2 value with the table χ^2 value at row 20. In our case, the calculated χ^2 value

(17.16) is less than its table value (28.412) and corresponds to a probability of 0.10. This means that our null hypothesis (an increase in the number of cigarettes smoked per day directly plays a role in the development of tobacco addiction), as it has a probability of greater than 0.10. The data in Figure 1 show that, across all the identified categories, the physical activity of schoolchildren exposed to passive smoking (Group 1) is lower than that of schoolchildren not exposed to passive smoking (Group 2). Thus, 16.8±1.6% of schoolchildren in the 1st group and 8.3±0.9% of schoolchildren in the 2nd group were exempt from physical education classes for medical reasons (t=4.62; p<0.001). 11.7±1.4% of schoolchildren and 6.1±0.8% of schoolchildren, respectively, were not exempted, but did not attend classes despite the measures taken (t=3.48; p<0.001).

Table
The ratio of cigarettes per day in tobacco-dependent families to the degree of their tobacco dependence

Intensity of exposure to passive smoking in families of schoolchildren							
Tobacco-independent						Result	Tobacco-independent 3090
1636							
Degree of tobacco dependence							
Weak <7 sig./day 408 families		Moderate 7-18 sig./day 504 families		Heavy >18 sig./day 724 families			
P	P1	P	P1	P	P1		
Age, years							
6,0-6,9							
36	33,8	46	41,8	54	60,2	136	
7,0-7,9							
38	36,8	48	45,4	62	65,4	148	
8,0-8,9							
34	32,2	38	40,04	58	57,4	130	
9,0-9,9							
40	37,4	46	46,2	64	66,2	150	
10,0-10,9							
44	39,2	58	48,6	56	69,8	158	
11,0-11,9							
38	37,4	44	48,6	68	66,2	150	
12,0-12,9							
42	41,2	48	51,0	76	73,2	166	
13,0-13,9							
34	34,2	42	42,4	62	60,8	138	

14,0-14,9							
32	40,2	50	49,8	80	71,6	162	
15,0-15,9							
36	39,2	52	48,6	70	69,8	158	
16,0-16,9							
34	34,8	32	43,0	74	61,8	140	
$X^2 = 3,36$		$\chi^2 = 6,4$		$\chi^2 = 7,4$		$X^2 = 17,16$	

Attending physical education classes

Figure. Attendance at physical education classes by schoolchildren exposed and not exposed to passive smoking.

Conclusion. Parental concern for their children’s health before they reach sufficient independence is not only a leading social factor in maintaining children’s health but also a mediator of the effectiveness of medical care for illness. With increasing duration and intensity of smoking, not only does the incidence of illness increase, but it also becomes more severe, leading to longer-term consequences and greater difficulty in treating. Smoking more than 20 cigarettes a day, a severe addiction, causes damage to internal organs and the nervous system, and often causes myopia, dry eye, and optic nerve damage in smokers themselves. At the same time, parental surveys have revealed very low awareness of the impact of passive smoking on children’s ophthalmological health. Passive smoking prevention should be aimed at reducing the number of public and government institutions where smoking is permitted. The number of smoke-free places, or so-called smoke-free zones, should be expanded. This fight began with the smoking ban in healthcare facilities and government institutions, but it must be the goal of every

citizen. Information technology is being actively integrated into the medical field. Physicians, in addition to practical skills, must be able to work with medical information systems and artificial intelligence. In particular, the use of virtual patients promotes the effective acquisition of clinical skills and the development of clinical thinking in both students and physicians. Thus, information technology not only expands educational horizons but also creates the conditions for the development of a new type of specialist who is prepared to work in a high-tech environment and apply innovative approaches in their practice.

References:

1. Siqueira L. M. *Committee On Substance Use and Prevention. Nicotine and tobacco as substances of abuse in children and adolescents / Siqueira L. M. // Pediatrics.* — 2017. — Vol. 139. — P. e20163436.
2. Babayev P.N., Askerov Z. A. *The role of passive smoking in global climate change and the negative impact of this phenomenon on the health and development of children/Ccientific-practical journal named after A.Aliyev “ The Medicine and Science” № 1 35.* 2024. P. 62-69.
3. Filippova, I. V. *Attitude of young students to the problem of smoking / I. V. Filippova, E. V. Saperova // Modern Science.* 2019. No. 10-2. P. 21-23.
4. T.N. Kozhevnikova, N. A. Geppe, I. M. Osmanov, N. F. Gerasimenko, N. G. Mashukova, N. A. Ilyenkova, A. B. Malakhov, M. M. Chepurnaya, N. D. Odinaeva, N. V. Savvina // *The problem of smoking among adolescents: yesterday, today, tomorrow // Pediatrics. Supplement to the journal Consilium Medicum* — 2021 — No. 2 — P. 101-108.
5. Christiansen C., Castillo-Fernandez J. E., Domingo-Relloso A., et al. *Novel DNA methylation signatures of tobacco smoking with trans-ethnic effects. Clin Epigenet.* 2021;13(1):36.
6. K.D. Okhotnikova *The influence of modern analog smoking methods on the human body / K. D. Okhotnikova, P. A. Rusanova // FORCIPE.* — 2019. — No. Appendix. — P. 562-562.
7. Barbaruk, Yu. V. *Features of the impact of warnings about the dangers of smoking on modern youth / Yu. V. Barbaruk, A. V. Barbaruk // Science for Education Today.* 2020. Vol. 10. No. 1. Pp. 113-126.
8. *The association between e-cigarette use and asthma among never combustible cigarette smokers: behavioral risk factor surveillance system (BRFSS) 2016 & 2017 / Osei A. D., Mirbolouk M., Orimoloye O. A. [et al.] // BMC Pulm Med.* — 2019. — Vol. 19 (1). — P. 180. — URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/31619218>.

9. Kuznetsova, L. V. (ed.). *Information technology in medicine*. — M.: MED press-inform, 2020.

10. Goryacheva, V. V., Kozlova, A. A. "Application of Information Technologies in Medical Education: Opportunities and Challenges." *Journal of Medical Informatics*, 2022, no. 4, pp. 20-29.

11. Almirall J. Passive smoking at home is a risk factor for community-acquired pneumonia in older adults: a population-based case-control study / Almirall J., Serra-Prat M., Bolibar I. // *Community Acquired Infection*. — 2015. — Vol. 2. — P. 32-37.

12. Mankibaev B. S. Main directions of implementation of artificial intelligence in medicine. / B. S. Mankibaev // *Science, education and culture*. — 2019. — P. 3.

13. Home Smoke Exposure and Health-Related Quality of Life in Children with Acute Respiratory Illness / Johnson J., Wilson K., Zhou C., Johnson D. [et al.] // *J Hosp Med*. — 2019. — Apr. — Vol. 14 (4). — P. 212-217.

14. Badea M, Luzardo OP, González-Antuña A, Zumbado M, Rogozea L, Floroian L, Alexandrescu D, Moga M, Gaman L, Radoi M, Boada LD, Henríquez-Hernández LA. Body burden of toxic metals and rare earth elements in non-smokers, cigarette smokers and electronic cigarette users. *Environmental Research*. 2018;166:269-275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2018.06.007>

15. Zhedunova L. G., Voldaeva A. S. Boundaries of the psychological space of the individual as a factor in eating disorders // *Yaroslavl Pedagogical Bulletin*, 2019, No. 4, v. II, pp. 237-241.

16. Andriani H. Parental Smoking and Under-Five Child Mortality in Southeast Asia: Evidence from Demographic and Health Surveys / Andriani H., Putri S., Kosasih R., Kuo H. // *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. — 2019. — Nov. 27. — Vol. 16 (23). — (pii: E4756).

17. Averianova O. A. Artificial intelligence in the context of modern medicine / O. A. Averianova, V. I. Korshak // *Natural and mathematical sciences in the modern world*. — 2016. — No. 5 (40). — P. 36.

18. Fersht V. M. Modern approaches to the use of artificial intelligence in medicine. / V. M. Fersht, A. P. Latkin, V. N. Ivanova // *Territory of new opportunities. VSUES Bulletin*. — 2020. — P. 127-128

19. Shaderkin I. A. Weaknesses of artificial intelligence in medicine. / I. A. Shaderkin // *Journal of Telemedicine and Electronic Healthcare*. — 2021. — P. 51-52.

20. Pikalyuk V. S., Shalanin V. V., Zhuravel E. A., Asanova Z. V. Structural changes in the lungs of rats during inhalation of nicotine-free e-liquid aerosol. *Journal of Anatomy and Histopathology*. 2016;5(2):41-45.

21. A.A. Khadartsev, T. N. Kozhevnikova / *Some issues of nicotine addiction treatment // Bulletin of new medical technologies. Electronic publication — 2021 — No. 4 (volume 15) — pp. 27-32*
22. Meshcheryakova A. M. *Artificial intelligence in medical visualization. Main tasks and development scenarios / Meshcheryakova A. M., Akopyan E. A., Slinin A. S. // Journal of Telemedicine and Electronic Healthcare. — 2018. — P. 100.*
23. Srivastava R. *Applications of artificial intelligence in medicine. Explor Res Hypothesis Med. Published online: Sep. 19, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.14218/ERHM.2023.00048>.*
24. Gainutdinov M.Kh., Khakimova D. M., Kalinnikova T. B., Shagidullin R. R. (2019). *On the role of the cholinergic system in the body's stress response and depression. Ulyanovsk Medical and Biological Journal. 1, 93-102.*
25. Briganti G., Le Moine O. *Artificial intelligence in medicine: today and tomorrow. Front Med. 2020; 7: 27. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.00027>.*
26. Alekseeva M.G., Zubov A. I., Novikov M. Yu. *Artificial intelligence in medicine. International research journal. 2022; 7: 10-3. <https://doi.org/10.23670/IRJ.2022.121.7.038>.*
27. Harvard University: *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: Applications, implications, and limitations. [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://sitn.hms.harvard.edu/flash/2019/artificial-intelligence-in-medicine-applications-implications-and-limitations/> (accessed 10.05.2022)*
28. Jimma B. L. *Artificial intelligence in healthcare: a bibliometric analysis. Telemat Inform Rep. 2023; 9 (Suppl. 1): 100041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teler.2023.100041>.*
29. Mironov MB, Abramov MO, Kondratenko VV et al. *Application of artificial intelligence in the diagnosis of absence epilepsy with simultaneous verification of the patient's level of consciousness during an ictal event. Epilepsy and paroxysmal states. 2024; 16 (1): 8-7. <https://doi.org/10.17749/2077-8333/epi.par.con.2024.178>.*
30. Lamotkin A.I., Korabelnikov D. I., Lamotkin I. A., Livshits S. A., Perevalova E. G. *Artificial intelligence in healthcare and medicine: history of key developments, importance for doctors, level of development in different countries. Pharmacoconomics. Modern pharmacoconomics and pharmacoepidemiology. 2024;17(2):243-250. <https://doi.org/10.17749/2070-4909/farmakoeconomika.2024.254>*
31. Hang B, Wang P, Zhao Y, Chang H, Mao JH, Snijders AM. *Thirdhand smoke: Genotoxicity and carcinogenic potential Chronic Dis Transl Med. 2019 Sep 26;6(1):27-34. e. Collection 2020 Mar. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2095882X19300672>*

32. Babayev P.N., Aliyev R. R. *Passive smoking of electronic cigarettes among children as a medical and social problem/ Scientific-practical journal named after A. Aliyev "The Medicine and Science" № 3 37. 2024. P. 31-40.*
33. Mogilny M. P. *Development of a program for the formation of a culture of healthy eating for children and adolescents / M. P. Mogilny, T. V. Shlenskaya, N. I. Valentinova // Successes of modern science and education. 2016. Vol. 2, No. 11. P. 15-19.*
34. Bazeo N. P. *All the secrets of healthy eating. Moscow: Medical Literature, 2018. Pp. 79-85.*
35. Rashid M.A., Ugrekhelidze D. T. *Social aspects of tobacco smoking // Pharmacoconomics: theory and practice. 2014. Vol. 2. No. 3. P. 82-88. 200*
36. Ahluwalia IB, Smith T, Arrazola RA, Palipudi KM, Garcia de Quevedo I, Prasad VM et al. *Current tobacco smoking, quit attempts, and knowledge about smoking risks among persons aged ≥ 15 years — Global Adult Tobacco Survey, 28 countries, 2008-2016. Morb Mortal Wkly Rep. 2018;67:1072-6. doi: 10.15585/mmwr.mm6738a7.*
37. Roshchin, D. O. *Protecting citizens' health from exposure to tobacco smoke: administrative practice / D. O. Roshchin, A. N. Plutnitsky // Healthcare Manager. — 2016. — No. 10. — P. 46-50.*
38. *Proper nutrition. A complete reference [electronic resource]: / Ed. B. Yu. Lamikhov. Saratov: Nauchnaya kniga, 2019, pp. 296-338. URL: <http://www.iprbookshop.ru/80176.html>*
39. *Physiology of Nutrition [electronic resource]: a textbook for students of secondary vocational education / Ed. S. Barysheva. Saratov: Vocational Education, 2020. pp. 99-115. URL: <http://www.iprbookshop.ru/92192.html>*
40. Kristofovich A. A. *Modeling of tobacco smoking and deposition of smoke and tar microparticles in the respiratory tract / Kristofovich A. A. // Pulmonology. — 2017. — Vol. 27, No. 5. — P. 643-649.*
41. Kulikova O.A., Kolositsyna M. G. *Socio-economic factors and consequences of excess weight//NRU, Russia 2019, vol.5 No. 4 — pp. 92-124.*
42. I. G. Silkis. (2019). *Possible mechanisms of the complex influence of acetylcholine on theta activity, learning and memory. Neurochemistry. 36, 101-118;*

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**A NEW PERITONEAL ADHESION INDEX (PAI-4GV/D)
IN THE CLASSIFICATION OF ABDOMINAL ADHESIONS
AND ITS ROLE IN DETERMINING THE RISK OF REOPERATION
ON LAPAROSCOPIC SURGERY**

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Abstract. Abdominal adhesions 'de novo' (following surgery for adhesive intestinal obstruction) represent an extremely undesirable complication for the patient. Adhesive connections in the abdominal cavity significantly complicate the work of surgeons, especially during repeat operations. This study utilized a scientific approach based on the concept of the so-called interface. The refined term 'adhesive interface' was proposed. Within this conceptual framework, a barrier mesogel was applied intraoperatively to prevent adhesion formation. An original

proprietary classification of the abdominal adhesion index has been developed. Unlike the widely used Peritoneal Adhesion Index (PAI), the index proposed and validated by us includes 4 gradations and 2 additional zones to account for adhesion localization (V-Ventral zone and D — Dorsal zone). It was found that 'de novo' adhesion is more frequently detected in the ventral zone and less frequently in the dorsal zone. The peritoneal index scale proposed by us, named PAI-4gV/D, may assist in determining the method and site of trocar insertion into the abdominal cavity. Including in single-port surgery (Single-port surgery).

Keywords: *'de novo' adhesion, Peritoneal Adhesion Index, surgery, adhesiolysis, adhesion prevention*

Abdominal 'de novo' adhesions (following surgery for adhesive intestinal obstruction) are a common and highly undesirable complication for the patient. Such adhesive formations in the peritoneal cavity significantly complicate surgeons' work during subsequent reoperations. Serious complications following surgical intervention for acute intestinal obstruction (AIO) are always associated with significant treatment challenges and suboptimal efficacy. This remains an unresolved issue for surgeons, gastroenterologists, and other specialists.

We conducted a review and comprehensive analysis of the most recent medical literature, where the mechanisms of adhesion prevention are systematically discussed and reconsidered. Special attention was given to the clinical features of the disease, diagnostic methods, and treatments most commonly used in patients recently, which have been the focus of discussions and scientific debates.

Furthermore, the positive properties and drawbacks of anti-adhesive agents were thoroughly studied. After applying various prophylactic methods in our surgical practice and obtaining insufficiently reliable, and in some cases highly unconvincing, results, we realized that primary attention must be paid to the physicochemical characteristics of anti-adhesive drugs and devices.

Experience and observations of patients in the surgical clinic indicated the direction in which research should be conducted regarding the causes of failures in the prevention and treatment of abdominal adhesions.

By analyzing contemporary publications, what was quite obvious but had long seemed less important was clearly identified. At the same time, two components were distinguished within a single paradigm, within which the problem of adhesion formation should be comprehensively considered.

1. First and foremost, this involves understanding and formulating a concept based on the following: for a thorough analysis, biological, chemical, and morphological studies of adhesions must be conducted. Particularly those adhesions that form and newly develop at the tissue interface ('de novo' adhesion). This adhesion process occurs: a) between the walls of the intestine, b) between the intestinal wall

and the parietal peritoneum, and c) also between the walls of the intestine and adipose tissue, including the omentum.

2. Secondly, the necessity to adopt and take into account the conceptual framework that highlights the predominant role of the qualitative composition of the anti-adhesive agent. As well as the condition of organs and tissues (severity of the inflammatory process, presence of peritoneal damage, depth and extent of desiccation, etc.) in the initiation and progression of adhesions. It is also necessary to consider and classify the methods of applying anti-adhesive films, as well as other devices, which can be grouped under the term 'Anti-adhesive implant/components' (AntiAI). Unlike routine approaches focused on the quantitative and volumetric application of materials, the new concept, based on the analysis of the interaction between AntiAI and surrounding tissues, aims to study the earliest processes of adhesion development (adhesions 'de novo'), with the goal of enhancing anti-adhesive efficacy. We support the opinion of certain clinicians regarding the presence of different types of adhesions between tissues. Our research is based on the issue of the development of such events (adhesion formation) at the boundary between two anatomical regions. More precisely, on the fact that this process occurs in the transitional layer between two surfaces, that is, at the contact point, at the interface between two media. Recently, this boundary layer has been termed the 'Interface.' We propose to consider it in a more specific manner. Therefore, in our study, during the investigation of the formation of abdominal adhesions, we designated it as the 'Adhesive Interface.' Considering current scientific advances in adhesion prevention and the concept of the interface, we have divided the classification of adhesion prevention mechanisms into several principal types. These include antiproliferative, tissue growth reducing/suppressive, anti-inflammatory, anti-edematous, and antifibrotic types. They correspond to the primary determinants of anti-adhesion efficacy. In this context, the volumetric properties of the adhesion mechanism serve as the main auxiliary factors supporting the mechanism of adhesion formation and enhancing the interface functionality.

By volumetric properties, we refer to: a) mechanical strength, b) degradation kinetics, c) compliance of adhesions, and their extensibility. In our studies of adhesions, we adhere to the contemporary scientific concept that characterizes the pathogenesis of adhesion formation. It encompasses three principal processes induced by operative trauma: (I) inhibition of fibrinolytic and extracellular matrix degradation systems; (II) induction of the inflammatory response involving the production of cytokines and transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β 1), a key regulator of tissue fibrosis; (III) induction of tissue hypoxia following disruption of blood supply to mesothelial cells and submesothelial fibroblasts, leading to increased expression of *factor-1 α* induced by hypoxia and *vascular endothelial growth factor*, which is responsible for collagen formation and angiogenesis.[1]

We employed well-known approaches to adhesion prevention, such as modern surgical methods (surgical method — Surg), which are optimally adapted for the abdominal adhesion process; pharmacological/medicinal products (pharmacological/medicinal products — PhmP); Anti-adhesion films/forms, so-called AntiAI. To prevent abdominal adhesion during laparoscopic surgery, the anti-adhesion gel “Lintex/Mesogel” was used as a PhmP, which belongs to the barrier component of the scientific concept of the “interface” proposed by Zhen Zheng et al. in 2025. The more specific term ‘adhesive’ refers to the management of adhesion resulting from intraoperative injury or desiccation of organ surfaces during surgery. The action of the gel is intended to create a temporary barrier around (at the interface of) the injured contacting surfaces. This ensures their separation during the healing period.

To characterize the volume, nature, quantity, and severity of the adhesion process in the peritoneal cavity, the well-established Peritoneal Adhesion Index (PAI) classification was used. [2] This classification includes the following gradations: 0 — No adhesions; 1 — Filmy adhesions, blunt dissection; 2 — Strong adhesions, sharp dissection; 3 — Very strong vascularized adhesions, sharp dissection, damage hardly preventable. For the assessment, 10 adhesion locations are also presented, ranging from ‘Epigastrium’ to ‘Pelvis’ and ‘Bowel to bowel.’

PERITONEAL ADHESION INDEX:

Regions:	Adhesion grade:
A Right upper	___
B Epigastrium	___
C Left upper	___
D Left flank	___
E Left lower	___
F Pelvis	___
G Right lower	___
H Right flank	___
I Central	___
L Bowel to bowel	___

However, our experience with the use of the aforementioned adhesion index over 10 years has revealed the necessity for its improvement. In our study, it was determined that obtaining a comprehensive overview of the adhesion process in a significant number of patients using PAI is challenging. Characterizing all adhesion localization sites in the abdominal cavity and their quality is quite difficult. It has been found that adhesions between the anterior abdominal wall and the intestine, as well as the greater omentum, impede not only the introduction of the trocar but also an adequate laparoscopic surgery with adhesiolysis. Analysis of clinical cases has shown that the nature and density of anterior adhesions differ from those of posterior adhesions (formed between the intestine and the posterior leaf of the parietal peritoneum). When such adhesions predominate, the introduction of trocars into the abdomen is not impeded, and ‘de novo’ adhesion at these sites is minimal according to our data.

According to our observations of 148 laparoscopic adhesiolysis surgeries, in 73 (49%) cases, the insertion of two or three trocars at different sites was extremely difficult. Therefore, we opted for a transumbilical single-port access to the abdominal cavity through a single incision, known as Single-port surgery (SpSurg). In the other cases, the access was traditional (3-port) or via open laparotomy. During the postoperative period, recovery was more favorable in patients with posterior (dorsal) localization of adhesions.

The dorsal zone — **D** (from Latin *dorsalis*) induced “de novo” adhesions less frequently than the ventral zone — **V** (from Latin *ventralis*). However, during reoperation, the localization of these adhesions was predominant. Complications such as acute intestinal obstruction were very rare, not exceeding 10% within 1 year. In contrast, for ventral localization, the incidence of intestinal obstruction was observed in 23% of patients after 1 year.

We considered this phenomenon in subsequent surgeries. Furthermore, reoperation using the single-port surgery (SpSurg) method demonstrated a minimal risk of injury to internal organs (intestine, omental vessels, etc.), since in those same patients with D localization of adhesions, the peritoneal adhesion index was lower. This risk cannot be calculated using the traditional PAI. In our developed PAI classification (with a 4-point grading scale considering ventral and dorsal zones), this issue was resolved quite successfully. The scheme of the developed and validated «Peritoneal Adhesion Index» is presented in

Figure 2. Peritoneal Adhesion Index — PAI-4gV/D; where V-Ventral zone (lat. ventralis); D — Dorsal zone (lat. dorsalis), separated by a vertical line.

The classification developed by us: «Peritoneal Adhesion Index — 4-grade V/D»

- 0 — No adhesions.
 - 1 — Filmy adhesions, blunt dissection.
 - 2 — Dense adhesions, sharp + blunt dissection.
 - 3 — Very dense vascularized adhesions, sharp dissection only.
 - 4 — Very dense vascularized adhesions, where injury is difficult to prevent.
- Regions **A, B, C, D, E, F, G, I, H** are supplemented by two zones: **V** and **D**.

As a result. For example, if there is a single dense adhesion **2g** located in region **H** supplemented by zone **D**, the index notation for the identified adhesion during surgery will be: **2gH/D**. If an adhesion **2g** is localized in region **H**, in the anterior ventral zone, then the adhesion designation according to our index will be **2gH/V**.

The adhesion index developed by us and presented in this article is highly practical for the surgeon's work; it is more precise and more universal compared to the index currently used worldwide. It is especially essential when deciding whether to perform surgery using the SpSurg method.

Conclusions. The study of the mechanisms of 'de novo' adhesion formation requires a new approach to the conceptualization of the so-called 'Adhesive Interface'. The analysis of various preventive methods and the development of new techniques should be undertaken within this new paradigm. This fundamentally proposes an approach to the prevention of adhesion formation within the framework of an anti-adhesive strategy aimed at preventing tissue fusion at the interface between two environments. In our study, the newly proposed classification

of abdominal adhesions, PAI-4gVsDs (comprising 4 gradations and two zones), enables an accurate characterization of abdominal adhesions, including their localization and nature. The primary advantage of our enhanced PAI-4gVsDs index is its capability to determine the risk of possible intestine injury during reoperation and the insertion of a laparoscopic trocar. The presence of a large number of adhesions-Vs (according to PAI-4gVsDs) indicates the necessity of performing single-port transumbilical access using the Single-port surgery technique.

References

1. Zhen Zheng, Shengli Gao, Jingwen Liu, Yong Zhang. *Interface before bulk: Mechanism-informed strategy for preventing postoperative adhesion based on polymer implants. Acta Biomaterialia. 2025; V.206: P. 43-73. doi: 10.1016/j.actbio.2025.09.021*
2. Coccolini F, Ansaloni L, Manfredi R, Campanati L, Poiasina E, Bertoli P, Capponi MG, Sartelli M, Di Saverio S, Cucchi M, Lazzareschi D, Pisano M, Catena F. *Peritoneal adhesion index (PAI): proposal of a score for the “ignored iceberg” of medicine and surgery. World J Emerg Surg. 2013 Jan 31;8(1):6. doi: 10.1186/1749-7922-8-6*

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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATION OF DENTISTS

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Abstract. *Phygital technologies in education constitute an integrated educational model based on the use of digital technologies and electronic resources to improve the effectiveness and personalization of the learning process. The authors developed and tested a virtual model program, the «VR simulator for tooth preparation for metal-ceramic crowns». The article presents the advantages and benefits of training surgeons using this VR complex, which provides opportunities for high-flex learning.*

Keywords: *fidgetal technologies, virtual reality, dental education training, digital education.*

Relevance. Digital education and digital transformation have become the most relevant and widely discussed topics in the modern educational environment. The

development of information technologies (IT) began in the late 20th century and has transitioned to a digital format across all sectors of the economy in general and in education in particular.

The Covid-19 pandemic has further accelerated the process of digitalization. Particular attention was given to the development of distance education. However, digital education is not limited to distance learning alone. It is a comprehensive system for modernizing the educational process by utilizing contemporary IT technologies in both distance and traditional education. The digital education environment includes a wide range of interactive tools, from cloud systems to virtual (VR) and augmented reality (AR), which facilitate more effective knowledge acquisition [1-3].

Ultimately, digital education and digital transformation have become integral parts of the educational sphere. They offer new opportunities for learning and development but require active engagement and training from all participants in the educational process. While attempts to use VR technologies in specialist training are already being made in surgery, they are entirely absent in dentistry.

The aim of this study was to develop a VR simulator for tooth preparation for metal-ceramic crowns.

Materials and Methods. The programming languages used were C++ and Blueprints. The software size was 8 GB. A simulation scenario was developed, and the compliance of actions with medical standards was verified; program code was written, and the interface was developed.

Results. We developed a virtual model designed to train skills for tooth preparation for metal-ceramic crowns. The simulator allows users to refine skills in handling various attachments, select the necessary tools for each stage of preparation, and perfect delicate instrument movements. The mechanics of operation and the form of the attachments replicate those in real life, enabling the development of muscle memory. During the simulation, the trainee is required to perform tooth preparation on five teeth: two upper and three lower.

Certificate No. 2025680038 dated 01.08.2025 has been issued. VR simulator for tooth preparation for metal-ceramic crowns. This patent was preceded by the surgical VR simulator Surgery VR, a computer program for training and skill development of students and practicing surgeons. The first version of the program was developed in 2021 by LLC 'X Red Group,' and has been actively refined and improved since then. The advantages of the program over domestic and international competitors include exceptional flexibility; an unmatched procedural generation system for tissue damage in surgical applications; the capability to assess and report trainee performance (evaluating accuracy of actions, speed of operation stages, correctness of the sequence of dental intervention, etc.); one of the highest levels of graphics and realism in the field; and excellent optimization due to the use of the best available visualization technologies.

Fig. 1 Materials of audiovisual representations generated by computer software/database

The use of this simulator is intended to optimize the training of dental practitioners. Furthermore, the simulator's functionality was adapted for use with gloves equipped with force feedback tactile features, enabling significant improvements in motion tracking accuracy and allowing the user to feel the shape of objects held in their hands. This technology had not previously been applied in surgical and dental simulations and was first tested by us on the SURVREYLINE simulator. The gloves were also produced by the scientific team of LLC 'X Red Group,' which included the author of this study, and have no domestic equivalents.

Conclusions. The developed simulator enables continuous and unlimited practice of fundamental dental skills without risking the condition of patients' teeth, providing a fully realistic visual and tactile experience. It is important to note the extremely low wear, minimal power consumption, and high maintainability of the hardware supplied with the program, ensuring reliable and uninterrupted operation of the training complex. Thus, the program simultaneously solves two tasks: reducing equipment procurement costs and saving training space.

References

1. Karvunis Yu.A., Kalinnikova Yu.G., Karvunis N. A., Kapilevich L. V. *Prospects for the Implementation of Phygital Technologies in the Educational Process of Higher Education Institutions // Vestnik of Tomsk State University.* — 2024. — No. 502. — pp. 167-172.
2. Gryaznova E. V. *Contradictions of Digital Higher Education in the Information Culture of Modern Society // Vestnik of Minin University.* 2023. — Vol. 11, No. 1 (42).
3. Galushko T. G. *Human-Centered Phygital and Digital Education: Digitalization and Humanization // Bulletin of the Herzen Russian State Pedagogical University.* — 2022. — No. 204. — pp. 25-34

THE EFFECT OF FIR EXTRACT ON INCREASING THE SHELF LIFE OF UNFILTERED FERMENTED KVASS

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Abstract. This article examines the dynamics of quality and safety indicators of kvass under the influence of coniferous extracts rich in natural antioxidants, primarily dihydroquercetin. The research object was kvass of the 'Domashniy' brand (LLC 'Vkus', Krasnoyarsk Krai). A coniferous extract was obtained from the green phytomass of fir and demonstrated antioxidant activity, in contrast to florentine water, which exhibited prooxidant properties. An increase in the shelf life of unfiltered fermented kvass by a factor of 4 at a temperature of 4 ± 2 °C under the influence of 1% aqueous fir extract has been demonstrated, which enhances the economic efficiency of kvass production.

Keywords: fermented kvass, fir extract, florentine water, antioxidant activity, prooxidants, shelf life.

Kvass belongs to a group of fermented grain-based products obtained through alcoholic and lactic acid fermentation. At present, kvass has not only retained but also strengthened its position among the most sought-after food products, with consumption occurring year-round. The technology for producing kvass is continuously developing, utilizing both traditional and innovative recipes of kvass (bread, fruit, berry, vegetable, spicy, etc.) [1]. According to Rosstat data (Fig. 1), kvass production represents a dynamically developing segment of the non-alcoholic beverage market.

Figure 1 — Growth of kvass production in Russia from 2017 to 2025 (cited from [2])

Among the challenges and risks for this segment is the seasonal nature of the product, with peak consumption occurring during the summer period [3]. For example, following the hot summer season of 2024, during which product turnover doubled, many producers increased production volumes in advance in spring, anticipating a similarly hot summer in 2025. However, Siberian weather is difficult to predict, resulting in a significant portion of the products spoiling. Therefore, the development of technologies to extend product shelf life, thereby protecting the market from unavoidable volatility, remains a relevant scientific and practical challenge.

Unfiltered, that is, unrefined, kvass has a minimal shelf life (two days) due to the presence of active microorganisms. Simultaneously, high consumer demand for the product marketed as ‘live kvass’ encourages producers to manufacture it and to continue searching for cost-effective and reliable technologies to extend its shelf life.

Such technologies include the use of stabilizing natural additives. Since the level of oxidation in kvass is determined by the rate of redox (oxidation-reduction) processes, the most promising additives are natural antioxidants that limit the content of active oxygen species (AOS) in the food system [4]. The metabolism of AOS, as well as antioxidants capable of regulating this process, are shown in the diagram (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 — Regulatory role of antioxidants in reactive oxygen species metabolism

The simultaneous presence of antioxidants with different mechanisms of action in a food system markedly enhances the effectiveness of their synergistic interaction. Coniferous biomass is a rich source of phenolic antioxidants [5]. Furthermore, during the processing of coniferous raw materials, secondary by-products with biological activity are produced, such as florentine water or hydrolate. This is an aromatic aqueous solution with a concentration of extractive substances (organic acids, phenols, terpenes) of 3 g/L, obtained during the production of essential oils by steam hydrodistillation [6].

Among the hydrophilic antioxidants of conifer biomass, the most active is the polyphenol dihydroquercetin (DHQ) [7]. This antioxidant functions through a reactive oxygen species (ROS) ‘trapping’ mechanism and is present in high concentrations in fir needles (Fig. 3).

Figure 3 — Content of dihydroquercetin in coniferous species (cited from: [8])

Despite the existing diversity of plant additives for kvass wort or finished kvass, coniferous extracts are not used in kvass brewing, despite the availability, off-season nature of the raw material, and the richness of its chemical composition. Phytoextracts of coniferous plants possess nutritional and prophylactic properties; therefore, there are no fundamental limitations on their use as additives to kvass.

The objective of the study was to determine the dynamics of quality and safety indicators of kvass under the influence of fir extract as a source of antioxidants.

The tasks of the study included obtaining fir extract; evaluating its antioxidant properties in comparison with Florentine fir water; investigating the dynamics of kvass quality indicators under the influence of fir extract and Florentine fir water; analyzing the organoleptic properties of kvass with additions of fir extract and Florentine water.

Materials and Methods. The study utilized commercial samples of unfiltered double-fermented kvass ‘Homemade’ (LLC ‘Vkus’, Krasnoyarsk Krai). Table 1 presents the product quality indicators.

Table 1 — Quality indicators of ‘Homemade’ kvass (LLC ‘Vkus’)

Indicator	Dry matter, %	Alcohol, vol%	Acidity, oH	Protein	Sugar
	5,54	0,62	2,44	1,05	9,15
GOST 31494-2012	from 3.5	up to 1.2	1,5...7	0...1,5	5...10

The data in the table indicate that ‘Homemade’ kvass (LLC ‘Vkus’) meets quality standards.

Fir phytomass was collected in the ecologically favorable Yemelyanovsky District (Krasnoyarsk agglomeration, September 2025). To prepare the extract, the coniferous raw material was separated from the branches, ground, and subjected to multiple undifferentiated hot water extractions using a separatory funnel. The extract was used immediately after cooling to 20°C. The study employed commercial Florentine water from LLC “Ekovit” (TU 9185-011-44601108-2010).

The organoleptic evaluation of kvass was carried out in accordance with the regulations (GOST 28188-89; GOST ISO 13302-2017) and expressed in points. The redox balance of the system was assessed by the chemiluminescent analysis method [9]. The device ‘Biochemiluminometer’ (SCTB ‘Nauka’, Krasnoyarsk), featuring automated counting and recording of the total photon counts (thousands of impulses) over the observation period ($T=120$ s), was utilized. Antioxidant activity was expressed in ORAC units (Oxygen Radical Absorbance Capacity, %) [10, 11]. In this study, ORAC was calculated as the difference between the control (100%) and the normalized value of the light sum (%). Verification of the research results was ensured by triplicate experimental repeats and statistical processing using the Student’s t-test ($p < 0.05$).

Results and Discussion. Figure 1 presents the results of the antioxidant activity assessment of fresh ‘Homemade’ kvass without additives, as well as fir water extract and Florentine water.

Figure 4 — Antioxidant activity of the samples

The presented figure shows that kvass and fir extract exhibited significant antioxidant activity, as the samples reduced free radical production in the model system by 3.6 times (‘Homemade’ kvass, ORAC=72%) and 5.4 times (fir extract, ORAC=82%). Meanwhile, Florentine water demonstrated a strong pro-oxidant

effect (twice that of the control). The ORAC indicator in this case is not meaningful; therefore, the light sum indicator was used for comparison of values.

The selection of the optimal dose for additive incorporation into the food system was conducted using organoleptic analysis (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 — Organoleptic profiles of kvass with coniferous additives

The figure shows that the best result corresponded to the kvass sample with the addition of 1% fir extract, whereas the addition of Florentine water reduced the flavor of the beverage irrespective of the dose. This is apparently explained by the predominance of pro-oxidant components in the composition of Florentine water, whereas antioxidants predominate in the fir extract composition. In industrial conditions, the formation of the specified 1% concentration is achieved by the dilution rule according to the law of equivalents $C1V1 = C2V2$; specifically, for every 1000 liters of kvass, 5 liters of extract with a dry matter concentration of 20% must be added.

Figure 6 presents the dynamics of the antioxidant capacity of 'Homemade' kvass with the addition of 1% coniferous extracts.

The figure shows that in the absence of additives, the ORAC value remains stable for the first two days, after which it begins to decrease. The addition of Florentine water accelerates this decline, consistent with the observed prooxidant effect of this sample. Conversely, under the influence of fir extract, the ORAC value remains stable for 172 hours (7 days), exceeding the regulated storage duration by 3.5 times.

Conclusion

1. Coniferous extracts exhibited bidirectional activity toward free radicals. Fir extract exhibited antioxidant properties (free radical production in the model system decreased by 5.4-fold), whereas Florentine fir water showed pro-oxidant effects (free radical production increased by 2.2-fold).

2. Kvass supplemented with fir extract at the minimal concentration (1%) received a higher organoleptic rating than that with 4% extract. The addition of Florentine water reduced the beverage flavor regardless of concentration.

3. The addition of 1% fir extract, containing a mixture of antioxidants with different mechanisms of action, increased the shelf life of commercial unfiltered unclarified kvass from two to seven days. Florentine water, in contrast, accelerates the oxidative spoilage of kvass.

Figure 6 — The effect of additives on the dynamics of antioxidant capacity of unfiltered fermented kvass “Domashniy” during storage.

References

1. Pchelkina, V. A. Analysis of antioxidant potential and investigation of microstructural features of selected spice species used in the meat processing industry / V. A. Pchelkina, N. V. Kupaev // *Theory and Practice of Meat Processing*. — 2023. — No. 4. — Pp. 289-301.
2. Beverages in Russia: materials from the website www.tadviser.ru/ 04.07.2025/ [Electronic resource] (Accessed 23.02.2026).
3. Cherëmushkina, I. V. Features of consumption of non-alcoholic juice-containing functional beverages and their role in human nutrition / I. V. Cherëmushkina, O. V. Oseneva, I. A. Sukhareva // *T PPP APK*. — 2025. — No. 1. — Pp. 40-52.
4. Lesovskaya, M. I. Antioxidant activity of various fruit extracts depending on their concentration and extraction conditions / M. I. Lesovskaya, I. S. Savchuk, I. D. Rakhimov / *In the collection: Scientific and practical aspects of the development of the agro-industrial complex. Materials of the National Scientific Conference*. — Krasnoyarsk, 2020. — pp. 16-21.

5. Leontyeva, N. V. *Flavonoids — natural antioxidants* / N. V. Leontieva // *Current Issues in Theoretical and Clinical Medicine*. — 2024. — No. 1. — pp. 45-50.

6. Kaisinova, A. S. *Florentine waters (fir and pine) of the trademark “Ekovit Siberian Coniferous Doctor” in the treatment of patients with diseases of the respiratory, digestive, and genitourinary systems* / A. S. Kaisinova, A. V. Kokareva, T. B. Menshikova // *Physiotherapy, Balneology, and Rehabilitation*. — 2019. — No. 3. — pp. 210-215.

7. Usoltseva, O. N. *Evaluation of the Quality and Biological Activity of Biodihydroquercetin* / O. N. Usoltseva, D. N. Olennikov, T. V. Potupchik // *Pharmacy*. — 2022. — No. 8. — pp. 5-14.

8. Gavrilov, A. B. *Composition of Polyphenols in Biomaterials of Russian Conifer Species* / A. B. Gavrilov, S. I. Goryainov, A. A. Marinichev, N. N. Gessler, O. I. Klein, E. P. Isakova, Y. I. Deryabina // *Chemistry of Plant Raw Materials*. — 2019. — No. 2. — pp. 51-58.

9. Lesovskaya, M. I. *The Influence of Nutrients on the Free Radical Balance of Blood in vitro* / M. I. Lesovskaya. — Moscow, 2015. — 94 p.

10. Garrett, A. R. *Measuring antioxidant capacity using the ORAC and TOSC assays*. / A. R. Garrett, B. K. Murray, R. A. Robison, L. O’Neill Kim. — In: *Armstrong Donald. Advanced Protocols in Oxidative Stress II // Methods in Molecular Biology. Humana Press*. — 2010; 594: 251-62.

11. Mazhaeva T. V. *Assessment of Antioxidant Levels in the Diet of Workers Exposed to Heavy Metals at an Industrial Enterprise* / T. V. Mazhaeva, S. E. Dubenko, I. A. Chirkova // *Hygiene and Sanitation*. 2016; 95 (2): 165-167. DOI: 10.18821/0016-9900-2016-95-2-165-167.

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CORRELATION IN MOTHER-DAUGHTER PAIRS

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Abstract. *In order to determine the effect of the ability to transfer the productive qualities of sows from mother to daughter, depending on the duration of the service period, 4 groups of sows were formed. The analysis of the correlation relationships between reproductive indicators (pregnancy, multiple births, and lactation duration) in sows and their daughters in four groups differentiated by the duration of the service period indicates that negative correlations prevail between all indicators in both mothers and mother-daughter pairs with a short service period (5-9 days). With an extended service period (22-32 days), there are also predominantly negative correlations between multiple births and lactation, but there is a positive correlation between the service period and gestation.*

Keywords: *duration, service period, negative, positive, correlations, mother-daughter pairs, multiple births, lactation, gestation.*

Introduction. In conducting breeding work in maternal breeds, considerable attention is paid to the reproductive traits of sows, such as multiple pregnancy and the number of piglets obtained from a sow during her utilization period [1 pp. 66-70; 7 pp. 19-21]. According to Hart and Ogden (1970), Howarth and Williams (1972), and Hart and Begon (1982), lifespan per se does not play a role, but the duration of the animal's breeding use is significant, as its increase leads to a rise in the number of reproductive acts. Particularly significant in this context is the ability of mothers to transmit their best qualities to their daughters.

Aim and objectives of the research. The aim of this research was to establish the patterns of transmission of reproductive traits in mother-daughter pairs.

The objectives of the research included: evaluating sows based on productivity; investigating the reproductive potential of sows depending on the duration of the service period, and performing a correlation analysis of reproductive traits in sow pairs of ‘Mother-Daughter’.

Materials and Methods. The studies were conducted on sows at the Lozoe Breeding Complex in the Tyumen region. Data from the database of the ASS software package (Automated Systems in Swine Breeding) were analyzed. The following parameters were investigated: number of farrowings and number of piglets obtained. Sows were divided into 5 groups according to age and number of farrowings from the first to the fifth. Data processing was performed using M. Excel.

Research Results. To determine the influence of the ability to transmit productive traits from mother sows to their daughters depending on the duration of the service period, 4 groups of sows were formed. The scheme for group formation is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 — Grouping of sows according to the duration of the service period.

Experimental group number	Service period duration, days	Number of pairs
Group I	Mother (22-32 days) — Daughter (5-9 days)	17
Group II	Mother (5-9 days) — Daughter (22-32 days)	27
Group III	Mother-Daughter (5-9 days)	43
Group IV	Mother-Daughter (22-32 days)	18

It should be noted that the use of correlation relationships also facilitates the selection of traits for breeding and enables the development of methods to enhance productivity. In this regard, we examined the effect of service period duration on the length of pregnancy, multiple pregnancy, and the lactation period in mothers, daughters, and in mother-daughter pairs. The significance of the correlation coefficients was assessed using Student’s t-test. The correlation relationships are presented as diagrams in Figure 1. It was established that in Group I, mothers with an extended service period (22-32 days) showed positive correlations with pregnancy duration ($r = 0.21$), multiple pregnancy ($r = 0.27$), and lactation ($r = 0.11$). Positive correlations were also observed between mother-daughter pairs for service period and pregnancy ($r = 0.19$), multiple pregnancy ($r = 0.32$), and lactation ($r = 0.25$). It should be noted that the daughters in these pairs exhibited a short service period (5-9 days), and negative correlations were observed between the duration of the service period and gestation length ($r = -0.45$), as well as lactation duration ($r = -0.23$). A slight positive correlation was identified between the duration of the service period and multiple pregnancy ($r = 0.02$).

Figure 1 — Correlation relationships between the duration of the service period and reproductive traits of mothers and daughters.

In the second group, among mothers with a shortened service period (5-9 days), negative correlations are observed between all analyzed traits. For example, between the short service period and pregnancy ($r = -0.27$), multiple pregnancy ($r = -0.21$), and lactation period ($r = -0.18$). In daughters from these pairs, the service period was prolonged (22-32 days), and a weak positive correlation with the duration of pregnancy was observed ($r = 0.10$). Negative correlations were observed with multiple pregnancy ($r = -0.23$) and lactation duration ($r = -0.18$). Analysis of Mother — Daughter pairs identified the following correlation patterns: a pronounced negative association with gestation length ($r = -0.36$); with multiple pregnancy ($r = -0.34$); and a slight positive correlation with lactation period duration ($r = 0.07$).

In Group III, the service period duration was 5-9 days for both mothers and daughters. The correlation relationships differ in the magnitude of their strength compared to the previously analyzed groups. In mothers, negative correlations were recorded between a short service period and the duration of the gestation period ($r = -0.07$); with the multiple pregnancy index ($r = -0.08$); and with the duration of lactation ($r = -0.22$). In daughters, a pronounced negative correlation was observed between a short service period and the duration of the gestation period ($r = -0.31$), a weak positive correlation with multiple pregnancy ($r = 0.08$), and a significant negative correlation with the duration of lactation ($r = -0.41$). The analysis of Mother — Daughter pairs revealed the following characteristics of correlation dependencies: the service period and pregnancy duration exhibit an inverse relationship with a correlation coefficient of -0.21 ; a slight positive association was observed for multiple pregnancy at 0.02 and for lactation duration at 0.13 .

In group IV, during an extended rest period (22-32 days), negative correlations were recorded for multiple pregnancy in mothers ($r = -0.18$) and daughters ($r = -0.26$), as well as for lactation period in mothers ($r = -0.08$) and daughters ($r = -0.35$). Moreover, a positive correlation was identified between prolonged service period and gestation length in mothers ($r = 0.32$) and daughters ($r = 0.21$). In the analysis of 'Mother-Daughter' pairs, negative correlations were found between extended service period and gestation length ($r = -0.25$), and multiple pregnancy ($r = -0.16$). A positive correlation was noted with lactation period ($r = 0.23$).

Conclusion. The conducted analysis indicates a relationship between the duration of the service period and the length of gestation. Thus, an increase in the duration of the service period leads to a decrease in the gestation period, characterized by negative correlations of $r = -0.31$ in daughters. The effect of rest period duration on multiple pregnancy has been noted; with an increase in this period, there is a decrease in the number of live-born piglets, with $r = -0.18$ and $r = -0.26$. A negative impact of the service period duration on the shortening of the lactation period has also been established, with correlations of $r = -0.8$ and -0.35 . The influence of a short service period on the duration of gestation, the number of live-born piglets, and the duration of the lactation period is insignificant, with r ranging from -0.08 to 0.11 . The analysis of correlation relationships between reproductive traits (pregnancy, multiple pregnancy, lactation duration) in sows and their daughters, differentiated by service period duration, indicates that with a short service period (5-9 days), negative correlations predominate among all traits, both in mothers and in Mother — Daughter pairs. With an extended service period (22-32 days), predominantly negative correlations are also observed for multiple pregnancy and lactation, but a positive correlation appears between service period and pregnancy. Daughters in all groups exhibit greater variability in correlation coefficients: in group III, daughters display stronger negative correlations with pregnancy ($r = -0.31$) and lactation ($r = -0.41$) compared to mothers; in group IV, daughters show more significant negative correlations for prolificacy ($r = -0.26$) and lactation ($r = -0.35$) compared to mothers. It was determined that correlations for prolificacy are negative and generally stronger in daughters.

Thus, the duration of the service period significantly affects the nature and strength of correlations between reproductive traits in sows and their offspring. The obtained data emphasize the necessity of a differentiated approach to reproductive management that takes into account the duration of the service period. The results of the study highlight the importance of considering the service period as a key factor in the selection for multiple pregnancy and lactation duration. Optimization of the service period may be an effective strategy for improving reproductive traits in animals and increasing their productivity.

References

1. Tretyakova O. L., Solonnikova V. S., Fedin G. I. Management of the reproduction cycle of sows. *Our agriculture*. 2025. No. 18 (362). Pp. 66-70. https://www.elibrary.ru/query_results.asp?pagenum=6
2. Rachkov I. G. Intensification of reproduction and increase in productivity of pigs using biotechnological techniques. Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Agricultural Sciences in the specialty 06.02.10-private animal husbandry and technology of production of livestock products. 2012, Stavropol. — 303 p.
3. Sein O. B. Physiological features of the formation of sexual function in pigs / O. B. Sein, D. O. Sein. — Kursk: Publishing House of the Kursk State Agricultural Academy, 2010. — 295 p.
4. Fedorova M. I. Productivity of sows in the conditions of the Voronezh region. In the collection: *Theory and practice of innovative technologies in the agro-industrial complex. Materials of the national scientific and practical conference. Voronezh, 2024*. Pp. 431-433. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=46954917>
5. Khlopitsky V. P. Symptomatic infertility of sows in industrial-type enterprises and pharmacological correction of their reproductive function. Dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Veterinary Sciences in the specialty 06.02.06, 2014, Voronezh. — 357 p.
6. Tsikunova O. G. Influence of the age of sows on their reproductive qualities // *Actual problems of intensive development of animal husbandry*. 2016. No. 19 (2). Pp. 36-42 URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/vliyanie-vozrasta-svinomatok-na-ih-voisproizvoditelnye-kachestva>.
7. Chebykina A. A., Ukrozhenko D. S. Factors Affecting the Longevity and Productivity of Pregnant Sows. In the collection: *The First Step into Big Science. Collection of Articles from the II International Research Competition. Petrozavodsk, 2023*. Pp. 52-60. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?edn=lpsvse>

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GENETIC EVALUATION OF BULLS AND ACTUAL PRODUCTIVITY OF THEIR DAUGHTERS

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Abstract. *A comparative analysis of the genetic evaluation of bulls' daughters and their actual productivity was conducted using the IAS "SELEX" and the predictive evaluation based on the calculation of indices. As a result of the research, it was found that the daughters of the bull Alta Olaf will have an increase in milk yield of 910 pounds or 413.14 kg compared to the Holstein breed basis. It should be noted that the same prediction is given for the bull Break Even positive on the milk yield of daughters + 862.12 pounds or +391.40 kg. It is assumed that the lactation of daughters will be longer by 3.43 months. When comparing the actual productivity, the superiority of the daughters of the bulls of the Reflection Sovereign line over the daughters of the Vis Back Ideal line and the average indicators of the herd was noted. In the first lactation, the daughters of Reflection Sovereign bulls exceeded the average by 1309.64 kg, while the daughters of Vis Back Ideal bulls exceeded the average by 439.27 kg, with 56.37 kg and 22.24 kg of milk fat and 40.35 kg and 8.69 kg of milk protein, respectively.*

Keywords: *genetic evaluation, bulls, Vis Back Ideal line, Reflection Sovereign line, productivity, daughters, lifetime profit index, milk productivity index, productive longevity index, actual productivity.*

Introduction. The efficiency of dairy farming largely depends on the accelerated and accurate determination of the breeding value of sires and their rational use in herd reproduction across the country's regions. Zhekamukhov M.Kh., Petrukhi-na L. L., Belozertseva S. L., Kuznetsov A. I., Denisenko L. V., Kuznetsov N. A.,

Rusanov A. N., Ponomaryova E. A., Yanchukov I. N., Aysanov Z. M., Lepyokhina T. V., Kosyachenko N. M., Abramova M. V., et al. It is emphasized that in the Russian Federation, foreign genetic resources have been widely used over the past 25-30 years to improve dairy cattle productivity. [1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 9, 11]

However, in recent years, scientists have observed a decline in genetic progress within herds. [6] This is largely due to the complexity of bull evaluation using the 'Interbull-MEYS' system, which is based on the genomic evaluation of bulls and includes more than 40 indices and sub-indices. [2,5]

Under current economic conditions, Russian milk producers find it difficult to compare the productivity levels of domestic livestock with those of animals in the USA and Canada. At domestic enterprises, it is much more important to control the use of bulls with high genetic potential by comparing this potential with the realized effect in their offspring at specific breeding reproducers and breeding farms. [6,9]

In this regard, a comparative analysis of genomic evaluation and the realized effect of Holstein bulls' daughters under the conditions of a particular enterprise becomes relevant.

Methods and principles of the study. Scientific research was conducted within the framework of the thematic plan for R&D at FSBEI HE "Don State Agrarian University" for 2021-2025. Under topic 11, 'Development of methods to increase the genetic potential of dairy and beef cattle breeds on farms of various ownership forms,' in accordance with the 'Strategy for Socio-Economic Development of the Rostov Region until 2025,' experimental studies were conducted on the Holstein cattle population at SPK "Kolos," Matveyevo-Kurgansky District, Rostov Region.

Artificial insemination was performed using semen from breeding bulls with genomic evaluations, obtained from FSUE CSIO "Moscow," LLC "Genetika Yug," and LLC "Alta Genetics." Genetic analysis of the bulls was carried out based on 396 daughters; 150 daughters possess a genomic passport and were evaluated according to the fertility index, calving ease, lifetime profit index, fat and protein content in milk, somatic cell count in milk, and productive longevity. Zootechnical and breeding records at the reproduction center are maintained using the information-analytical system (IAS) "SELEKS" (developed by LLC "RC "PLINOR"). Data processing was performed using statistical and mathematical analysis methods incorporated in the software M. Excel.

Main research results. At the reproduction center of SPK "Kolos", semen from bulls of two Holstein cattle lines is used: the Wis Beck Ideal line and the Reflection Sovereign line. All bulls have genetic evaluations (predictions developed by the Holstein Association of the USA) according to the "Interbull-MACE" system [10]. The results are presented in Figures 1-2.

Figure 1 — Genetic evaluation of sires according to the ‘Interbull-MEYS’ system

(NMS lifetime net merit index, PTAM milk production index).

Figure 2 — Genetic evaluation of sires according to the ‘Interbull-MEYS’ system (PTAF, fat, % — milk fat content; PTAT, protein, % — milk protein content).

The value of the genetic index NMS\$, calculated by the U. S. Council on Dairy Cattle Breeding (CDCB), determines the expected lifetime profit a cow will generate relative to the population base. The proportion of traits within the index is typically updated approximately every five years. PTAM — milk yield, the expected genetic difference in the milk yield of a bull’s daughters, expressed in US pounds. Steve Schnell and Jenny Bjelland explain, ‘... the PTAM milk yield indicator reflects the forecast

of the expected milk productivity of the bull's future adult daughters, expressed in pounds of milk, + (more), — (less) than the base levels. In the present article, the 2024 base is used: average figures for the USA: milk productivity 11,583 kg, fat (PTAF) 444 kg \approx 3.83%, protein (PTAT) 366 kg \approx 3.16%, PL — 0, SCS — 3 points — (62 thousand units/ml). It has been established that the daughters of the bull Alta Olaf 3150701313 will have an increase in milk yield of 910 pounds or 413.14 kg compared to the 2024 baseline for the Holstein breed, with a decrease in fat content by 0.02% and protein by 0.002%. It should be noted that the same forecast is given for the bull Break-Even 3209641335 — positive for daughters' milk yield (+862.12 pounds or +391.40 kg) and for protein (+0.03%), and negative for fat content in daughters' milk (–0.006%). It is assumed that the lactation period of daughters will be extended by 3.43 months. The forecast for the productivity of the daughters of bull Fortnite 3200824963 is generally positive, showing an increase in milk yield by 191.10 pounds (86.75 kg), an increase in fat content by 0.09%, protein by 0.03%, and a lengthening of lactation by 2.2 months compared to daughters of bulls with '0' indices. Significant individual variations in productivity indicators were observed among daughters of different bulls, particularly in the fat content of milk. As an example, the evaluation (prediction) graphs of Alta Olaf's daughters are presented (Fig. 3).

Figure 3 — Genetic evaluation of the daughters of the bull Alta Olaf.

Thus, the daughter of bull Alta Olaf 3150701313 with individual number 1901 ranks first by the lifetime profit index, yet she ranks 30th by the milk profit index, 4th by the fat yield index, 14th by the protein yield index, and 3rd by the productive longevity index. The daughter of ind. № 1856 holds 1st rank according to the milk profit index; however, according to the lifetime profit index, she is ranked 11th, according to the fat content index 28th, according to the protein content index 27th,

and according to the productive longevity index 29th. Regarding the fat content in the milk of daughters, a positive forecast was noted only for all daughters of the bull Break-Even 3209641335.

Similarly, daughters of bulls from the Reflection Sovereign line were evaluated; graphical analysis identified the 20 top-ranking daughters according to the indices. Daughters of the bull Dandy 2288, ind. № 1702, 1760, and 1733 have high ranks according to the lifetime profit index; according to the milk productivity index, daughter № 1760 ranks 1st, № 1702 ranks 14th, and № 1733 ranks 22nd; however, according to the PTAF (fat) index, she holds 4th rank, and according to the PL (productive longevity) index, 1st rank. Daughters of the bull Beyond 0987, № 1721, 1591, and 1593 have high ranks according to the lifetime profit index; according to the milk productivity index, № 1591 ranks 1st, № 1721 ranks 3rd, and № 1593 ranks 14th.

The obtained data on the productivity levels of bulls' daughters are difficult to interpret at the level of a specific farm; therefore, the evaluation was analyzed based on the actual data obtained from each daughter. The superiority of daughters of the Reflection Sovereign bull line over daughters of the Wis Back Ideal line and the herd average was noted, both overall for the line and for individual sires. Thus, in the first lactation, daughters of bulls from the Reflection Sovereign line exceed the herd average by 1309.64 kg, and their peers from the Wis Back Ideal line by 439.27 kg in milk yield; in milk fat by 56.37 kg and 22.24 kg, and in milk protein by 40.35 kg and 8.69 kg, respectively. The bull Alta Tarnkey has daughters characterized by a prolonged period of use — 5 lactations with high productivity indicators: 11,767.05 kg milk yield over 305 days of lactation, 464.79 kg milk fat, and 390.66 kg milk protein, exceeding the average herd milk yield by 1,225.95 kg, milk fat by 53.69 kg, and milk protein by 44.91 kg, respectively. Significant variability in dairy productivity traits is observed among daughters of individual sires and lactations. Thus, in the first lactation, daughters of the bull Alta Tarnkey exceed the herd average by 864.18 kg, daughters of Alta Admiral by 1170.66 kg, daughters of Break-Even by 684.18 kg, daughters of Fortnite by 577.17 kg, and daughters of Alta Olaf by 749.57 kg, respectively. The fat content in the milk of daughters during the first two lactations changes insignificantly, whereas an increase is observed in the 3rd and 4th lactations. Regarding the daughters of bulls: VH Finish at 0.19%, Beyond at 0.08%, Alta Admiral at 0.16%, Alta Olaf at 0.36%, Break-Even at 0.46% compared to the herd average. The variability in protein content of the milk of bulls' daughters is insignificant.

Discussion. The Interbull-MEIS system enables the comparison of bulls across various indices. [2,5] Many researchers emphasize that the improvement of dairy cattle over the past 25-30 years has been carried out using diverse genetic material, including both domestic and imported bulls, predominantly of American, Canadian, and European origin. The replacement of the breeding stock in farms of the Russian Federation during

this period was also conducted through the importation of heifers and young cows from various countries. Thus, Kuznetsov A. V., Kosyachenko N. M., Abramova M. V., et al. in their works state that ‘... the transnational Holstein breed is bred in 163 countries with different objectives of animal selection and breeding programs.’ Therefore, there arises a need for genetic analysis and evaluation of productive potential within specific structural elements — breed and zonal types, micropopulations. [3, 6, 7, 11] It should be emphasized that, in terms of breeding work with the Holstein cattle population in the Russian Federation until 2030, among the prioritized tasks remains the improvement of animal evaluation methods, the development of a selection index, and the monitoring of selection indicators in the country’s breeding farms.

Conclusion. The analysis conducted allowed the identification of bulls that influence an increase in the milk yield of their daughters by more than 1300 kg in the first lactation compared to their contemporaries. Thus, in the Wis Back Ideal line — Alta Admiral 3014562353, and in the Reflection Covering line — Rodeo 6947, Beyond 0987, Alta Carey 8894. The breeding work to improve milk productivity in the population of the SPC “Kolos” in the Matveyevo-Kurgan district of the Rostov region must take into account not only the evaluation of sire bulls according to the Interbull-MEIS system but also the actual realized productivity potential of the bulls’ daughters. Thus, the comprehensive evaluation of breeding bulls in zonal populations of Holstein cattle may hold both practical and theoretical significance, as it can form the basis for the extensive use and identification of animals for breeding purposes, for more intensive utilization of highly valuable individuals, and for adjusting selection efforts based on evaluation results.

References

1. Alekseeva A. Yu. *Sravnitel'naya effektivnost' ispol'zovaniya by'kov-proizvoditelej golshtinskoj porody' razlichnogo proisxozhdeniya v plemzavodax Leningradskoj oblasti.* [Comparative efficiency of using Holstein bulls of different origin in breeding farms of the Leningrad Region.] PhD dissertation in 06.02.07: defended 2017-10-12; approved 2018-05-26 / A. Yu. Alekseeva. — Moscow: 2017. — 148 p. [in Russian]

2. *Genome-based assessment of the breeding value of Black-and-White dairy cows based on a combination of milk production and fertility traits / F. S. Sharko // Genome-based assessment of the breeding value of Black-and-White dairy cows based on a combination of milk production and fertility traits.* — 2022. — № 1. — URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/genomnaya-otsenka-plemennytsennosti-molochnyh-korov-chno-pestroy-porody-po-sovokupnosti-priznakov-molochnoy-produktivnosti-i>. (accessed: 27.01.26) doi: 10.32607/actanaturae.11648 [in Russian]

3. Kosyachenko N. M. Golshtinskaya poroda v sozdanii uluchshenny'x genotipov i vnutriporodny'x tipov krupnogo rogatogo skota [Holstein breed in the creation of improved genotypes and intra-breed types of cattle] / N. M. Kosyachenko, M. V. Abramova, A. V. Il'ina et al. — Yaroslavl': OOO "Kanczler", 2020. — 157 p. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44821251>. (accessed: 27.01.26). [in Russian]

4. Zhekamuxov M. X. Using the gene pool of American and Austrian breeding bulls to improve the herd of the Kabardinsky Breeding Farm [Using the gene pool of American and Austrian breeding bulls to improve the herd of the Kabardinsky Breeding Farm] PhD dissertation: 06.02.04: defended on 2000-01-27: approved on 2000-08-27 / M. X. Zhekamuxov. — Nalchik: 2000. — 144 p. — URL: https://www.elibrary.ru/author_items.asp?authorid=912821&pubrole=100&show_refs=1&pubcat=risc. (accessed: 27.01.26). [in Russian]

5. Kislyakova E. M. Ispol'zovanie rezul'tatov genomnoj ocenki v selekcii krupnogo rogatogo skota [Using genomic evaluation results in cattle breeding] / E. M. Kislyakova, Yu. V. Yusupova, V. Yu. Yakimova et al. // Dairy and beef cattle farming. — 2023. — № 5. — P. 35-39. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=54785910> (accessed: 27.01.26). — DOI: 10.33943/MMS.2023.45.81.007 [in Russian]

6. Kuznecov A. V. Baza sushhestvuyushhej sistemy' ocenki produktivnosti krupnogo rogatogo skota otechestvenny'x molochny'x porod [The basis of the existing system for evaluating the productivity of domestic dairy cattle] / A. V. Kuznecov, O. N. Lukonina // Dairy and beef cattle farming. — 2025. — № 1. — P. 12-19. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=80478942> (accessed: 27.01.26). — DOI: 10.33943/MMS.2025.76.49.003 [in Russian]

7. Lepyoshina T. V. Prognozirovanie plemennoj cennosti proizvoditelej po priznakam molochnoj produktivnosti ix docherej [Prediction of the breeding value of producers based on the milk productivity of their daughters] / T. V. Lepyoshina, F. R. Bakaj, O. Yu. Papurina // Zootechnics. — 2022. — № 7. — P. 4-8. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=49503495> (accessed: 26.01.26). — DOI: 10.25708/ZT.2022.58.91.002 [in Russian]

8. Lepyoxina T. V. Realizaciya geneticheskogo potenciala molochnoj produktivnosti docherej otdel'ny'x by'kov-proizvoditelej v stade Vologodskoj oblasti [Realization of the genetic potential of the milk productivity of the daughters of individual bulls in the herd of the Vologda Region] / T. V. Lepyoxina // Zootechnics. — 2023. — № 7. — P. 2-6. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=54604383> (accessed: 26.01.26). — DOI: 10.25708/ZT.2023.77.67.001 [in Russian]

9. Petruxina L. L. *Vliyanie plemennoj cennosti by'kov proizvoditelej i produktivnosti ix materej na molochnuyu produktivnost' ix potomstva [The influence of the breeding value of bulls and the productivity of their mothers on the milk productivity of their offspring.] / L. L. Petruxina // Vestnik IrGSKHA. — 2020. — № 98. — P. 94-100. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=43419804> (accessed: 25.01.26). [in Russian]*

10. Fedorov V. X. *Ocenka genealogicheskoj struktury' stada korov golshhtinskoj porody' Rostovskoj oblasti [Evaluation of the genealogical structure of the herd of Holstein cows in the Rostov Region] / V. X. Fedorov, G. A. Karchava, O. L. Tret'yakova et al. // Bulletin of the Don State Agrarian University. — 2024. — № 2 (52). — P. 46-53. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=67960287> (accessed: 23.01.26). [in Russian]*

11. E'zergajl' K. V. *Ocenka molochnoj produktivnosti korov, po urovnyu kompleksnogo pokazatelya prognoziruemoj produktivnosti [Evaluation of the milk productivity of cows based on the level of the complex indicator of predicted productivity] / K. V. E'zergajl', V. A. Chuchunov. // In the collection: Innovative Technologies in the Production and Processing of Agricultural Products in the WTO Environment; edited by Volgogradskij gosudarstvenny'j texnicheskij universitet, GNU Povolzhskij NII proizvodstva i pererabotki myasomolochnoj produkcii Rossel'xozakademii — Volgograd, 04-05 Iyunya: VolgGTU, 2013. — P. 32-34. — URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25703543>. (accessed: 24.01.26). [in Russian]*

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